

D2.1 – The Social Contract: History, Theory, and Con- temporary Challenges

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Author(s):	AUP (editors): Nathanaël Colin-Jaeger
Reviewer(s):	CLS: Ruzha Smilova

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General Introduction

Nathanaël Colin-Jaeger (American University of Paris)

Social contract theories have a long history in political philosophy, offering a normative framework to justify the legitimacy of political authority, the obligations of citizens, and the structure of social arrangements. At its core, social contract theory seeks to answer fundamental questions: How should society be organized? What makes political coercion and social rules legitimate? Who has the right to rule? How to justify the right to exercise power? Traditionally, social contract theories—exemplified by the works of Hobbes, Locke, Rousseau, and Kant—have addressed these questions by positing a hypothetical agreement among idealized agents, often in a constructed "state of nature" or "original position," to derive principles of political obligation, legitimacy, or justice. These theories are increasingly encountering challenges when confronted with contemporary phenomena that strain their foundational assumptions and normative ambitions.

This deliverable makes three contributions. *First*, it proposes a general overview of social contract theories and fills some important gaps in the existing narrative on social contracts, most notably developing the ideas of sociological contracts. *Second*, it considers the existing challenges to social contract theories. Three challenges – of different nature – are of particular importance:

1. *The rise of non-national institutions*, such as the European Union, challenging one pre-commitment of social contract theories, i.e., focus on the nation-state.
2. *The rise of polarization*, in particular affective polarization, challenges the idea that individuals possess the empirical capacity to overcome deep disagreements and reach a substantial consensus on the rules of the game.
3. *The increasing importance of climate concerns*, militating for the enlargement of the scope of traditional social contract theories, focused on the interests of individual citizens and nation-states.

Third, it paves the way towards future works and deliverables, particularly D2.3, focusing on the difficulties of developing the CO3 model which emphasizes continuity, democracy and inclusiveness.

Overview of the Deliverable

In addition to developing a general overview of the history and theories of social contract (see the first contribution by Nathanaël Colin-Jaeger, AUP, and the contribution by Stephen Sawyer, AUP), this deliverable gives a particular place to the necessity of renovating and rejuvenating social contract theory. Four topics for contributions particularly highlight this necessity.

1. **The Rise of the EU and Global Governance.** The emergence of supranational entities like the European Union (EU) poses a profound challenge to traditional social contract theories, which were designed with the nation-state as the primary unit of political organization. As explored in the contribution "The EU Social Contract" (Claudia Wiesner, Fulda) the EU represents a unique political experiment that transcends methodological nationalism, raising questions about the applicability of social contract theory to a multi-level governance structure. Traditional theories assume a unified "demos" (a cohesive political community) as the basis for legitimate governance, yet the EU lacks a clear demos, grappling instead with questions of European identity, the relationship between treaties and constitutions, and the role of the welfare state in a supranational context. These issues highlight the need for social contract theories to account for continuous construction, empirical diversity, and the inclusion of non-traditional subjects (e.g., non-citizens, and future generations) in political decision-making.
2. **The Fallacy of Meritocracy and Social Justice.** Another significant challenge arises from the critique of underlying assumptions, such as the belief in meritocracy, which has been a cornerstone of modern liberal societies. The contribution "Normative Beliefs about Justice and the Social Contract in Europe" (Ruzha Smilova, CLS) critically examines the meritocratic ideal, which posits that social and economic inequalities are justified if they reflect differences in effort and talent. Drawing on empirical data from the European Social Survey (ESS), this contribution reveals a widespread normative belief in the "Equity principle" (that hard work should be rewarded), particularly in Central and Eastern Europe (CEE). However, it also highlights a growing mismatch between normative preferences for meritocracy and perceptions of its realization, especially in post-communist societies where corruption and nepotism undermine the ideal. This mismatch fuels distrust in political elites, erodes social cohesion, and weakens the social contract, as citizens perceive existing arrangements as unjust. Moreover, philosophical critiques, such as those by Michael Sandel, challenge the moral core of meritocracy, arguing that it fosters "meritocratic hubris" and neglects the role of luck, thus questioning the legitimacy of merit-based inequalities. These critiques underscore the need for social contract theories to incorporate more nuanced principles of justice, such as desert and recognition, and to address the tensions between meritocracy and democratic equality.
3. **Polarization, Hegemony and the Conditions of Social Agreement.** Polarization and hegemony pose serious challenges to traditional social contract theories, which assume a rational, static agreement among equals. Affective polarization—where emotional divides turn political opponents into existential threats—undermines the trust and consensus needed to legitimize authority. It disrupts collective problem-solving and questions the idea that reason alone can unite people under shared norms. Meanwhile, hegemony exposes how power shapes the social contract to favor dominant groups, often sidelining marginalized voices and skewing the agreement to reflect the interests of the powerful rather than a neutral consensus. These dynamics reveal the limitations of traditional theories, which fail to account for emotional realities and power imbalances. A modern social contract must evolve to address these issues by incorporating emotional and cultural factors, recognizing unequal power dynamics, and embracing ongoing renegotiation rather than a fixed deal. Insights from recent discussions, like those in Contributions 6 and 7, by Emilia Palonen (UH), Szilvia Horvath (UH) and Pinar Uyan Semerci (IBU) stress the need for a more inclusive, dynamic, and empirically informed approach. This renovation ensures the social contract remains relevant in a divided, power-stratified world, adapting to real human experiences rather than idealized assumptions.

4. **Idealization, Exclusion, and Stability.** The contribution "Towards a Resilient Social Contract" (Nathanaël Colin-Jaeger, AUP) highlights the tension between inclusivity, democracy, continuity, and stability, framing it as an "impossibility square." Traditional theories, with their focus on static equilibrium, struggle to accommodate the dynamic nature of modern societies, where new challenges (e.g., climate change, geopolitical tensions) and contestations (e.g., struggles for recognition) demand continuous adaptation.

List of the contributions

Contribution 1: Theories of Social Contract - An Overview (Nathanaël Colin-Jaeger, American University of Paris) traces the historical development from Hobbes to modern iterations, spotlighting gaps like the neglect of sociological perspectives and setting the stage for contemporary critique.

Contribution 2: Taking the Mapping Seriously (Nathanaël Colin-Jaeger, American University of Paris) presents a visualization methodology to compare social contract theories across dimensions like democracy and inclusivity, providing a systematic tool for identifying areas of improvement.

Contribution 3: Sociological Social Contracts (Stephen Sawyer, American University of Paris) challenges the idealized nature of traditional models by focusing on empirical realities—such as power dynamics—bridging normative theory and descriptive analysis.

Contribution 4: The EU Social Contract (Claudia Wiesner, Fulda University) explores how social contract theory applies to supranational entities like the EU, addressing governance beyond the nation-state and probing issues of identity and legitimacy.

Contribution 5: Normative Beliefs about Justice (Ruzha Smilova, Centre for Liberal Strategies) delivers empirical data on justice perceptions in Europe, particularly post-communist regions, enriching the discourse on meritocracy and fairness.

Contribution 6: Polarization, Hegemony (Emilia Palonen and Szilvia Horvath, University of Helsinki) uses hegemony theory to analyze how polarization stifles political plurality, offering a fresh lens on barriers to social agreement.

Contribution 7: Affective Polarization (Pinar Uyan Semerci, Istanbul Bilgi University) investigates how emotional divides weaken mutual regard and democratic legitimacy, identifying a critical obstacle to social cohesion.

Contribution 8: Towards a Resilient Social Contract (Nathanaël Colin-Jaeger, American University of Paris) proposes a framework balancing inclusivity, democracy, continuity, and stability, overcoming the limitations of static traditional models.

The Broader Aims of the CO3 Project

This deliverable serves as a critical and foundational step in the broader aims of the CO3 project, which seeks to renovate social contract theory to meet the demands of the 21st century. By identifying the limitations of traditional theories and proposing alternative frameworks, it paves the way

for future deliverables that will develop more positive, constructive theories of the social contract. Specifically, subsequent deliverables (e.g., D2.3; D3.1 and beyond) will focus on:

1. **Empirical Grounding:** Building on the empirical sensitivity emphasized in this deliverable, future work will incorporate case studies from EU countries to test and refine theoretical models, ensuring they are responsive to real-world diversity and contestation. This future work will also generate an understanding of how different social contracts are presently being challenged in the EU, and how these contestations could be met depending on different national contexts.
2. **Dynamic Models:** Future work will develop resilience-based models of the social contract, operationalizing concepts like adaptability, pluralism, and feedback loops to address new challenges (e.g., climate change, geopolitical tensions) and struggles for recognition. The relation between the long term, medium term and resilient social contracts, as developed more extensively in D2.2, directly refers to this future work, and WP5, dealing with polycrisis, will be the opportunity to develop fully the resilience framework announced in the last contributions of this deliverable.
3. **Normative Refinement:** Building on the critique of meritocracy and justice principles, future deliverables will propose renovated theories of justice that incorporate recognition, intergenerational considerations, and a theory coping with the tensions between different features of the CO3 project. Future WP and deliverables all participate, with a constant dialogue with empirical research, to refine the normative tenets of the CO3 framework.
4. **Deliberative Innovations:** As hinted in "Towards a Resilient Social Contract," future deliverables will explore the potential of deliberative democratic mechanisms—such as citizens' assemblies and mini-publics—to rejuvenate social contracts, making them more inclusive and democratic. As announced in D3.1, deliberative experiments are a way to meet the continuity, democratic and inclusive criteria.

In sum, *D2.1* offers a critical diagnosis of the challenges facing traditional social contract theories, while also providing a theoretical and methodological foundation for their renovation. By addressing empirical realities (e.g., the EU), normative critiques (e.g., meritocracy), and conceptual limitations (e.g., idealization and stability), it sets the stage for a more inclusive, democratic, continuous, and resilient social contract theory, which will be further developed in the CO3 project's subsequent phases. This work not only contributes to academic debates in political theory but also has practical implications for addressing contemporary crises of legitimacy, representation, and social cohesion in Europe.

Contribution 1: Theories of Social Contract. An Overview

Nathanaël Colin-Jaeger (American University of Paris).

Introduction

This contribution pursues two main objectives: (i) Providing a general roadmap of the history of social contract theories, distinguishing its main phases, based on recent scholarship; (ii) Proposing a mapping of the different options along several dimensions that are constitutive of the CO3 project: democratic/undemocratic; continuous/one shot; empirically sensitive/a priori; inclusive/exclusive; and the kind of theories of justice they promote.

The presentation follows this structure: Section 1 gives a general definition of social contract theories, what they are, and what they are for; Section 2 presents the seminal contributions of classic social contract theorists (Thomas Hobbes, John Locke, Jean-Jacques Rousseau, and Immanuel Kant); Section 3 devotes some space to John Rawls' contribution, which sparked the rebirth of social contract theories in the 1970s; Section 4 describes the two main sides emerging out of this Rawlsian moment: theories of fairness based on rational agreement and fairness as justification, exemplified by the works of David Gauthier, James Buchanan, Brian Barry and Thomas Scanlon; Section 5 presents how traditional assumptions of social contract theories were challenged by critical race theorists and feminist theorists, with the example of Charles Mills' and Carol Pateman's critiques; Section 6 explores a separate understanding of Social Contract Theory, based on David Hume's and Rousseau's insights, which challenges core assumptions of traditional and Rawlsian social contract theories, i.e., evolutionary social contracts; Section 7 provides a brief survey of recent contributions to the theoretical discussions on social contract theories, developed in the recent and important book *New Approaches to Social Contract Theories* (2024); Section 8 draws the consequences of this mapping and suggests avenues of research, as a conclusion.

This overview contributes to presenting the main developments of social contract theories, developing a standardized history of social contract theories. For this reason, I will mostly refer to the primary literature on the topic and only sparsely to the overabundant secondary literature on each other and social contract theories. Furthermore, social contract theories have gone in many different directions in the last decades. In this perspective, social contract theory is like any other category in the history of political thought: the difference between who is in and who is out might be hard to define definitively. There are good arguments to include, among many others, Richard Nozick's *Anarchy, State, and Utopia* (1974), Jürgen Habermas' *Faktizität und Geltung* (1992), Philip Van Parijs' *Real Freedom for All* (1995), or Gerald Gaus' *The Order of Public Reason* (2012) in the discussion. Although these authors will be mentioned in passing, this overview will not present their work specifically, focusing on work engaging more explicitly with social contract theories.

This contribution helps constitute the main options in the social contract literature and provides a first step toward developing a CO3 model. It paves the way to show how other contributions in this

Deliverable are contributing to the theory of social contract, adding new objects or concerns. In particular, Section 9 lays the groundwork for highlighting missing aspects of social contract theories, such as sociological social contract theories developed in the 19th century, anthropological elements of the social contract, and what kind of questions and objects could renew social contract theories, e.g., the case of the European Union, as well as what phenomenon may require us to modify the theory, e.g., rising polarization or relations of domination.

Social Contract Theories: What They Are, What They Are For. A Brief Survey of the Most Relevant Works.

Theories of social contract form the foundation of political philosophy. They seek to answer the following question: How should society be organized? How should power be divided? Who is to rule and why? These questions vary in extent, leading to different social contract theories.

Despite the diversity of social contract theories, which have led some to think that there cannot be a unified model of social contract (Boucher and Kelly, 1993, 2-3), two important aspects should be stressed. First, these questions are *normative*, which means that social contract theories help us answer the question of whether social arrangements are legitimate, and what they *should* be. Social contract theories do not describe how social arrangements emerged. They are not historical theories, although they can be enriched by history. Second, these theories are distinct from other theories seeking to answer the same questions. Indeed, social contract theories do not reach their conclusion based on transcendental grounds (as for God-based theories), they give instead an important role to individual consent, agreement, and negotiation.

Following Weale (2013, 8-9), we may offer the following general depiction of social contract theories:

[Social Contract theories] have a logical form in which agents negotiate the terms of their association with one another. Political associations are to be evaluated in terms of the principles to which such agents would agree. The agents are assumed to be rational in senses that different theorists specify in various ways, but as rational agents they are not only capable of entering into commitments with one another but also capable of having reasons for entering into those commitments consistent with a prudent concern for their own interests.

Social contract theories are therefore first and foremost devices of justification for a set of rules defining the form of political associations, and they help us define what is a just arrangement, respecting every individual, since political coercion should be exercised if and only if every individual has a good reason to accept this commitment. In short, social contract theories tell us why rules imply justified coercion when they are based on grounds one cannot refuse since these rules are the ones we would have chosen ourselves.

Here, it may be useful to provide a slightly formalized description of what social contract theories aim for, to clarify the variables at hand. Let us define N as the ideal individuals, choosing a set of rules R for a society. Social contracts often distinguish between idealized individuals and real individuals: rules are chosen by idealized individuals N in some ideal setting M , and the obligation

to abide by the rules applies to N^* , real individuals. Following D'Agostino et al. (2020), we may describe what social contract theory accomplishes like this:

N chooses R in M and this gives N^* reason to endorse and comply with R in the real world insofar as the reasons N has for choosing R in M can be shared by N^* .

Most of the differences between different social contract theories are a consequence of different ways of defining N and M : how do we idealize agents N ? What is their rationality? Are they reasonable? How do we idealize the choosing agents? How do we define the choice situation? Should it be the State of Nature, if yes—with what features? Should it be an original position, if yes—how should it be defined? With what kind of uncertainty/ignorance? How close should they be to real individuals? How far should contestations of real agents undermine the agreement of idealized agents? Different answers to these questions imply different conceptions of a just society and the rules individuals should abide by and may concern a different range of objects defining the content of social contract theory.

Furthermore, recent contributions, from the late 1980s onwards, tend to put into question this model—or rather its use in traditional and post-Rawlsian social contract theories. This is particularly the case for what I termed critical contract theories developed by Carole Pateman and Charles Mills, who offer a sustained critique of the idealization consubstantial to the model, putting into question the legitimacy of the rules (R) chosen in the choosing situation (M). One must consider this model as a benchmark to assess different contributions since even these critical contract theories refer implicitly to this model.

Traditional Social Contract Theories: Hobbes, Locke, Rousseau, Kant

Although some authors, such as Barry (1991, chap. 1), read statements of social contract theories in Plato, or later in Pufendorf and Grotius, the first systematic iterations of social contract theories occurred in the 17th and 18th centuries. *The Leviathan* (1651) by Thomas Hobbes; *The Second Treatise of Government* (1689) by John Locke, and *The Social Contract* (1762) by Jean-Jacques Rousseau, have been recognized for a long time as three major theorists in this tradition. More recently, *The Doctrine of Right* (1779) by Immanuel Kant, was also recognized as participating in classical contributions to social contract theories (Ripstein, 2009). Each of these works has generated a large amount of secondary literature and differs from one another in important respects. In this section, I will describe each theory separately and emphasize what they all share as a conclusion.

Hobbes' theory is built on a specific understanding of the baseline situation, i.e., the State of Nature. In *The Leviathan*, he famously describes the process leading from living a life in the State of Nature to a "War of all against all", based on equality of conditions and hopes, and fear of death allowing preventive strikes against others. The state of nature is a state of utter distrust, and no stable large-scale cooperation may emerge. As a consequence, while everybody would prefer peace, this situation leads everybody to war and mutual distrust. The social contract provides a solution for this dilemma: since everybody wants to enjoy security and social stability but cannot trust another person when contracting privately, individuals ought to surrender their natural rights, and institute one authority (a person, or an assembly) with the authority to enforce the initial contract and punish perpetrators. The Leviathan is this overarching authority, legitimized by the rational agreement of the individuals, who should not bring down their sovereign – albeit possessing absolute powers – since it was erected to secure their life and security to start with. The

social contract is the most fundamental contract of any society because it explains the condition of possibility and the legitimacy of any given social arrangement.

Leviathan is the first work of the genre and specifies the idealized agents (Ns) as rational agents in the State of Nature (M), above all interested in their survival and fear for their lives based on some anthropological assumptions. This leads real individuals (N^*) to generate obligations since the Leviathan (R) is legitimized based on the hypothetical agreement of Ns in M . As real individuals are assumed to share the reasons to endorse R , i.e., they value security and life, R is legitimate. The strength of Hobbes' demonstration is that once we accept the premises of his argument, we are condemned to accept his conclusion in support of absolute sovereignty. If the choice is between the – deadly and violent – State of Nature, and the existence of a Leviathan, the rational choice is always to choose the existence of the Leviathan because it allows cooperation, private contracting, and safety. Logically, any social order superior to the State of Nature is legitimate. Other social contract theories precisely differ in how they consider Ns and M , producing different theories of power legitimacy.

This is the case of Locke's theory, which identifies differently the State of Nature and individuals. In the *Second Treatise*, the State of Nature is described as allowing cooperation between individuals and is more peaceful than Hobbes'. The main reason is that individuals are not rational in the sense of Hobbes, but recognize the value of life, health, liberty, and property. This stems from their shared reason, which makes them recognize others as equals – for Locke because they all belong to God. Consequently, individuals are allowed to follow their plans, free from others' interference, which leads to a different baseline situation for the social contract to arise. Property, in particular, plays an important role in Locke's story, because it may exist in the State of Nature when individuals mix their labor with land. The situation of wars occurs precisely when there are conflicts over property, based on a situation of stealing or when someone is reduced to slavery by another. Since there is no civil power to protect property rights (on oneself and belongings), and to arbitrate competing claims, these situations will degenerate into war in the State of Nature. Note here that the situation of war is not the same as in Hobbes' theory: war is among individuals, but it is not a general state of war, since individuals could cooperate as well, especially within "conjugal societies". In this context, the rationale for the emergence of a civil government justified by consent is the preservation of pre-existing rights, through the formulation of laws, the existence of judges to adjudicate them, and the executive power to make them respected.

Since cooperation and property are already possible in the State of Nature, any civil power cannot be justified. For instance, a power that would not protect individuals' external property would be illegitimate and trigger a justified right of resistance. The Lockean social contract does not seek to secure security, but individual rights and property, which leads to very different desiderata for a legitimate state. The Ns and the M are defined in a very different fashion, this theory leads to accepting as legitimate a distinct set of social rules R to abide by such that real individuals N^* and the government ought to respect property rights as pre-political data. N^* shares with Ns reasons to respect R , given that both supposedly value private property and a sphere of autonomy from political power as vital requirements to their existence.

Social contract theories consequently always have implications for the current state of affairs and play a decisive normative role, imposing constraints on obligations and social arrangements. This is particularly clear in Rousseau's work, especially in *The Social Contract* – for another side of

Rousseau's theory, see the section below on evolutionary theories. The main question of the *Social Contract* is less about how civil society came to be possible and what implication it has, but how should it be made legitimate, such that individual liberty and social coexistence are possible. Rousseau's answer comes from the idea that in obeying made legitimate—the foundation of civil society—we only obey ourselves. When individuals abandon the State of Nature, they surrender their rights to a new person, the collective, or the general will. Since the general will aims and accomplishes the common good, individuals cannot decide whether or not they can fulfill their duties to the sovereign: being forced to be free is based on the idea that individuals have to be forced as private individuals to obey themselves as citizens. Rousseau's social contract seeks to achieve the alchemist's task of transmuting private interests into common good.

For Rousseau, the formation of the general will entails the participation of every citizen in a general assembly, to decide the set of rules defining their social arrangements, which leads to unanimous agreement of citizens based on their public interests. Contrary to Hobbes or Locke, the Ns are not the idealized individuals in the State of Nature, but citizens enlightened by the public interest in an assembly situation (M)—even though individuals aggregate their judgments rather than deliberate. Notwithstanding the conundrum posed by the general will's concept—one of the most debated concepts in political theory—, and the social and institutional conditions for the theory to apply – relatively small cities and so on—Rousseau's theory derives the legitimacy of social arrangements R from the emergence of a general interest that represents individuals' true preferences even though real individuals N^* do not privately express them. Ns and N^* may not be different individuals, as they are in Locke's and Hobbes' accounts, but two aspects of the same individual: the individual as a citizen, allegedly directed towards the common good and public interest, and the private individual, above all motivated by his private ends.

Rousseau's theory highlights the distinction between private wills and a general will, which explains the specific normativity of social contracts, allowing them to generate obligations for individuals and legitimacy for institutions, circumventing the problem of imposition of duties by a private will. As such, the general will corresponds to the aggregation of Ns interests generating these obligations and duties.

Kant continues this elaboration in *The Doctrine of Rights* and proposes a priori derivation of what he calls omnilateral will. For Kant as for others, the social contract – or the original contract – is not a historical event, but an idea of reason, a rational criterion for the mere existence of political societies. Duties and rights are not the rightful product of historical events, but the effect of this original contract, such that this idea of reason restricts the legislator to what people could have consented to. However, consent has a very specific meaning in Kant's theory, such that for many commentators Kant's social contract theory is not consent-grounded, since consent is not what would be empirically consented to, based on the preferences individuals have, but what would unanimously be agreed upon based on reason alone, independently of any possible empirical information. Consequently, the social contract is what is owed to rational individuals conceived as autonomous agents. As such, civil society's rules can be enforced *against* individual consent, and individuals can be forced to enter civil society based on the desiderata of pure practical reason alone.

This is possible, for Kant, because property relates to the exercise of freedom as autonomy. If individuals are free, they must be able to make choices and use objects, possess them, and use them for themselves such that interference from someone else is undue coercion. Indeed, practical reasons imply the possibility of property if individuals are considered as autonomous agents

able to freely use objects. Nevertheless, such a claim on any object consists in imposing duties on others unilaterally. If human subjects are equal, unilateral impositions of duties cannot be legitimate. Property rights seem at the same time necessary for freedom and impossible conceptually. The only way such property – that Kant calls intelligible property rather than physical possession – can be instituted is if we collectively agree to recognize each other's rights. The original contract starts from this logical necessity to define rights – in opposition to Locke for whom rights are pre-political. For rights to exist, there is therefore the need for an omnilateral will. This entails the institution of civil powers. The strength of Kant's theory is to derive this a priori based on three problems that logically emerge from the mere institution of rights: the problem of the definition of rights, in opposition to the unilateral imposition of duties; the problem of their enforcement, to ensure mutual insurance; the problem of the adjudication, to ensure that disagreement on rights is properly refereed. These answers give birth to the three branches of government: the legislative, the executive, and the judiciary.

In short, Kant's theory generates obligations for individuals based on what is necessary for them to be free subjects, that their fully rational counterpart N would accept, even when N^* would not consent to the rules R . As N justification is fully rational, it ought to be accepted by N^* , who would be irrational and negate their freedom if they opposed public coercion based on R .

Hobbes, Locke, Rousseau, and Kant's theories are very different in many respects. They idealize the individuals N differently (are they instrumentally rational like Hobbes, reasonable like Locke, publicly minded like Rousseau, or guided by practical reason like Kant?), and their construction of the situation of choice M differ (is it a State of war, a cooperative state of nature, the situation able to generate the general will or the postulate of pure reason). They end up defending very different institutions, rights for individuals, and extensions of public power. Consequently, they spurred different varieties of social contract theories and defined different branches of social contract theories (see Fig. 2, and Fig. 3, for examples).

Nevertheless, these classical contributions share important aspects, justifying classifying them as participating in the same genre, i.e., what may be termed as *traditional social contract theory*.⁴ First, they are mostly *normative and hypothetical*. Legitimate institutions are derived from what individuals would have chosen under more or less ideal conditions. Second and consequently, these theories define the social contract as a *one-shot decision*, meaning that social contracts ought not to be reenacted, i.e., *they are not continuous*. Consequently, these theories do not give much power to actual individuals (N^*) to modify and challenge the fundamental rules R chosen by idealized agents N , even by democratic means. Third, social contracts, because they are based on more or less moderate idealization of the individuals N s and the choosing situation M are *not or only moderately sensitive to empirical information*. As the original agreement is obtained hypothetically with a high degree of generality, it is only sensitive to very general facts about human nature (such as the rationality of individuals). These theories are not originally – see section 5 for an explicit critique of this point – developed to produce different results depending on various social and historical conditions. Fourth, these theories primarily aim to secure fundamental goods, such as security, property rights, or freedoms but are not concerned with more demanding goods, such as social justice, i.e., *they have a limited scope*.

All these features, taken together, define the basic structure of Social Contract Theories, which will be discussed and modified throughout history. In the social contract model, we can see that the idealized agents and the choosing situation play a fundamental normative role, which requires substantive justification. As such, it has attracted substantial attention, especially after

Rawls's contribution. The reasoning of the idealized agent constitutes a heated debate, most notably between defenders of rational choice theory and defenders of reasonableness. The choosing situation and the alleged universal validity of the derivation of legitimate rules were heavily questioned in the 90s, most notably by Pateman and Mills. In contrast, the one-shot aspect of the social contract was questioned by evolutionary approaches drawing on aspects of Hume and Rousseau's theories. Identifying the elements of the social contract models, and how it impacts the outcome of social contract (democratic or not, one-shot or continuous, more or less sensitive to empirical content, and so on) is key to developing an alternative model for the CO3 project.

	Hobbes	Locke	Rousseau	Kant
<i>N</i> (Idealized agents)	Instrumentally rational individuals	Reasonable individuals recognizing the law of reason	Individuals able to consider the legitimacy of the general will	Rational individuals following pure practical reason postulate
<i>M</i> (Choice situation)	State of Nature characterized by a War of all against all	State of Nature characterized by cooperative relations and the possibility of violence	Public Assembly (through aggregation rather than deliberation)	Original contract as an Idea of Reason (a priori)
<i>R</i> (Justified social arrangement)	Leviathan and absolute sovereignty	Limited government protecting individual rights	Civil society legislatively directed by the general will	Civil society to address the three problems of definition, assurance, and arbitrage
<i>N*</i> (Actual individuals)	Individuals in the post-social contract society	Individuals in the post-social contract society	Individuals with private preferences and self-interested	Individuals in civil society
<i>Shared reasons</i>	Preference for safety, stability, and fear of death	Preference for property and independence	Ability to access shared interest	Logical constraints on what is rational

Figure 1: Common Framework for Traditional Social Contract Theories.

The Rebirth of the Social Contract: The Rawlsian Moment

According to Boucher and Kelly (1993) and Weale (2020), Rawls is responsible for reviving the social contract theory, which was eclipsed by utilitarianism in the late 19th until the mid-20th, represented by important figures such as Henry Sidgwick and later Francis Edgeworth and others. If we let the theory of John Harsanyi aside – who is explicitly utilitarian and yet contractualist – we can indeed say that John Rawls is responsible for the return of social contract theory in the foreground. As such, Rawls is probably the most influential political philosopher of the 20th century, whose work provoked tremendous interest and commentaries. In what follows, I will present a standard version of Rawls' arguments in *A Theory of Justice* (1971), without diving into the plethora of commentaries

and discussions his work sparked. Rawls' essential contribution is developed in *A Theory of Justice* (1971, xviii), which

generalize and carry to a higher order of abstraction the traditional theory of the social contract as represented by Locke, Rousseau, and Kant. In this way I hope that the theory can be developed so that it is no longer open to the more obvious objections often thought fatal to it.

Rawls was, indeed, an excellent connoisseur of social contract theories, as displayed in his *Lectures on the History of Political Philosophy*. The fatal objections refer to the assumptions made by Locke in the State of Nature, the use of the general will by Rousseau, or the disconnection between rational justification and political acceptance by Kant. Rawls aims to overcome these problems using a specific device, the original position, his version of the State of Nature, characterized by rational and reasonable individuals situated under a veil of ignorance, to select principles of justice. Let us unpack quickly these fundamental concepts of Rawls' analysis, to understand how we renew social contract theories.

Rawls's theory aims to develop a theory in which the procedure for choosing principles of justice is fair, such that they do not reflect partial conceptions of the good or just and could be recognized as such by individuals living in a just society, as justice is the primary virtue of social arrangements. Justice indeed would fit the nature of a cooperative arrangement between free and equal individuals. If the procedure is fair, then the principles are too, answering the fundamental question his theory seeks to answer: How can we ensure the terms of cooperation are fair? The procedure itself should be justified such that it corresponds to our moral judgments or fairness, rather than deriving the legitimacy of institutions from natural inequalities. The counter-model, despite its technical mastery, is, for Rawls, Hobbes' *Leviathan*, which justifies coercive power based on an unequal baseline in the State of Nature, which may well be realistic in some sense but does not capture our best judgments on fairness and therefore cannot meet fully the legitimacy requirement.

The original position therefore consists in a choice situation, in which a set of individuals must choose principles to live together cooperatively. Two types of constraints ensure this. First, there are reasoning specifications: individuals are rational, meaning that they will choose the set of rules that will be of advantage to them, i.e., they are mutually disinterested and seek to maximize their expected outcomes. They have a *sense of the good*, with their preferences. Yet, they are also reasonable, meaning that they are not opportunistic to seek to free ride on others, such that they can abide by rules based on a *sense of justice*, even when they hurt their rational interest. Second, there are information constraints, represented by the veil of ignorance. It entails that the individuals in the choosing situation do not have access to a set of information specific to their future position in society, e.g., their level of wealth, gender, race, talent, disabilities, or even the kind of society they will live in. The available information is only general information about human psychology and conditions for social life established by social sciences. Given these two constraints, Rawls argues that the choice will eliminate partial conceptions of justice that do not respect others as equals. It is easy to see why: if one does not know whether she is a male or a female, she will not rationally be tempted to choose principles of justice restricting women's rights and affecting their opportunities. Compare the consequences of such a device with the State of Nature in Hobbes and Locke. The same goes for the other variables.

Since the choosing situation idealizes greatly individuals (Ns), they will converge towards unanimity on a set of principles (R) superior to others, without reflecting private endowments, meaning

that the procedure displays impartiality. These principles are the two Principles of Justice and Fairness, which are chosen at a pre-constitutional level, to apply to the basic structure of society, such that any posterior rule or law should abide by it. The principles are concerned mostly with how basic goods (Primary social goods, according to Rawls' terminology), such as liberties and social and economic goods should be distributed. The first principle states that everyone should have as much liberty as possible (be it: freedom of association, of religion, of thought and expression, of choosing a career, and so on), as long as it does not diminish the liberty of others. Other options, such as aristocratic powers and so on, are eliminated by the veil of ignorance. The second Principle is divided into two parts, stating that social and economic positions should be equally accessible, favoring equality of opportunity (The Equality of Opportunity Principle), and that they should be organized to be to the advantage of everyone, such that inequalities should benefit everybody (The Difference Principle). In practice, it means that inequalities are justified if and only if the worst off is in a better situation than in any other alternative arrangement. This could be exemplified in a society in which there are richer and poorer individuals, but which constrains the richer enrichment to the condition in which the poorer gains at least comparable gains. This second principle is chosen in the original position because every individual does not know which position she will end up in ex-post and therefore minimizes the risks of being the worst-off, applying the so called maximin principle, which leads to maximizing the advantages of the worst possible option. The order of the principles is particularly important, as they are for Rawls strictly hierarchical: we should first apply the first principle (on the distribution of liberties), and then the second (on the distribution of social and economic goods). It is the case because civil liberties have a logical priority compared with economic goods, for Rawls, such that we cannot sacrifice part of our liberties to gain economic advantages.

The original position and the veil of ignorance consist, for Rawls, of devices of representation for our best moral intuitions. Their aim is less to derive the legitimacy of just institutions from hypothetical consent than to present a theory for a conception of justice as fairness that everyone can recognize as more appealing than other alternatives. Furthermore, Rawls' theory *extends the scope* of traditional social contract theory, with specific (and more demanding) principles of justice, which should dictate the shape and aims of any institution in a given society. Additionally, despite its high degree of abstraction, it is *more sensitive to empirical content* than traditional social contract theory, since the principles of justice will differ in their implications depending on specific social and economic conditions and empirical discoveries. Even though Rawls keeps the model developed within traditional social contract theory, in which idealized agents N chooses a set of rules R in a choosing situation M , such that real agents N^* can share reasons with N to recognize R as legitimate, he developed a specific theory to justify the procedure of the choosing ensuring fairness, which will probably be one of the most influential elements of his theory for the future history of social contract theories.

Rawls pursued his project after *A Theory of Justice*, most notably in *Political Liberalism* (1993), which focuses on the problem of political stability in a society based on the principles of justice, *The Law of Peoples* (1993), applying his theory to questions of global justice, and *Justice as Fairness* (2001), reformulating the original theory after decades of discussions. These works refine and extend the scope of the original theory. In particular, *Political Liberalism* is key to understanding contemporary political philosophy, because it introduces the question of how to cope with diversity – the so-called reasonable disagreement – and a *model of democratic justification* through the public expression of reasons, generating important works, most significantly in the field of deliberative democracy. It is still an open question of how much we can apply the Rawlsian tools developed in these works for forms of unreasonable disagreement and various institutional realizations.

Justice as mutual gains vs justice as impartiality: Gauthier, Buchanan, Barry, and Scanlon

In *Theories of Justice* (1991), Brian Barry distinguishes between two main families of theories of justice, which expanded after Rawls, in the wake of the social contract revival. The first family consists of theories deriving justice from *mutual advantage*, based on rational agreement and negotiation. This justifies inequalities between individuals from a rational agreement to secure important goods, such as liberty or security. This theory, for Barry, is inspired by Hobbes and Hume. The second consists of theories deriving justice from *impartiality*, based on fairness requirements. We may say that the first family insists on the rationality requirement, while the second extends the reasonableness requirement. James Buchanan and David Gauthier represent the first genre, while the second is represented by Barry himself and Thomas Scanlon.⁷ Both families refer extensively to Rawls' contribution and seek to expand his work or criticize core assumptions.

The first family grounds justice on the principle of *mutual advantage*, and it is well represented by David Gauthier's *Morals by Agreement* (1986) and James Buchanan's *Limits of Liberty* (1975). Gauthier states the aim of this tradition most clearly: we can, and we should, base moral and political agreement as founded entirely on the negotiations between rational individuals. While Gauthier and Buchanan mostly agree on the method, and the idea that we should derive the legitimacy of conventions and institutions based on what rational individuals would have consented to because it is in their interest, they differ, nevertheless, in their understanding of what kind of agreement such rational individuals would reach. These theories have an advantage over impartial theories – such as Rawls' theory – since they explain why morality would be to the advantage of individuals, explaining *ipso facto* why individuals act following morality. I will present what these theories share, and only in passing how they differ.

The bulk of the theory of justice as mutual advantages lies in the idea that the contract is acceptable if it is advantageous to all self-interested parties. For this statement to be meaningful, one must specify the baseline compared to which agreement is advantageous (situation *M*). For Gauthier and Buchanan, the starting point is a State of Nature in which individuals are independent of each other, as many Robinsons Crusoe on their island. Each individual is strongly interested in cooperating with others to increase his satisfaction. We can easily see why: each individual possesses limited time and capacity to diversify his production, such that an exchange with others allows him to access a broader range of goods and services, accessing preferred baskets of goods than the no-trade situation. To illustrate this, think of a two-person model with *A* and *B*, in which *A* produces beer and *B* crops, where *A* produces 10 units of beer and *B* 10 units of crops. Since the marginal utility of goods consumption is decreasing, *A* and *B* reach their point of repletion by consuming 5 units of beer or crops, so they have an important surplus. Both gain from trade, because they value each other's product more than their product once they have consumed what they produce. In this situation, any trade is beneficial when, for *A*, the marginal utility of a consumption of a unit of crop is at least equivalent to the consumption of a unit of beer. At first, every individual will claim the maximum from the cooperative surplus (*A* will want 5 units of crops for 1 unit of beer from *B*), yet this hardly will occur. Players will therefore start making concessions, constituted by all acceptable points below the initial maximal claim. Here, it is notoriously difficult to say anything about how concessions relate to one another, since individuals may have different utility scales. Buchanan, for instance, is agnostic about the precise point where an individual may stop and argues that an agreement will be legitimate as long as it is Pareto-

superior to the no-trade baseline, meaning that both individuals are better-off. Gauthier develops a more specific theory for the sharing of the cooperative surplus, i.e., his *minimax relative concession* theory, which proposes to compare the relative magnitude of the concession (the difference between what is obtained with their maximal claim, and what is obtained by a no-trade situation for them). Let us suppose that the outcome of A's in the no-trade situation is U^* , his outcome at the maximal claim point is U_1 and his outcome at the concession point is U_2 , then the relative magnitude of the concession will be defined by $[(U_1 - U_2)/(U_1 - U^*)]$, where the maximum number would be 1 (where the concession equals the no-trade, such that individuals are not better-off cooperating) and the minimum 0 (where individuals make no concessions). For Gauthier, this method minimizes the maximum concession in relative terms. If we assume, for the sake of simplicity, that A and B value beers equally and have a low no-trade utility, they will probably make the same relative concession, basically giving 5 units to the other. This may lead to less equal results in absolute terms when the negotiators are not equal ex-ante. Think of the difference if A produced 15 units and B 5, where, for simplicity, we assume that they have a utility of 0 if there is a no-trade, the rule entails that A should end up with three times the utility of B since he started with three times more. Gauthier's fair agreement would not entail an equal distribution ex post, if individuals gain from the trade and the relative concession is equalized.

Yet, it is well known from Hobbes' theory that it is not sufficient to have an interest in cooperation to cooperate, since individuals may still fare better paying lip services and then violating their cooperative agreements. Buchanan accepts this and grants legitimacy for the Leviathan to allow cooperation and to escape the Prisoner's Dilemma of the State of Nature.¹⁰ The rest of his work ensures that the Leviathan does not exceed the limits of this initial justification, i.e., protecting individual rights and providing security. Buchanan distinguishes different functions of the State, grounded on two separate arguments: the protective State, which should protect individual rights and guarantee security, and the productive State, which offers service when individuals consider they obtain more this way than they would with private actions. Hence, the Leviathan is required to secure cooperation but should be checked rigorously not to expand into other domains, with the risk of increased control over individuals' lives. We may coin Buchanan's position as a form of *limited hobbesianism*. Gauthier claims that it is possible to circumvent the problem posed by the State of Nature without appealing to a Leviathan. He appeals to a solution to the Prisoner's Dilemma consisting in the fact that individuals should develop the disposition of acting cooperatively when it is in their interest, such that they should be "constrained maximizers" rather than "straightforward maximizers", such that individuals should abstain from opportunistic behavior to get the result from cooperation. Cooperating is rational because it produces a surplus, and this rationality can be described as morality because it entails fairness of treatment (equality of sacrifice and equal consideration). For Gauthier, this entails that a Leviathan should not be instituted, since morality has been internalized by the agents, but should only come at an ex-post moment, to regulate individual behaviors, such as the *proviso* for the initial appropriation of land, stating that no individual should better his situation at the expense of others. In both theories, fairness emerges from rational agreement even when it reflects unequal initial endowments and bargaining powers if it displays mutual advantage. Therefore, it produces a general model of political agreement based on mutual gains from trade and cooperation, which should be secured by public powers.

In this perspective, individuals' claims pre-exist civil society, such that Gauthier and Buchanan criticize Rawls' arguments leading him to the Difference Principle, most particularly the argument of moral arbitrariness, stating that no individual deserves any credit for their talents, because they are (a) the result of a natural lottery, and (b) historically and socially contingent. This leads

Rawls to defend the argument that talents should be understood as participating in a common pool of resources for society. For Gauthier and Buchanan, Rawls' argument leads to not recognizing the distinction between persons – since it invites us to consider individual characteristics as participating in a common set of goods society ought to make use of, returning to a form of utilitarianism – and negates individual freedom since it forces individuals to use their bodies for the benefit of others. For Buchanan, in particular, the risk of Rawls' reasoning is to confuse two functions of the state: the protective and the productive, such that this argument would justify the extension of the state's activity well beyond the protection of individual rights and the production of what is less costly to provide publicly than privately.

The second family of social contract theories stemming from the Rawlsian moment is the theory of justice as impartiality, as exemplified by Brian Barry's *Justice as Impartiality* (1996) and Thomas Scanlon's *What We Owe To Each Other* (1998). They share with Rawls their insistence that the rationality of the choosers ought not be only the one of the rational individuals, but the one of the deliberative individuals as well. These theories are grounded on an analysis of mutual advantage as being insufficient to ground fairness since ex-post agreement necessarily reflects ex-ante inequalities, notwithstanding the bargaining theory one uses (be it Minimax relate concession or Nash Bargaining). Barry (1991) devotes a third of his book to demonstrating this claim. If the baseline for negotiation is crippled with bargaining inequalities, the agreement must be considered unjust, rendering invalid the claims that bargaining entails justice. One case illustrates the problem particularly well: the case of intergenerational justice (Weale, 2020, 218). Future generations cannot reciprocate for mutual advantage and have no place in justice as mutual advantage framework. Consequently, their interests should be ignored. This goes against a strong moral judgment that future individuals ought to have rights.

Barry and Scanlon's social contract theory aims to propose a baseline of agreement that is not plagued with unequal starting points but displays a deliberative component, such that rules and actions should be justified on grounds that others cannot reasonably reject (Scanlon, 1998, 7). In Rawls' the veil of ignorance ensures impartiality, but Barry and Scanlon do not take up this solution, as they are interested in broader arrangements including less idealized agents. They follow the road opened by *Political Liberalism*, which introduced the question of axiological diversity and public justification, rather than the apparatus of *A Theory of Justice*, which considered the original position as an application of rational choice theory. Their original position is constituted of deliberative individuals trying to justify their favored rules to each other, within the constraint of reasonability. Impartiality means that all interests are considered equally, such that everyone can fare as well as they could reasonably hope. The key term for doing the work for both Barry and Scanlon is *reasonableness*. As for Rawls, it entails that individuals are not making any claim, but internalize the claims of others, recognizing other individuals as moral equals. Reasonableness implies that the propositions made by individuals verify the criterion of impartiality, which is based on the recognition of a common human dignity. Equality means that no particular conception of the good, or justice, should be given priority or a privileged position in defining a common framework (Barry, 1996, 160-161). The reasonableness test implies that every conception should propose rules or policies that recognize the equality of competing conceptions of the good and the just. When a proposition is made, one must consider the reasonable complaints that others can have against the proposition. The original situation is, thus, a situation of exchange of reasons, which relates to how social relationships ought to be conceived. A reasonable complaint is decided on the merits of the claims, which are not only rational claims about well-being but also based on the suitability of some moral principles to account for mutual recognition (Scanlon, 1998, 194). This excludes *de facto* fanatic principles of justice, as well as integralist, or imperialist

conceptions, granting a veto right to any group that would be considered inferior by others because they have reasonable grounds to object to a policy. Conversely, some policies cannot be reasonably objected to, for instance, the mandatory rule to wear a helmet while driving a motorcycle, since nobody can argue that they are granted inferior status based on this ruling. What we owe to each other, namely our obligations, depends on the merits of the arguments for and against us having these obligations, and whether they could be reasonably rejected.

Barry and Scanlon apply the procedure of reasonable justification on a variety of grounds, from principles of justice to more specific policies, such as the defense of a Universal Basic Income, a defense of religious and sexual liberties, or even specific public policies such as the housing market and water resource management. In practice, many rules and policies are *at the same time* supported and rejected for reasonable reasons. Think of any conflict implying trading off values such as efficiency and justice, or different conceptions of justice and fairness. In these cases, Scanlon (1998, 198) proposes to adjudicate the relative strength of permissive and prohibitive reasons. This leads philosophical justification to legal reasoning, characterized by the balancing of competing considerations, broadening the scope of social contract theories.

It is to be noted that if both Barry and Scanlon do not use the veil of ignorance in their theories, it does not entail that their original position is composed of real individuals. Reasonable agreement is still hypothetical and produces reasons to accept or reject a rule or policy. The hypothetical nature of the agreement is, therefore, *more empirically sensitive* than Rawls' original position, since they want to model a political problem, with different groups holding different values – think of different religious groups, different political parties, and so on. This entails that the choosing situation (M) has to be informed properly by how real individuals N^* are, to constitute their counterpart N , who deliberate about R . As such, N and N^* share some reasons, since N is constructed based on N^* model, idealized as reasonable. Barry calls this way of modifying the social contract model the “empirical method”. It ensures that institutions and social arrangements are justifiable to those who are asked to accept them.

These renewed theories of the social contract not only re-actualize the theories of Hobbes, Locke, Rousseau, and Kant, but also modify the structure of the social contract model substantially (see Fig. 2 below). Of course, Buchanan, Gauthier, Scanlon, and Barry differ on fundamental matters, above all the conception of individuality and relevant inequality. For instance, Buchanan and Gauthier contend that baseline inequality is unavoidable if we are to recognize individual freedom, and that only cases of extreme duress and abuse are to be rejected, whereas Barry and Scanlon consider individual contracting as occurring only meaningfully within justified and impartial rules that everyone has good reasons to accept. Nevertheless, all these authors introduce significant modifications to the model of social contract theories. First, these theories *are wider in scope and extension* and are not merely concerned with civic contract – the justification of a public power – but with the moral dimension of contract – what arrangements and rules are justifiable to the individuals who are to live under them (Boucher and Kelly, 1993). The problem is not only the question of sovereignty and the existence of the State but also the justifiability of constitutions, laws, policies, and even moral conventions. Second, although the contracts are hypothetical and take place with idealized individuals, they are not necessarily one-shot but *can be continuous*. This is the case with Buchanan, which allows Pareto-superior renegotiations, and especially with Barry and Scanlon, allowing the reexamination of established rules based on new reasonable reasons. Third, these theories *are more empirically sensitive* than the traditional contract theories and Rawls' early contribution. This is especially true for Barry's theory, which explicitly claims an empirical approach, but also for Buchanan's insistence on the status quo as a

baseline for partial renegotiation, Gauthier's conception of compensation based on past abuse of the provision and breach of cooperation, or Scanlon's theory of adjudication. As such, they pave the way for *more dynamic and open* conceptions of social contract.

	Rawls	Buchanan	Gauthier	Scanlon	Barry
<i>N</i> (Idealized agents)	Individuals under a veil of ignorance	Rational individuals	Rational cooperative individuals	Deliberative agents in a hypothetical contractual situation	Deliberative agents modeled on the empirical features of real individuals
<i>M</i> (Choice situation)	Original position with strong information constraint	Bargaining situation with uncertainty	Bargaining situation with a problem of sharing the cooperation surplus	Deliberative situation of exchange of reasons	Deliberative situation of exchange of reasons
<i>R</i> (Justified social arrangement)	The Two Principles of Justice	Limited Leviathan and freedom of contracts (market arrangements)	Bottom-up cooperation concerning the rules of cooperation (market arrangements)	Egalitarian principles of justice and application to a variety of specific policies and rules	Egalitarian principles of justice and application to a variety of specific policies and rules
<i>N*</i> (Actual individuals)	Individuals living in a well-ordered society	Post-constitutional rational individuals	Individuals in any society	Individuals in situations of conflict about a rule	Individuals seeking to justify social arrangements
<i>Shared reasons</i>	Reasonableness and rationality	Mutual advantage and rationality	Mutual advantage through cooperation and rationality	Appeal of reasonableness through justification	N are modeled on N* interests and values
<i>Traditional Social Contract theory inspiration</i>	Rousseau/ Kant	Hobbes/ Hume	Hobbes/ Locke	Kant	Rousseau

Figure 2: Social Contract Framework for Rawlsian and post-Rawlsian theories.

Expanding and Questioning the Social Contract: Pateman and Mills

In the 1990s, social contract theories were on a roll, whether of the Rawlsian kind or its critics and successors. Yet, some were wary that the device of hypothetical agreement, allegedly impartial, would reflect biases and harmful values, such as sexist and racist values. Carole Pateman, in *The Sexual Contract* (1988), and Charles Mills, in *The Racial Contract* (1997), develop these important critics at length, challenging core assumptions of the dominant paradigm of their time. Social contract theories aim to produce a non-historically and socially dependent theory of

legitimacy: this is exactly what is challenged by these theories, which contend that social contract theory rationalizes historical agreements excluding some classes of individuals, namely women, and non-whites.

Let us start with Pateman's contribution, which states that the traditional social contract theories of Hobbes, Locke, Rousseau, and Kant, are based on a more fundamental contract within the family, subordinating women to men. This may sound odd at first, considering that social contracts, even when they refer *verbatim* to men, can theoretically have a universalist understanding. However, for Pateman, the social contract establishes a patriarchal sexual order in an original pact, in which civil freedom is a masculine attribute depending on patriarchal rights (Pateman, 1988, 2). A patriarchal right does not consist in the domination of a *pater familias* but of the domination of males for the conjugal life. This, Pateman argues, was translated into social contract theory.

Indeed, classic social contract theories do not recognize women as full individuals, such that they do not participate in the creation of civil liberties through agreement – their role is indeed confined to the private sphere. In the State of Nature, families are a natural given, in which women are subordinated in a marriage contract, which is prior to and more fundamental than the social contract. This omission is meaningful since the sexual contract within families does not give any rights, and introduces few obligations for men, as it is seen as natural and pre-political. It survives the establishment of civil society in the form of the private sphere, in which women are relegated – following a classic distinction between the *oikos* and the *polis*. Hence, the distinction between public and private runs along the distinction between natural and civil: civil society may well abolish domination in the public sphere, but not in the private sphere, which is required for men to be autonomous. This leads Pateman to argue that society is built on patriarchal assumptions, which can be seen in some consequences, for instance, the fact that women's bodies are commodified in civil societies, as goods that should be accessible in the market by men, through marriage contract – allowing “marital rape” in the 1980s. Prostitution or surrogate motherhood are two other examples for Pateman of the fact that women's bodies should be accessible and controlled by men. Consequently, contractual relations are not necessarily emancipating for the individuals, but may also be instruments of domination, if they are based on an unequal social structure.

Pateman's argument extends beyond traditional social contract theories and tackles the same issue as Rawls' original position. Even if the individuals are sexless in the original position, because they are under the veil of ignorance, they are still considered as heads of families, namely men representing their wives (Pateman, 1988, 43). The liberal individuals of the social contract may well be supposed to be ageless, sexless, and classless, as in Rawls' original position or Gauthier's Robinson, he still embodies the characteristics of a historicized self. Even Rawls, therefore, does not seem to question the existence of the family – and its hierarchy – as a natural given. Pateman demonstrates this clearly for traditional contract theorists like Locke, who mentions the role of men in governing families and the subsequent subordination of women, but we may extend this critique to every social contract theory claiming universality. This would be the case of Buchanan and Gauthier's *homo oeconomicus* maximizing his private interests in autonomy, as representing the autonomy and freedom of men once their private life is secured through domestic work from their wives. The often-invoked value of fraternity exemplifies this matter of fact since it originally meant love between brothers and was then promulgated as a cardinal and universal value of political societies (Pateman, 1988, 79). This requires questioning social contract theories, and the role historic social structures play in their idealized agreement.

Charles Mills transposes this analysis to the question of race, defending that contracts, and above all social contracts, exclude non-white people, who do not count as real citizens. For Mills, understanding this contract is fundamental to understanding the world. Traditional political theory teaches us a lot about ideal theories, from egalitarianism to libertarianism, but does not tell us much about how racial domination came to shape our social and political institutions. As for the sexual contract, the racial contract is more fundamental than the social contract, because it defines who gets to be counted as an individual worthy of being seen as an equal. White men are usually conceived as free and equal, and able to enjoy the freedom of civil society. Consequently, they are the subjects of social contracts, while other individuals can only be the objects of these contracts. As Pateman, Mills invites us to consider the history and how *existing social contracts* displayed discriminatory features.

The racial contract is, therefore, a meta-contract, stating who should count as proper subjects of the social contract. Social contracts require a definition of who counts as a subject and hence depend on social and historical conditions, which are the outcomes of historical evolution. Mills describes extensively the different codes amounting to colonial contracts granting racial superiority to Europeans, creating a racially hierarchical polity (Mills, 1997, 27). Based on these experiences, it is way more correct to say that we live in a world constructed from racial contracts rather than the universal and counterfactual traditional social contracts.

Racial contracts have many dimensions for Mills: they are epistemic, such that some individuals are negated as subjects, and are based on an epistemology of ignorance, in which some individuals are negated; they are political and moral because they grant rights and dignity to only a subset of possible individuals; and they are exploitative since they generate political orders in which white men dominate economically others. Some may claim that colonialism and hierarchical orders would not account for most of the European and American societies, but Mills argues that the story about European exceptionalism is ultimately founded upon the economic exploitation of other parts of the world: colonialism lies at the heart of Europe (Mills, 1997, 35). A non-ideal theory of social contract, as proposed by Mills, urges us to recognize the unequal baseline for agreement one must consider.

Indeed, colonialism and explicit hierarchical political orders disappeared in the late 20th century – at least in Western countries; however, the world keeps the stain of the racial contract: non-whites still possess fewer opportunities, are perceived as having lower status, are poorer, less educated, and overall inherit unequal racial contracts. Mills is adamant that such a situation ought to be recognized for social agreement to fix the consequences of the racial contract. In this perspective, hypothetical contracts as imagined by traditional social contract theories or Rawlsian social contract theories play a dangerous ideological role, i.e., ignoring racial or sexual contracts undermining the conditions for real equality.

Pateman's and Mills' contributions are of the utmost importance for social contract theory because they put into question some basic characteristics of social contract theories (see Fig.3 below at the end of the next section). The idealization of N is dubious if it does not incorporate historical features about the evolution of societies and oppression. They invite us to consider social contracts not as hypothetical agreements but as *historical agreements* favoring some individuals at the expense of others, with long-term consequences for real individuals N^* . Most historical agreements are, therefore, plagued by unequal bargaining powers, and straightforward exclusion from political status. In their perspective, social contract theories ought to be *empirically sensitive*

to be relevant, and Pateman's and Mills' arguments campaign for developing *continuous and renegotiated* contracts, recognizing equal status to marginalized individuals. Such a social contract theory ought still to be developed, to assess exactly how to not only integrate marginalized groups in social contract theory but also to assess how they should be compensated for past injustices.

Evolving Contracts, A Natural Theory of Social Morality: Binmore and Skyrms

Traditional as well as post-Rawlsian social contracts – at the notable exception of Buchanan's theory – display one important feature: they rely on a one-shot hypothetical agreement among individuals grounding legitimacy. Yet, some authors rely on Hume's theory of *Treatise of Human Nature* (1739) theory of conventions and social morality or Rousseau's *Discourse on the Origins and Foundations of Inequality Among Men* (1754), which proposes a naturalized and evolutionary version of the social contract and the emergence of civil society. Since the 1980s, this is probably one of the most active subfields of study on social contract theories.

In this section, we will focus on a theory that considers the possible evolution of social contract theory, as developed from the 80s onwards. Many authors could be mentioned as participating in this perspective: from Andrew Schotter's *The Economic Theory of Social Institutions* (1981) and Robert Sugden's *The Economics of Rights, Cooperation and Welfare* (1986) to Peter Vanderschraaf's *Strategic Justice* (2017). This section will focus on two major and systematic presentations of this approach, developed by Ken Binmore in *Game Theory and the Social Contract* (1994, 1998), and Brian Skyrms' *Evolution and the Social Contract* (1996).

Evolutionary social contract theories start with a different question: they do not ask what rational decision-makers would agree to in the State of Nature, but how our implicit social contract – the rules of coordination, conventions that allow us to live together – evolved and continue to evolve. Game theory helps to study this dynamic process, as it was already used in evolutionary biology to study animal strategies. This approach is mainly explanatory, namely, it shows how norms, conventions, and social rules may have evolved and how *social morality* emerged, but it does not tell us why fairness rules are just. These theories help us understand how rules can be stable because individuals N^* recognize rules as, for instance, equilibrium, but do not tell us why the process of stabilization is just, while traditional social contract theory proposes the opposite. Binmore (1998, 7) thus understands social contract as the set of rules and conventions individuals respect to live together, without the need to rely on an external enforcing mechanism, such as a theory of obligation.

The concept of equilibrium plays a central role for Skyrms and Binmore. An equilibrium occurs when two optimization strategies depend on each other, such that no one has an incentive to modify her strategy once the equilibrium is reached. John Nash is usually credited for the mathematical demonstration that equilibrium of this sort exists in great generality (Nash, 1950). Now, as Skyrms argues (Skyrms, 1996, 5), it is not enough that something is an equilibrium to be fair. If A and B must share a cake, any pair of positive claims amounting to 100% of the cake is a Nash equilibrium, be it 50/50, 60/40, or 99/1. Indeed, in every case, exceeding the claim would not be possible because it goes over 100%, and diminishing it is a strict loss. Why, then, do most people share the cake 50/50, as many experiments showed? A Rawlsian answer would be to

posit a veil of ignorance to define justice. *A* and *B* are both ignoring who they are and should apply the maximin rule, securing 50% of the cake for both. For Skyrms, this solution is costly and supposes a general level of risk aversion among players. The alternative solution for Skyrms is to run an evolutionary model, in which every player has a strategy and encounters others in pairwise interaction to divide a cake. Many strategies may exist, some may systematically propose a 50/50 split, others a 99/1 split, or even a 100/0 split. The payoff of the game is the result of each strategy against others, i.e., which strategy ends up with the highest rate of deals. A *Darwinian veil of ignorance* is created out of these interactions since players cannot know the strategy of others before playing with them. The only stable equilibrium, in the long run, is a 50/50 split, which maximizes the payoff of every player. Indeed, if we suppose for the sake of clarity that strategies are evenly spread along the continuum from 0 to 100, individuals claiming more than 50% chance have more chance to get a no deal than a deal, and individuals claiming less than 50% have more chances to get a deal than a no deal. Based on these results we can build a payoff matrix in which every strategy has a different expected value based on the probability of encountering other strategies, and we can show that a 50/50 split is the only stable equilibrium, since anybody asking more would end up with less than the average population, and the same occurs for anybody asking less. The equal split equilibrium maximizes the interest of all individuals.

Of course, many cases are more complicated than symmetrical two-player games. Skyrms and Binmore (1996, chap.1) developed more sophisticated tools and concepts in cooperative and non-cooperative game theory to study them. However, the gist remains the same, and we can show that many important rules, such as rules of fairness, mutual aid, conventions, and so on, evolved following a dynamic process of interactions between individuals seeking to maximize their gains while depending on others to do so. Rules, conventions, and norms are described as equilibria that are stable in virtue of being in individuals' interests given some sets of constraints. They both claim to offer a *naturalized* conception of social contract theory, which does not rely on hypothetical agreement, but in which norms and rules draw their legitimacy from the recognition of individuals producing reasonable expectations based on them.

Evolutionary social contract theories may be understood as a continuation of the justice as mutual advantage perspective, as developed by Gauthier (1986): coercive rules and norms are in place because they are the equilibrium that emerged from repeated interactions. Contrary to Gauthier, however, evolutionary social contract theorists are more tempted to describe their theories as descriptive rather than normative. Gauthier spends pages explaining and defending why his bargaining solution and the initial conditions are fair, despite potential inequalities, whereas Skyrms and Binmore describe the emergence of the social conception of fairness, rather than appealing to another ethical and political framework. Their theory thus possesses the opposite strength of traditional social contract theories: they explain very well why individuals follow rules and abide by them – because rules are equilibria which they, by definition, do not have interest to leave – but less well why these equilibria would be justified from another standpoint. However, for both Skyrms (1996, 110) and Binmore (1998, 8), evolutionary social contracts have an important normative role to play: *they constrain what is feasible in terms of possibility*, i.e., they describe the dynamics of social and moral agreement, excluding some options which are not stable equilibria from the feasible set of social institutions and arrangements. These theories invite us to consider the weaknesses of arrangements that are unstable because individuals would have incentives to constantly deviate from them, in other words, they lead us towards a non-ideal theory of social contracts.¹³ Constraints do not, nevertheless, imply the impossibility of intervening. Evo-

lution does not need to be an impersonal process. Both Skyrms and Binmore advocate for reforms and gradual improvements. Indeed, some equilibria might be strictly dominated – meaning that every individual would prefer being in the other situation – by other potential equilibria, requiring reform and political intervention. In doing so, they pave the way for *renegotiated and continuous social contracts* in light of other potential considerations, such as different conceptions of justice, although Binmore is very explicit in his preference for whiggish and compromise-based reforms. Evolutionary contracts are very sensitive to empirical content, such as the feeling of injustice when some populations face social norms, or social scientific discussions on noxious norms and rules – for example in the case of pluralistic ignorance. It remains to be developed how exactly these theories can cross the bridge between a descriptive theory of the evolution of social contracts and a normative theory justifying political legitimacy and obligation.

	Pateman and Mills	Evolutionary theorists
<i>N</i> (Idealized individuals)	Individuals have access to the public sphere and are granted political privileges.	Individuals characterized by strategic rationality
<i>M</i> (Choice situation)	History, especially from the 16 th century onwards	Strategic and repeated interactions
<i>R</i> (Social arrangement)	Discriminatory rules granting specific privileges to white men	Various equilibria allow individuals to fulfill their interests, but particularly fair arrangements
<i>N*</i> (real individuals)	Individuals of current societies, inheriting structural injustices	Individuals of current society (approximated by <i>homo oeconomicus</i>)
Shared reasons	Disconnection: <i>N</i> is demonstrated as displaying false universalization of <i>N*</i>	Close to <i>N</i> : low degree of idealization due to evolutionary models
Social contract influence	None: both are critical of the theory	Hume, Rousseau's <i>Second Discourse</i> , Hobbes

Figure 3: *Challenging the Social Contract Model: Critical Social Contract Theory and Evolutionary Theory.*

New Approaches to Social Contract Theories: The Very Recent Contributions

Research on social contract theory is still burgeoning and has shown important transformations. The most important ones are well described by John Thrasher and Michael Moehler's *New Approaches to Social Contract Theory* (2024). First, recent developments in social contract theories are based on a deeper recognition of *diversity and polarization*, recognizing a larger set of views as legitimate, even if the resulting polarization may lead to a multiplicity of justifiable social outcomes. Second, they introduce a *dynamic aspect* of social contract theories, studying how social justice may be *context-dependent and dynamic* rather than fixed and static. Third and finally, they invite us to *broaden the use of empirical methods* to cope with diversity and the dynamic nature of social agreement, such as experimental approaches, and computational simulations, to complement counterfactual and hypothetical agreements.

Seminal contributions displaying such features are Gerald Gaus' *The Order of Public Reason* (2011), Ryan Muldoon's *Social Contract Theory for a Diverse World: Beyond Tolerance* (2017), Michael Moehler's *Minimal Morality: A Multilevel Social Contract Theory* (2018) and the contributors of the recent collective volume edited by Thrashed and Moehler cited above. Alexander Schaefer (2024), one of the contributors, states one central issue with social contract theories perfectly: the justification of rules R depends on how idealization is conducted for N s and, as this overview demonstrates, different authors may have different (and sometimes flawed – as argued by Pateman and Mills) ways of idealizing agents, we then end up with a set of various justified rules $\{R_1, R_2, \dots, R_n\}$ depending on different manners of defining idealized agents $\{N_1, N_2, \dots, N_n\}$.

The question, for Schaefer, becomes less about what rules would be justified based on a specific set of assumptions, but what kind of social arrangements would fit a society of axiologically diverse individuals holding different views about justice. In other words: what kind of social arrangement would maximize the co-existence of individuals holding various conceptions of what society should be?

Considering seriously this question leads us toward a dynamic conception of justice, especially when one grants liberal freedom, which tends to upset any pre-established pattern (Muldoon, 2024). In this perspective, normative disagreement and radical diversity should not be perceived as problems and limits for social contract theories, but as strengths allowing us to experiment and discover new forms of life. The social contract argument evolves - it is not a question of knowing a priori what social arrangements should be justified, but of arguing that an experimental society, characterized by a diversity of rules and innovations, is to the advantage of everyone given moral equality because it produces consequences that everybody can take advantage of. Muldoon provides arguments based on experimental studies showcasing the superiority of diverse groups compared with homogeneous groups to strengthen his case for this argument. Schaefer and Muldoon's arguments campaign to move social contract theories toward dynamic and diversity-driven theories in which social arrangements are evolving and constantly transformed by an autocatalytic process – a process of transformation that fuels itself.

This program is still open-ended and introduces new problems as it relaxes important assumptions of the social contract model. As coined by Moehler (2024), such theories encounter the Diversity Paradox. Traditional social contract theories manage to offer a single justified social arrangement at the cost of idealization – the N 's agreement justifies the legitimacy of R based on M – but once we introduce different N 's in the initial conditions, we may end up with a set of accepted institutions which is indeterminate. Consequently, there is a fundamental tension between the stability of a conception of justice and the justification of a conception of justice. Justification of a conception can only occur when holding strong idealizing assumptions, while stability requires us to recognize a diversity of individuals. Defining the existence of a justified conception of justice entails reducing diversity, and to answer stability we need to consider diversity. Moehler himself defends that we may insulate problems, accepting Hobbes' solution for questions of security, while accepting a more gradual perspective for other issues, following Buchanan's social contract theory.

The paradox is challenging because it is particularly problematic to associate stability with legitimacy. Cailin O'Connor (2024) demonstrates this in her critique of what she calls "natural social contracts" – social arrangements that are the outcome of an evolutionary process, corresponding to section 6's arguments or Schaefer and Muldoon's favored processes. Spontaneous interac-

tions between individuals may well produce stable norms, but also unfairness. When we introduce different sub-groups in the models, we end up with results showing that unfair agreements are very likely to emerge, based on a variety of mechanisms. Particularly two mechanisms generate unequal agreements, introducing systematic differences in consideration between individuals: *unequal power* and *minority status*. Unsurprisingly, the greater the bargaining power of a group, the more the outcome will be in its favor. This is the case because powerful individuals have a very high disagreement point (the no-deal point in the bargaining situation) compared with less powerful individuals since they are not worse off in the status quo. Consequently, they will end up making higher demands and re-enforce their position. Minority status is another example. For O'Connor, minority groups tend to be more risk-averse, because they are less stable economically, which tends to lead to disadvantages in bargaining. After all, small risk-averse groups tend to accept accommodating demands. In addition, if groups are biased towards in-group favoritism and out-group bias, minorities' existence leads to general bargaining disadvantages. In general, most significant asymmetries generate unequal outcomes, and this is particularly the case once we input social categories in the bargaining models. As a result, the spontaneous emergence of norms is a very important aspect of the research, but it requires an external normative benchmark to avoid taking stable institutions as justified by default.

These contributions – which illustrate only a part of the contemporary works on social contract theories – exemplify the roads taken by contemporary social contract theorists, toward *more realism* – considering deep diversity and more empirical facts, such as social categories, empirical disagreement, and polarization – and the development of *continuous social contracts*, able to cope with *societal transformations*. As such, they also highlight the most important tensions we already encountered many times: tensions between the question of the normative justification of a set of rules, and the question of the empirical stability of these rules. This is probably what underpins the differences between theories of justice as a mutual advantage, focusing on the issue of ex-post acceptability by real individuals, hence stability, and theories of justice as impartiality, focusing on the conditions for judgments to be reasonable, seeking to reach some external benchmark to assess justifiability. These tensions are still lively and call for more work to answer them properly.

Conclusion: Unexplored Roads on the Map

This general overview of social contract theories throughout its history – albeit, as mentioned in the introduction, not by any means complete, as other important contributions could be added, such as Habermas', Nozick's, Gaus' or Van Parijs' – shows that important foundational assumptions of social contract theories are progressively being relaxed. Most importantly, traditional social contract theories are *one-shot*, *counterfactual*, and not particularly interested in *democracy* or *inclusiveness*. Furthermore, these theories mostly focus on a *minimal conception of justice*, understood as a theory of the legitimacy of public authority. Rawls and post-Rawlsian theories expanded the scope of social contract theories to theories of social justice and moral norms. Paterman and Mills, as well as evolutionary social contract theories, challenged that social contract theories would be one-shot and counterfactual, with a universal value. Social contracts – understood as the agreement on the fundamental rules of society – ought to be constantly renegotiated to account for past inequalities, lack of inclusiveness, and the constant production of inequalities in complex societies.

As much as social contract theories propose a decisive tool to justify various alternative social arrangements, the history of the concept shows that there is by no means one social contract

theory characterized by one set of assumptions. It is self-evident now that Barry, Hobbes, Rawls or Gauthier's theories do not share the same starting points and the same political outcomes. Social contract theories are characterized by a unity of methods rather than assumptions or outcomes. Moreover, this overview emphasizes how social contract theories should be reworked. For instance, Pateman and Mills clarified that impartial agreement on social rules could reflect past inequalities and structural inherited injustices. However, they did not provide a conceptual framework allowing to systematically update the social contract based on these revendications.

At the heart of this first presentation, one can also notice the large hole in the history and theory of social contract theories, with a blank of more than one century between Immanuel Kant and John Rawls. According to Weale, as referred to above, it corresponds to the time of the domination of utilitarianism. However, as argued in another contribution of this deliverable, it is not only possible but important to fill this gap, to develop a sociological understanding of social contract theory in the French tradition in the 19th century. Developing this aspect shows yet another tradition of social contract theory, giving more place to the continuous and democratic aspect of social contract theories.

Additionally, a complex society may continuously generate new injustices and revendications one must deal with. *Resilience* is, therefore, a particularly important feature to develop for social contract theories, allowing them to cope with persistent contestations and revendications. *Democratizing the decision-making procedure*, to make sure every interest is heard, is a possible solution, which would still require work to develop a democratic theory of the social contract. This will lead us towards the first iteration of a CO3 model in D2.3.

Moreover, social contract theories, from Hobbes to the post-Rawlsian literature, hold on to methodological nationalism, i.e., the assumption that the proper territorial unit for social contracts is the national one because nations display some levels of homogeneity and like-mindedness, as well as share common interests. Developing a social contract theory for different entities, such as the European Union (see the other contributions in this deliverable), may require modifying substantially the existing assumptions, to consider the diversity of nations and the heterogeneity of interests.

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Contribution 2: Taking the Mapping Seriously: Democracy, Continuity, Empirical Basis, Inclusivity and Justice. An Essay on the Visualization of Social Contract Theories

Nathanaël Colin-Jaeger (American University of Paris).

Introduction

This contribution complements Contribution 1, which proposed a theoretical overview of social contract theories from Hobbes to more contemporary theories. In this contribution to D2.1, I expand the conclusion and propose a mapping of the different characteristics of social contract theories, mainly the most important ones for the CO3 project, i.e., the democratic component of social contract theories, their continuous aspect, their openness to empirical facts, their inclusivity. In addition, I compare what kind of theory of justice they tend to promote.

Indeed, during our travels in social contract theories, we encountered many theories that followed, with important differences, the same general model. Providing a general mapping of these theories can be useful to clarify the overall picture. In this contribution, my goal is to generate a readable map of the options, to show how the different features of social contract theories are correlated.

In this contribution, I show three ways to map the theories of social contract: (i) a Heatmap of the theories showing the five dimensions; (ii) parallel coordinate plots; and (iii) a multiple correspondence analysis. This required quantifying the different features of social contract theories on a [0; 1] scale, based on the qualitative analysis provided in the previous contribution.

Methodology

Important dimensions emerge from the overview we provided. Five dimensions can, therefore, be isolated, based on their importance for the project, and the proper understanding it gives for social contract theories:

Democratic/non-democratic: This criterion is fundamental for the project, and yet the link between social contract theories and democracy is not straightforward: idealized agreement in a counterfactual situation is not democratic and may justify non-democratic institutions, as this is possibly the case with Hobbes and Kant. Democracy is a complex concept that may cover very different institutional grounds, from aggregative democracy above all characterized by votes, to deliberative democracy characterized by the public justification of reasons. To visualize the different theories, I created a common scale [0;1] to map the theories along one dimension. I did so with the following criterion: the more a theory is close to 0, the less room it gives to any form of

democracy, the more a theory is close to 1, the more it introduces democratic mechanisms (voting, deliberation, but also potentially public contestation), especially if it allows a democratic discussion on the most fundamental rules.

Continuous/one-shot: Traditional social contract theory is mostly composed of hypothetical theories justifying social arrangements as a one-shot agreement. Rawls' theory keeps this feature with the Original Position. Nevertheless, the history of social contracts features many theories allowing or defending the possibility of partial or total renegotiation. This appears not only in the theories using bargaining theory, such as Buchanan's and Gauthier's, or the moral theories of the social contract of Barry and Scanlon but also in the more historical theories of Pateman and Mills, which call for a renegotiation of the social contract. Again, I ranked social contract theories on a common scale [0;1] to represent the degree of openness of the social contract, 1 being full openness and 0 being one-shot. As for the democratic feature, the choice may be contentious, since theories may be open in different ways. As such, it is hard to assess which theory is more open. I chose to rank social contract theories as more open when they were more open to contestation and the inclusion of new social concerns from within.

Empirical sensitivity: The empirical basis of social contract theories varies greatly, from Kant's theory which is completely a priori, to the more empirically informed New Diversity Theory or the Pateman-Mills approach. The agreement on a set of rules depends on what information individuals possess when deliberating about what they will accept, which may be different (Economics, History, Sociology, Anthropology, etc.). The same problem occurs as with the other dimensions, since different theories may be sensitive to different empirical aspects. I chose to rank social contract theories by introducing more concepts related to power differentials, historical inequalities, or social contestation higher than the ones using rational choice theory and game theory, which were ranked higher than *a priori* theories. As for the two first dimensions, I ranked the options on a [0;1] scale, 1 denoting a higher degree of sensitivity and 0 lesser.

Inclusive/non-inclusive: Inclusivity refers to the capacity of the social contract theory, and the social arrangement that stems from it, to accommodate diverse perspectives and preferences, which amounts to recognizing the place and prerogatives of marginalized individuals (such as women), minorities (such as ethnic minorities), or even infants, non-humans, and the nature. The same method was used as before to rank the options: the more inclusive the theory, the closer it will be to 1. Again, contentious choices had to be made, since some theories were historically non-inclusive, such as Locke's theory criticized by Pateman, but do not necessitate theoretically the exclusion of women. I chose to rank these theories low since they did not address explicitly the issue of inclusivity, even though one could argue that there is nothing in these theories preventing them from recognizing minority interests.

The type of theory of justice: Finally, it is illuminating to compare theories on the kind of theories of justice they promote. Two important families are represented throughout the history of social contract theories: justice as mutual advantages and justice as impartiality. I used the same method as for other variables, ranking mutual advantages theories closer to 0 and impartiality theories closer to 1. I used a continuous scale rather than a binary variable (such that theories would score 0 or 1 and never 0.5, for instance), because in a lot of theories, we may find both theories. Rawls' original position combines both with the use of the maximin since individuals choose rules to defend their interests as members of the cooperative venture while reaching an impartial position to judge what is fair. Conversely, Gauthier's theory is certainly based more on

mutual advantage, but he argues that the fairness of his bargaining solution is just because it can be accepted as fair by individuals, hence appealing to some conception of impartiality.

Once the different parameters and variables are defined, we obtain Table 1, completed in Excel. This table is used as our dataset to compare social contract theories. Although I entered the value, I asked several other researchers – from AUP, the CO3, and external researchers - with expertise in philosophy if they agreed on the rankings and the value, and asked them to fill the same file, and they obtained similar values.

Social contract theorists	Democra	Continuous / one	Empirically sensitiv	inclusive / nor	Mutual advant
Hobbes	0	0	0,25	0,15	0,2
Locke	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,1	0,1
Rousseau (Social Contract)	1	0	0,15	0,3	0,6
Rousseau (Second Discourse)	0	0,75	0,6	0,3	0,15
Kant	0,3	0	0	0,2	1
Rawls (Theory of Justice)	0,6	0	0,3	0,5	0,7
Gauthier	0,2	0,6	0,35	0,35	0,1
Buchanan	0,5	0,7	0,35	0,3	0,1
Barry	0,9	0,85	0,85	0,75	0,8
Scanlon	0,85	0,8	0,7	0,7	0,9
Pateman	0,75	0,9	0,85	0,8	0,25
Mills	0,75	0,9	0,8	0,9	0,25
Binmore	0,4	0,95	0,7	0,5	0,1
Skyrms	0,4	0,95	0,7	0,5	0,1
New Diversity Theory (Gaus, Muldoon, Schaefer)	0,65	1	0,95	0,8	0,4

Table 1: Social Contract Theories Five Dimensions.

This document consists of our dataset to compare the theories. I used a common continuous scale from 0 to 1 to have the same kind of variables and not mix categorical, binaries, and quantitative variables. Social contract theories constitute the only categorical variable, allowing the use of Student tests for correlations, using R to generate visualization, and running correlation tests.

Results and visualizations

First, one can say a few things about the correlations across dimensions. Running a correlation test on each variable, we obtain Table 2. Given the size of the dataset and the nature of the values, running a significance test to assess the p-value was not useful.

Variable	Democratic	Continuous	Empirical/A Priori	Inclusive	Mutual Advantage/Impartiality
Democratic / non-democratic [0;1]	1.000	0.175	0.332	0.602	0.461
Continuous / one-shot [0;1]	0.175	1.000	0.896	0.648	-0.377
Empirically sensitive / a priori [0;1]	0.332	0.896	1.000	0.798	-0.215
Inclusive / non-inclusive [0;1]	0.602	0.648	0.798	1.000	0.180
Mutual advantage or Impartiality [0;1]	0.461	-0.377	-0.215	0.180	1.000

Table 2: Table of Correlation Between Variables.

Above all, these numbers should be taken with caution. As indicated above, the values – although tested intersubjectively – result from evaluative choices, and the dataset is too limited in size to generate any definitive claim. This contribution should be taken to facilitate the mapping of the theory, to complement the general theoretical overview provided before.

Some dimensions are strongly correlated, above all the continuous dimension and the empirical dimension, with a correlation coefficient of around 0.9, indicating a strong positive linear relationship, meaning that the more theory is empirically sensitive, the more it has a chance to be continuous. This is unsurprising given our dataset since the theories being more empirically sensitive are also the ones leading to more continuity, e.g., Pateman and Mill. However, one might add that it is not necessarily an artifact based on the dataset but is justified by theoretical arguments. Indeed, the continuous aspect of a social contract theory, i.e., its ability to renegotiate social agreements, requires empirical elements to assess and evaluate the injustice of past agreements. Even though the correlation need not be as high as 0.9 for any theory, we can expect these two aspects to be correlated rather strongly. The same occurs to a lesser extent between the empirical and the inclusive dimension (0.8), as well as between the democratic and the inclusive dimension (0.6), for similar reasons. We may also note some negative correlations, namely between types of theories of justice and the continuous and empirically sensitive aspect. The more theory lies towards impartiality, the less it is susceptible to being continuous in our dataset (-0.375 for the correlation between Impartiality and Continuity). This can be explained by the specificity of some theories in the dataset, e.g., Kant's and Rawls'. However, I do not think that this result is definitive. Recent theories such as New Diversity Theory aim to provide quasi-impartial ways to compare perspectives while drawing on significant empirical evidence. One could even argue that developing an empirically based impartial theory of justice is what should be aimed at in future work and potentially within the CO3 project.

The main difficulty consists in comparing the theories using these five different dimensions at the same time, to offer a general readable mapping. Most visual tools and techniques are unfit for five-dimension comparisons or are arduous to understand – such as Principal Component Analysis. Averaging the values is meaningless since there is no commensurability and possible trade-offs among the relevant dimensions of the comparison, since a “high” does not mean that the theory is better or worse. A mapping is not an evaluative ranking.

Furthermore, reducing the number of dimensions to produce a more readable mapping of the theories (ideally across two dimensions) would tremendously improve the comparison. Graph. 1 below displays the result of a *Multiple Correspondence Analysis* doing exactly this.

Graph. 1: Multiple Correspondence Analysis on Social Contract Theories.

Multiple Correspondence Analysis (MCA) is a factorial analysis method. Each dimension captures part of the total variance of the data. The first dimensions are the most important, as they explain the most variance. To read the graph, it is important to know that the distance between points reflects their similarity, while the angles between variables indicate their correlation (0 means perfect correlation while 180 means perfect negative correlation). The contribution of variables to the axes tells us which characteristics define each dimension. In our case, the first two dimensions explain around 57% of the total variance, which is a good representation of our data.

This analysis shows how the different social contract theorists are positioned relative to each other based on their characteristics. Visualization helps us see two things:

Dimension 1 (horizontal axis) separates more traditional approaches (positive values) from more modern ones (negative values)

Dimension 2 (vertical axis) distinguishes between impartiality-focused theories (upper part) and mutual advantage-focused theories (lower part)

The theorists are clustered based on their similar characteristics. For example, Hobbes, Kant, and Rousseau (Social Contract) are in the same cluster based on their acceptance of a one-shot social contract (with Rousseau and Rawls being further away from Hobbes than Kant); on the left side, Skyrms and Binmore are close to New Diversity Theory, based on their emphasis on the evolutionary aspect of social contract theory. The general picture shows well the main opposition between the theories: Gauthier and Scanlon are opposed, while they both share some aspects of Rawls' work (the impartiality aspect for Scanlon, and the non-continuous aspect for Gauthier). Finally, the red points in the visualization represent the different categories of each variable, helping us understand which characteristics are associated with each theorist's position in space.

While it conveys very useful information, the MCA analysis is far from offering a complete overview of social contract theories and explains only 57% of the total variance. To move further and provide a general overview, I chose to generate what is known as a *Heatmap* and a *Parallel Coordinates Plot*, allowing one to compare every theory with an image. The Parallel Coordinates Plot is less readable than the Heatmap, but it provides alternative visualization without reducing the different dimensions of the comparison. In doing so, I merged some authors (Pateman-Mills; Scanlon-Barry; Skyrms-Binmore) and used shorter names for some (Rousseau of the *Social Contract* becomes Rousseau 1 while Rousseau of the *Second Discourse* becomes Rousseau 2, while Gaus, Muldoon and Schaefer are merged in the category of New Diversity Theory). We obtain the following visualization.

Graph 2. Heatmap of Social Contract Theories Across Five Dimensions.

Graph. 3. Parallel Coordinates Plot Across Five Dimensions.

The heatmap visually represents the correlations between the different theoretical dimensions in the dataset, using a color gradient where dark blue indicates strong positive correlations, and quasi white-blue indicates strong negative correlations and lighter shades represent weaker relationships. One can notice the same patterns as with the correlation analysis. Indeed, one of the most striking observations is the strong positive correlation (0.90) between "Continuous / one-shot" and "Empirically sensitive / a priori", which suggests that theories emphasizing continuous interactions are also likely to be more empirically sensitive rather than a priori in nature. Similarly, the relationship between "Inclusive / non-inclusive" and "Empirically sensitive / a priori" (0.80) is also strong

and significant, implying that theories that are empirically grounded tend to be more inclusive in their scope.

On the other hand, "Democratic / non-democratic" and "Continuous / one-shot" have a weak positive correlation (0.17). However, "Democratic / non-democratic" has a stronger positive correlation with "Inclusive / non-inclusive" (0.60), suggesting that democratic theories tend to be more inclusive. Another interesting finding is the negative correlation between "Continuous / one-shot" and "Mutual advantage or Impartiality" (-0.38), indicating that theories that emphasize continuous interactions are slightly more likely to focus on mutual advantage rather than impartiality.

Overall, the heatmap reveals some key patterns: empirically sensitive theories tend to be more continuous and inclusive, while democratic theories are more likely to be inclusive. The analysis provides valuable insights into how different dimensions of social contract theories relate to one another, but they should not be taken as definitive results, given the size of the data set and the irrelevance of statistical signification tests.

Conclusion

The results depend on the qualitative reading of the different social contract theories. Some results may be contentious, e.g., giving Mills-Pateman a high rate for the Democratic variable is interpretative since they do not offer a positive theory of democracy in their critical work. I interpreted their theories as implying such a development, to accommodate minorities' claims. Unsurprisingly, Barry-Scanlon scored the highest in this category, since they defended that social contract should imply an active exchange of reasons between citizens, which could be instantiated in assemblies (at least for Barry).

Likewise, the degrees of empirical sensibility depend on a lot of criteria one can and should discuss. Evolutionary approaches based on rational choice theories score high in this category, because evolutionary game theory, as demonstrated by O'Connor (2024), could integrate many results from social sciences such as social categories, minority status, and so on. In the end, the scores with this variable depend on how one weights the use of potential different disciplines against one another (game theory and rational choice – for Buchanan, Gauthier, and evolutionary theories –, history – for Pateman-Mills, moral psychology – for Rawls, and sociology and anthropology, for other potential approaches). Scores close to 1 do not imply that it is not possible to incorporate more empirical data, but that these are the theories that are comparatively more empirically sensitive.

Inclusiveness may also be contentious. Theories score well for inclusiveness when they tend to recognize more diverse interests and give equal status to different axiological approaches. However, it may be argued that the deliberative process of organized exchange of reason is, by its nature, not very inclusive, as argued by Sanders (1997) and others. Conversely, Pateman-Mills score well on this metric, but their theory calls for inclusiveness more than they develop a positive theory of how social contract theories would evolve considering minorities.

Reading this table, we can, for example, see that three theories display high levels of four different variables (Democratic, Continuity, high empirical sensibility, inclusiveness): the Barry-Scanlon approach; Mills-Pateman's approach, and the New Diversity Theory approach. These

theories are therefore particularly relevant to developing Continuous Constructions of Social Contracts Theory.

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Contribution 3: Sociological Social Contracts

Stephen W. Sawyer (American University of Paris, ssawyer@aup.edu)

Introduction

A reigning narrative on the social contract in the history of political philosophy and political thought asserts that there was a golden age in the birth of the social contract along largely liberal lines – that is as a means of defining the possibilities, limitations, and necessities involved in a rights-based sovereign willing subject's choice to join a state. This golden age began in the seventeenth century, usually considered to have started with Hobbes, and dominated political theory through the eighteenth century, finding its last classical formulation in Kant's elaboration of the concept. This classical concept of the social contract then gave way, quite suddenly in the wake of the French Revolution, the narrative goes, to utilitarianism in the early nineteenth century, which then became the benchmark for liberal theory. Then, as Albert Weale (2023), asserted in the opening to his powerful reading of the social contract tradition: "In the second half of the twentieth century, social contract theory was reborn as a flourishing branch of political theory and moral philosophy. Reviving an idea that many had thought long dead." As Weale, as well as the first contribution to this deliverable, demonstrated, over the next 75 years the social contract tradition was deeply revised, expanded, and fit to the purpose of twentieth-century liberalism.

As important and useful as this narrative is for understanding the work of the classical social contract theorists and those who emerged 150 years later, from the perspective of the history of political thought and political theory the bagel theory (as I call it) of the social contract, that is, with a gaping hole of more than a century between its classical formulation and its revival in its middle, seems at once historically improbable and politically problematic. This takes nothing away from the extraordinary work that has been done, it just suggests that something is missing in our story of the social contract.

Relevant literature

As I argue in my recent book (Sawyer, 2025), this story is in some essential ways incomplete. Social contract theory did not disappear and did not give way entirely to utilitarianism but rather continued to thrive on the European continent and especially in France. This was partially for historically contingent reasons tied to the legacy of the French Revolution and the perceived importance of Rousseau for that event. Unlike in other parts of Europe and especially in Britain, where for many political theorists the move to utilitarianism offered a way of thinking away from the French Revolution as a necessary path for their political development, in France it represented the expression of a national political past. So, coming to terms with Rousseau, with social contract theory, and with the French Revolution became a central feature of nineteenth-century political thought. I, therefore, offer a complement to the history proposed by Weale (2023) and others.

However, it was also clear to many that the deployment of social contract theory could not take place along the same lines that it had developed in the pre-revolutionary phase. This was largely tied to the way that political and social theorists understood the relationship between Rousseau, his greatest hero during the Revolution, Robespierre, and the possibilities of Terror. In particular, it was tied to the way that individual abstract will, as Hegel had argued, was held to be responsible for the Terror. Indeed, what emerged across the nineteenth century was a broader

critique of the idea that the entire edifice of the social contract could be constructed on individual and collective will. I build on two important sources to conduct this work:

- (ii) **Nineteenth-Century French Thought:** Tocqueville's *Democracy in America* (1835) reinterprets Rousseau through the lens of New England's founding, emphasizing historical examples of social welfare regulation. Proudhon's *Idée générale de la révolution au XIXe siècle* (1851) critiques Rousseau's individualism, proposing a mutualist social pact. George Sand's *Indiana* (1832) and Victor Hugo's *Les Misérables* illustrate cultural critiques of individualist contract theory. Hortense Allart's *La femme et la démocratie de nos temps* (1840s) advocates for a scientific reorientation of Rousseau's egalitarianism. Jules Simon's *La Liberté* (1859) rejects the idea of society as a human-made contract.
- (ii) **Sociological Foundations:** Auguste Comte's *Cours de philosophie positive* (1841) critiques contractual individualism, laying groundwork for sociology. Guillaume De Greef's *Introduction à la sociologie* (n.d., late 19th century) and Émile Durkheim's early writings, including *Hobbes à l'agrégation* (2011) and *Montesquieu et Rousseau précurseurs de la sociologie* (1966), reframe the social contract as a product of social evolution.

The Limits of the Bagel Theory

The traditional narrative of social contract theory posits a flourishing period from the seventeenth to eighteenth centuries, followed by a shift to utilitarianism in the nineteenth century, and a revival in the twentieth. This "bagel theory" leaves a historical gap, implying that social contract thought stagnated for over a century. Rather, nineteenth-century social contract revisionists looked elsewhere. By the 1820s, just as utilitarian theory was gaining steam, in France a profoundly different discourse set in.

Revising the social contract became a mainstay of democratic political thought in France. It was certainly no accident that Victor Hugo staged the first shot fired past Marius in the climax of *Les Misérables* on the *rue du Contrat Social*. In her historical fiction *Indiana*, George Sand highlighted the limits of an individualist conception of contract theory when she blamed the despotism and suspiciousness of the heroine's husband on the fact that he "had only ever studied the social contract of *to each his own*." (Sand, 2018, 78). Tocqueville provided his deeply original rendering of Rousseau's work when he recounted the founding of the New England colonies in the second chapter of the first volume of *Democracy in America* (1835) "You must not believe," he argued, "that the piety of the Puritans was only speculative, or that it proved to be unfamiliar with the course of human concerns." Rather, he argued, "they immediately enacted an agreement" which was "the social contract in proper form that Rousseau dreamed of in the following century." In his explicitly *democratic* revision of Rousseau's social contract, Tocqueville posited concrete historical examples of regulation toward social welfare as the foundation of a modern polity.

Hortense Allart, whose *Women and the Democracy of our Times* offered a woman's perspective on the ideas of the *doctrinaires* in the 1840s similarly insisted that Rousseau was the father of modern democracy having "claimed in the Social Contract that all voices in the state were of equal value." (Allart, 1840, 61). In her view, however, his egalitarian ideals had been misapplied during the revolution, which had marginalized the "genius" of Mirabeau in favor of Robespierre's "mediocrity." To overcome such errors, it was necessary, she argued, to transform this legacy, through

a new study of society. “Organize science for this nation, make of it something worthy of the inspiration it has received!” (Ibid., 85). She announced, that “a new political science is necessary.” (Ibid.) “Any social state has its science,” she added, convinced that “man attains beauty through science.” (Ibid., 77). For Allart, this science would reveal not only the true genius inherent in a new French democracy, it would also pave the way for those women with talent to shape the public good.

Pierre-Joseph Proudhon provided one of the most ambitious revisions of contract theory as the Second Republic ended in 1851. He captured the spirit of a revised contract when he suggested that the problem with Rousseau’s social contract was that there was nothing “social” about it. As a result, Rousseau “had understood nothing of social contracts,” Proudhon (1851, 124) argued. In Rousseau’s account, Proudhon continued, “the social contract was not a commutative act nor even an act of society,” but a mere “act of arbiters, chosen by citizens, outside any preestablished convention.” In his view, a “real, positive contract” was rooted in the questions “what do I owe my fellow citizens? What have they promised to myself?” (Ibid., 128). These questions provided the foundation for a social pact that went far beyond guaranteeing individual liberty. It was a question of recognizing the mutual contraction of obligations between social individuals. If one did not have a clear sense of the social responsibility of specific individuals towards specific ends, then “the thousand infractions regulated by the police of cities, countryside, rivers, forests,” Proudhon argued, “were nothing but punishments.” Under such conditions, “your police, your judgments, your enforcement was no more than a series of abusive acts.” (Ibid., 126) Protecting individual liberty was profoundly unjust without a clear sense of social duty. “The social contract must increase welfare and freedom for every citizen.” (Ibid.) The new social contract, Proudhon argued, required the protection of public welfare *and* liberty. To do so, the new social contract needed to push into all those areas that, Proudhon argued, Rousseau had entirely ignored: how to organize work, education, property relations, industrial power, economic rights, transfer of goods, exchange, prices, in other words “that mass of relations that for better or worse, constitute man in perpetual society with his fellow man,” (Ibid., 129) and which animate the subsequent chapters of this book. Elaborating this revisionism, Jules Simon stated that “some free thinkers suppose that society is a social contract, by which they mean an association which is purely of human origin established by will.” Such a conception was misguided, he insisted, since “society is not created by man, whatever Rousseau might argue. It is not a contract between each one of us. We are born in a society and in a society that is already organized.” (Simon, 1859, 154).

In the years that followed, revising the social contract became central to founding the discipline of sociology. Auguste Comte had prepared the terrain for the sociological critique of Rousseau’s social contract, referring to it as “the savage negation of society itself.” (Comte, 1851, 5). In his *Introduction à la sociologie*, Guillaume De Greef (1842-1924) argued that Comte’s positivist ambitions had shattered contractualist notions of individualism and liberty. “The equally absolute theses of ‘the individual against the State’ and ‘the State against the individual’ represent only transient stages of social evolution: the solution of their antinomy is in the development of the social contract, no longer placed with Rousseau, at the beginning of societies, but at their apogee.” (De Greef, 1886). De Greef captured a core contribution of this contractual revisionism: by turning the social contract on its head, he reversed the social contract’s origin. For De Greef the social contract did not find society but rather emerged as a product of increasingly dense and complex social relations that emerged *sui generis* (Follert, 2020). As a result, in his view, the social contract was gradual, accretive, and reciprocal, that is, it emerged to regulate, harmonize, and improve the social relations that always existed between social individuals. “There is no society, in the true sense of the word, except where physiological unity and collective social strength are equally respected. This mutual guarantee can only be approximated by the development and perfection of the social contract.” (De Greef, 1886, 140).

This reversal of early modern social contract theory found its way into the heart of Émile Durkheim's early sociological writings. Challenging Hobbes and Rousseau,^[1] he attempted to align social contract theory with a new, more sociological conception of the social: "If we put all metaphysics aside," Durkheim argued, "a contract is nothing more than a spontaneous adaptation of two or more individuals to each other, under conditions determined by the social and physical environment in which they are placed." (Durkheim, 1886). The new social contract did not found society out of abstract rights-bearing individuals, Durkheim argued. Rather it regulated a social organism that always and already existed at various levels of complexity. In short, Tocqueville, Proudhon, De Greef, and Durkheim's historical and sociological conception of the social contract emerged out of situated relations between individuals. These concrete relationships were then regulated over time to monitor social obligation, ensure individual well-being, and care for collective social development. Such regulation could only be achieved, these authors argued, by developing a strong grasp of the society in which one was living. Hence the structural role of history and sociology in ensuring a social contract in a democratic society.

In this conception, the demos had not formed in a hypothetical, originary, and idealized social contract imagined out of a state of nature. On the contrary, while the demos legitimately self-governed according to a contractual relationship, this process of collective actualization, and the endless demands and shortcomings it produced, took root in an iterative process of popular practice, demands, and administrative responses. In other words, the social contract was revised as a historical, sociological, and pragmatic process through confrontations with problems that were identified as being of public importance. As varied as the problems and solutions were, they were driven by a conviction that the state could hardly be reduced to the elaborate trappings of ceremony and the heteronomy of sovereign authority. In a democracy, government and administration need to address specific public problems and provide clear responses. The regulatory and administrative drive of modern democracy contained a profoundly pragmatic necessity to address the basic problems faced by their communities. It was out of the popular demands for public solutions and the development of responses on the part of public authorities that the foundations of a modern democratic state were constructed.

Recovering this social contract revisionism is not simply a recovery project, it also offers some perspectives for contemporary theoretical considerations on the democratic social contract. Essential to this contribution is understanding how the revised contractualism of the nineteenth century took aim at what was considered a basic shortcoming of previous social contract theories in which free-willing individuals joined together, creating a sovereign general will and in turn, formed a government to ensure its will was effectively executed. In particular, it provides resources for thinking about the social contract as a historically iterative process of elaboration and expansion beyond individual will toward the importance of government and inclusivity within the polity.

As Rawls famously characterized the relationship between the social contract tradition and government, we could think of "the original contract as one to enter a particular society" and "to set up a particular form of government." (Rawls, 1971). In his *On the Social Contract*, Rousseau (1762) concluded that within this process, no doubt a mixed constitution, including some forms of aristocratic and democratic government, would most effectively execute the general will.^[2]

The nineteenth-century sociological revisionism of the contract radically maintained the central ideas of this process, while inverting it. Instead of starting with individuals who used a contract to enter society and set up a government, they started from society. Essential to this view, however, was the idea that democratic society was not transparent to itself. That is, a democratic society needed to be analyzed and understood to be governed. Such an ambition was structured around three imperatives inherent in democratic society: it was (1) made over time, (2) through social

structure, (3) via reflexive self-orientation. These three imperatives of *history*, *sociology*, and *pragmatism* were considered essential to the good governance of modern society. They formed the backdrop for actions and responses of those who sought to build a modern administrative power in the first half of the nineteenth century.

This conception of a cumulative social contractualism provided a precedent for what Jeremy Waldron describes as an “anthropological” contractualism. As opposed to the classic, hypothetical and normative criteria of a classic state of nature, in Waldron’s anthropological alternative “the whole course of the evolution of political institutions out of prepolitical society cannot be seen as a single intentional or consensual process.” Instead, “individual steps in that process can be analyzed and evaluated in contractualist terms.” (Waldron, 1989). The revisionism discussed here shares Waldron’s fundamental argument for a processual contract, exploring the actual historical, sociological, and pragmatic constraints and obligations that shaped our ability to self-govern.

Conclusion

One of the essential lessons of the story told here, which may be profitably deployed within contemporary democratic theory, is the idea that democratic society is formed through what I refer to as a *mixed social constitution*. Such a constitution is not designed to establish a specific type of government. Rather, it structures *how* democratic society may legitimately understand itself in its aim to self-govern. The mixed social constitution undermines the idea that there is a knowable popular will and that such a will should provide the foundation for government and determine the boundaries of the political community. Rather, it revises the social contract, pushing it to both historical and social openness in three ways. First, in response to the social contract’s hypothetical one-time collective covenant between individual wills, the democratized social contract regulates through a historical process of resistance, provisional consent, revision, and accretion. Second, in response to the social contract that posited the formation of a given society as an assemblage of abstract free-willing individuals, the democratized social contract recognizes the structural constraints and opportunities of socially embedded individuals. Third, in response to the early modern social contract’s focus on rights preservation, the democratic social contract emphasizes the ends of administrative action, regulatory intervention, and social obligation. These branches of the mixed social constitution provide a foundation for the legitimate exercise of public power in democratic society. Legitimate governance in this view is neither the product of a formal agreement between wills nor a hypothetical compact to preserve abstract rights; it is rather a general disposition to legitimately guide and regulate a democratic society toward its own self-determined ends over time.

Reckoning with this lost era of social contract theory will be essential as we continue to build in new directions on the important innovations of social contract theory that began in the mid-twentieth century and have found themselves so battered in our contemporary world.

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^[1] Durkheim wrote explicitly about Hobbes's social contract theory in a course for the French national exam, the agrégation, see Durkheim (2011) and Rousseau's social contract in Durkheim (1918).

^[2] As Rousseau argued in the opening to his chapter on "Mixed Government": "Strictly speaking, there's no such thing as a simple or unmixed government."

Contribution 4: The EU social contract

Claudia Wiesner, Fulda University of Applied Sciences (Claudia.wiesner@sk.hs-fulda.de)

Introduction

The core question in the following is whether and to what extent the EU can be said to be based on a social contract (SC). This discussion is based on a short genealogy of how social contracts have been previously theorized in the history of ideas. This genealogy reveals a series of core conceptual questions and puzzles that need to be generally addressed by social contract theories.

The nexus between citizens and governors (bottom-up), on the one hand, and government to citizens (top-down) as well as among the citizens as demos is key to understanding social contracts and their current challenges.

Any stable social contract will rely on

1. a legitimate foundation that usually has a legal dimension and works in a top-down direction (this can be a constitution) and
2. a bottom-up basis, namely citizens and their support and identification of the social contract in a broad sense.
3. Horizontal links between the citizens.

The question leading the following considerations is: how the top-down, bottom-up and horizontal dimensions of a social may be conceptualised, and what kind of explicit/ formal and implicit/ tacit consent do they entail – or not?

Methodological nationalism – and why there is so little academic debate about the EU Social Contract

There is a first very important remark to make on the validity of the SC concept for the EU. SC is a concept that originated in Political Theory jointly with the development of nation-states. Accordingly, it is not only traditionally referencing nation-states and nations – we also face a problem of methodological nationalism, i.e., the fact that the SC is above all focused on nation-states. SC theories at least implicitly referring to the nation both conceptually and empirically means that they will per se not apply to the EU - which is not based on a nation. Social contract theories, however, are linked to the history of nation-building and relation to state-building, or – if they are more recent – they refer to nation-states.

This reflection underlines, on one hand, that the EU indicates the limits of SC theories – they are not fully applicable for the multilevel system that the EU is. The EU does not have a nation, and does the EU have a society? On the other hand, if social contract theories are based on nation states and nations, the question is to what extent these concepts are applicable to the EU?

Interestingly, the problem in EU theorizing often is a complementary one. There is a bias towards methodological nationalism in parts of the EU political-theoretical literature. Categories and criteria according to which the EU's political system and its democratic situation are judged often are explicitly or implicitly taken from established mainstream interpretations of concepts. In particular, in several contributions, the criteria according to which the EU's democratic quality is judged are – again, explicitly or implicitly – taken from the example of nation-states, in a static and a-temporal use. The German debate on an EU demos development (see Kielmannsegg 2003; Scharpf 1998 and Wiesner 2020) is a good example of this: several contributors speak of inappropriateness of institutional EU democratization, using a-temporal understandings of key concepts like demos and democracy, and not taking into account that today's democracies developed over time and continue to develop.

But the EU cannot simply be judged according to the same criteria and categories as a nation-state. In terms of conceptual history, the nation-state is a contingent result of definite historical constellations in Europe, especially in the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries. Nation states, hence, have themselves been contested and controversial. Understanding conceptual changes in European unification does not only mean extension (amplification) of the nation-state paradigm. On the contrary, it requires relativizing this paradigm and creatively applying forms of political practices and institutions independently of their organization levels (Wiesner 2019, 27).

This is why the following considerations are based on a more general approach, focusing on a genealogy of core problems of social contracts in general.

Core problems of social contracts – a genealogy

“A genealogy is a methodological tool in intellectual and conceptual history (on the concept of representation see Urbinati, 2006; on the concept of the state see Skinner, 2009). Different from a classical literature review, a genealogy summarizes the main lines and traditions of thinking on a concept, the key controversies, predominant understandings, and crucial issues of conceptualizing it. The goal of the following genealogy therefore is accordingly to trace these controversies, different understandings and core questions. The criterion for selection of the literature in the following accordingly is the relevance and contribution of a respective text to the conceptual debate on legitimacy. It focuses on those contributions that made crucial arguments and emphasize the key issues of the conceptual controversy.” (Wiesner and Harfst 2022, 3)

A genealogy of how social contracts have been previously theorized in the history of ideas reveals a series of core conceptual questions and puzzles that need to be generally addressed by social contract theories:

The nexus between citizens and governors (bottom-up), on the one hand, and government to citizens (top-down) as well as among the citizens as demos is key to understanding social contracts and their current challenges.

This means that a social contract is not merely a constitution, i.e. a legal document that has been concluded in a top-down way but also consists of bottom-up identification and support by the citizens.

Founding Actors and founding act

Who found the social contract? And what does this mean? Is a foundation needed? In most conceptual literature, the social contract is constructed as a fiction, in the sense of a hypothetical contract between the citizens or the citizens to be, where the demos act as both source and result of the act of foundation. The influence of social contract theories on European political history notwithstanding, modern Western societies are, in legal and political practice, based on constitutions – which can be seen as legal expressions of and frameworks for social contracts. Constitutions are usually written and decided upon by selected high-level representatives, rather than the demos itself.

Relation of SC to constitution

The relation of a social contract to a constitution is not a simple one. While the constitution acts as the legal foundation of the polity as a political community and defines the demos of the polity, it is not identical to the social contract. The constitution effects a particular depersonalization of power and anticipates the constitutional state, that is the subordination of the sovereign to the law, but it nevertheless – as all social and political imaginaries do – requires the identification and support of the people/ citizens. It was not unsurprisingly therefore soon accompanied by the personification of the nation (Koschorke et al. 2007).

Invested with a new claim to generality and a higher level of abstraction, the nation provides a new body for the decorporated society of the French Revolution but given that “absolute beginnings are not possible in the political realm” reverts to a “hostile takeover” (Ibid.) of old monarchical and Christian elements. The latter points to the fact that the constitution alone struggles to provide enough affective cohesion and grounds for societal identification, necessary for a stable and resilient social contract.

Relation of SC to common good

The “common good” encompasses the general aim that the demos united in a polity and by a social contract should have common interests and that these should be reflected in the aims of the polity, the goals outlined in the constitution and in general the policies carried out.

Relation to welfare state: what follows from SC postulate?

Some decades after the ideas of constitution and nation/nation states, the ideas of social contract and common good were at the basis of the development of welfare states which incorporate, in theory, the idea of equality between citizens, although in practice they have been the outcome of political struggles.

An EU social contract? Conceptual questions and solutions

Again, the question then is to what extent the question after a social makes sense for EU at all. After what has just been said, it needs to be reframed or rethought into the three elements named above:

1. The legal or top-down dimension, which includes the EU Treaties and the question to what extent these work as a constitution, and which might include EU citizenship (Wiesner 2017, 2019, 144–61).
2. The bottom-up identification of citizens
3. The horizontal identification among citizens

The first question will be discussed below. The two others lead over to the question after the EU Demos and or EU identity.

Top-down / legal foundation

We might argue there is a legal foundation of an EU social contract if we see the Treaty ratification as founding moment and/or the Treaties as constitution. Based on the various EU Treaties, the EU developed by and by (Wiesner 2019). European integration has been largely “integration through law” (e.g. (Bogdandy 2024); (Joerges 2016).

The Treaty on European Union (TEU) in this represents a key step: Until 1992, the EU was a supranational organization and a regulatory state (Majone 1998). In 1992, the Political Union was added, a citizenship was created, and the Common Market Treaty was complemented by many classical elements of a constitution.

This moment can be interpreted as the founding moment in which the “philosopher kings” in shape of the heads of state and government on Maastricht concluded on the quasi-constitution.

There are a couple of other open questions to this account. The TEU is de facto a constitution, i.e., it works as such. However, the question is whether in this the European Council can be compared to a constitutional convention. Moreover, there was a constitutional convention that until 2005 issued a draft constitutional treaty that was rejected in two referenda and then not ratified.

It can be argued, on the one hand, that all this did not create a social contract but just a legal framework. Especially the horizontal social contract, i.e. a European Demos, seems to be missing (see below and Wiesner 2024, 2020).

As opposed to this claim, Bogdandy argues that it was precisely integration through law that created a European democratic society, i.e., a full-fledged social contract (Bogdandy 2024). Moreover, integration entailed several frictions with existing social contracts especially in the welfare state dimension (Joerges 2016; Scharpf 1999; Wiesner 2019).

The Treaties as constitution?

The constitution-like character of the Treaties can be contested. First, the now existing Treaties still have a quasi-constitutional character but are explicitly not called “constitution”. Secondly, the EU Treaties entail both a horizontal contract between sovereign nation states with rights and obligations in a multilateral European community as well as a vertical contract between European citizens and European Union. Thirdly, the EU gives rise to a ‘constitutional enigma’ (Zetterquist 2007), since although it possesses no sovereign power, it nevertheless exercises a considerable amount of state power – legislative, executive and judicative – over both Member states and European individuals alike.

Zetterquist is one of the few academics that explicitly discussed the question of an EU social contract, more precisely the question to what extent the Treaties and the existing legal landscape of the EU build a social contract. His arguments will therefore be discussed at some length. Interestingly, the supreme power of EC law over Member states’ own constitutions cannot be found in the Treaties, nor has it been explicitly acknowledged by the Member States. An argument against the constitutional character of the EU thus may resort to the formal fact that Member States never signed up to a European constitution. Zetterquist (2007) argues that one can nevertheless speak of a ‘constitutionalisation’ of the Treaties that took place in the 1960s via the case law of the Court of Justice of the European Communities (ECJ). The constitutional character of EC law was ultimately founded on the claim of the ECJ that the EC qualified as a constitutional legal order rather than a traditional intergovernmental organisation (ibid).

Zetterquist recognises the paradox of foundation, as the supremacy of EU law over Member state constitutional law was ‘strictly speaking, a legal impossibility, since it would be contrary to the constitutions that enabled the Member states to conclude the treaties [in the first place] ... The slightly odd situation is then that the Member states... are legally precluded from conferring constitutional authority on this organisation. On such a view it could be argued that the system of international law [...] is incapable of achieving the objective of the social contract, namely the quitting of the (European) state of nature’ (341).

According to Zetterquist, two elements were required for the constitutional legitimacy of the EU: First, historically, the ECJ took the role of an ‘external solution’, that is, an element not available in the social contract model, to bring about the transition from state of nature to civil society. Second, constitutional legitimacy was strengthened by the protection of fundamental rights of the individual, placing ‘hitherto unprecedented emphasis on the position of the individual in international law’. Together these elements transformed EC law from a law between Member states, to a law within Member states.

It is precisely the emphasis on the individual that brings Zetterquist to argue that the Treaties do not only form a contract, but a social contract, since its universalistic and individualistic foundation proves more readily adaptable to supra-national constitutional theory than collectivist notions like the nation or historical community (323). Similar to Bogdandy (2024) Zetterquist argues the EU to

be a Lockean ‘political Community’, i.e. situated ‘half-way’ between the state of nature and political society’s Commonwealth but failing to fulfill the second stage of the Lockean social contract, i.e. it is not yet a full democratic polity (343).

Despite the constitutional importance of individual rights, however, he admits that ‘the idea of individual consent has historically been the weak spot of social contract theory. Such consent can rarely, if ever, be established to have occurred and if expressed may be for entirely other reasons than those of the legitimacy of the social order. Hobbes and Locke both resorted to the idea of a tacit consent to solve the problem of consent, but tacit consent is also problematic from a contractualist point of view’ (328).

Even though we might thus argue that the legal fiction exists – supposing the EC in 1992 or then the founding moment or the Euratom and ECSC and/or the EEC were enough – the second part of the social contract, the imaginaries and narratives, are weakly developed.

Continuous construction of social contracts

To what extent does the EU show the other elements of a social contract, i.e. horizontal identification and bottom-up identification?

Continuous construction of social contracts refers to democratic activity such as participating in elections, demonstrations – to an active demos (Wiesner 2024, 3).

From a normative point of view, democracy, regardless of whether it is based on a republican, a communitarian or a liberal model, must not only consist of electoral and civil rights, but also of democratic practice. For a representative democratic polity, this means that its democratic institutions and procedures must be supported by a democratic subject, a demos, which to a certain minimum extent should also define itself as such.

These reflections lead to the concept of “democratic identity” discussed in more detail below. It describes both the bottom-up and the horizontal dimensions of the social contract:

Democratic identity then implies this self-definition of the demos, i.e., 1) an awareness of and identification with the polity to which rights and democratic practice refer and, 2) a mutual identification and recognition of the demos’ members. Democratic identity thus concerns processes of identification that go in two directions: First, horizontally, between citizens who recognise each other as members of a demos; and second, vertically, from citizens to the system level and government, identifying with them and accepting their policy outputs (Wiesner 2024, 23).

Does the EU have a Demos?

In Political Science and EU studies, the EU’s democratic deficits have been intensely debated regarding the strengths and weaknesses of the EU’s institutional system since the 1990s (for an overview see Føllesdal and Hix 2006). Another strand of the democratic deficit debate regards the question of whether the EU has, or can obtain, a proper democratic subject, a demos. This strand hence regards the affective dimensions behind the mechanisms of legitimation in representative democracy. Input legitimacy, this is the core argument, requires a democratic subject, a demos,

that has a certain affective link to the EU. In the academic debate, it is often argued that the EU population is a long way from being such a demos.

I have discussed the question of whether the EU can develop a full-fledged demos and whether it is on the way in this direction at length elsewhere (see in detail Wiesner 2014, 2024). For the purposes of this chapter, I will address the main questions and arguments in the conceptual academic debate.

The question of EU demos formation has been raised particularly in German contributions, which have argued, first, that a mere democratisation of EU institutions (like an improvement of the competences of the European Parliament) is not sufficient (Scharpf 1998; Kielmannsegg 2003; Habermas 2005) because representative democracy needs to be based on a democratic subject, a demos.

Following Lincoln's well-known formula democracy is government of, by, and for the people. This leads to distinguishing three decisive directions and components of the relations between citizens, their representatives and government. The input dimension refers to the citizens and their rights and possibilities for participation and contestation, as well as the right to elect their representatives. Throughput refers to the representatives being accountable; the procedures of election and government in the representative system must be organized transparently and follow the rule of law, and possibly the ideal of the separation of powers (Schmidt 2013). The output dimension refers to the decisions taken by the representatives satisfying the majority of the represented.

It is the input dimension that is of utmost importance to the question of demos formation, as it entails the decisive normative interrelation between the practice of democracy and the development of a demos lined out above: Democracy, no matter if it is conceptualised following a republican, communitarian or liberal ideal, needs not only elections and citizenship rights, but also a minimum of democratic practice (meaning participation, contestation and representation). Consequently, democratic institutions and procedures must be carried out and should also be actively filled by a democratic subject, a demos, that defines itself as such, at least to a minimum extent.

This self-definition and self-identification of a democratic subject, then, can be termed democratic identity (see in detail Wiesner 2014, 2024), and it is necessary in a democratic polity for several reasons. It is a condition for political activity that the demos be at least conscious of the fact that it is linked to a respective polity—that is, people should consider themselves as members of that polity. If this is not the case, people will not direct their political activity to it. Moreover, to make redistributive policies acceptable, the members of the demos should mutually identify themselves as such—again, if this is not the case, redistributive policies are not impossible but will be hardly accepted beyond a minimum degree (Wiesner 2019, 27: 249-260).

I hence argue that the democratic subject needs, at least to a minimum extent, a) to define itself as such (mutual recognition of the citizens or demos members), b) to identify with the EU as a polity (for example, by identification and support) and c) to be politically active in the EU as a polity (Wiesner 2014, 38–43). So far, I agree with the argument made in the demos debate.

The chicken and egg question of demos building

When it comes to the development of a demos, the academic debate, particularly in Germany, also indicates there are two approaches to the processes that can or will lead to EU demos formation.

First, there are the adherents of the no demos thesis, many of them German academics. Their argument can be summed up as such: currently, the EU does not show – or does not show enough of – a democratic identity among the population, a European public space, or a European civil society. Therefore, it lacks crucial elements of a demos. These are seen as preconditions (not only conditions) for EU democratisation by the defenders of the no demos thesis, for whom further democratisation of the EU would not only be unwise but could also be dangerous from a normative point of view (e.g. Scharpf 1998; Kielmannsegg 2003).

What is the main content of the argument? The no demos thesis postulates a normatively binding succession in times of demos-building and democratisation. It argues that before institution-based democratisation (like an empowerment of the European Parliament) may take place, the development of an EU demos is needed, consisting in the development of a European identity, a European public space and a European civil society.

The no demos thesis, in sum, postulates a pre-political identity as a precondition for the further democratisation of the EU. It implies a formula that claims democratisation to follow demos-building. This also, and obviously, means that the legal framework of European citizenship described above is insufficient for establishing a demos. Looking at the current debate on the EU, one notices that the no demos thesis is still frequently defended (see e.g. Streeck 2014).

The opposing approach is more constructivist and claims that this postulate must be declined, first from a normative point of view: democratic identity as well as a European public space or a European civil society can and probably will develop within (representative) democratic institutions and democratic practice. It is democratic citizenship that enables this development (Habermas 2005; Lepsius 1999).

Moreover, as will be argued in more detail later, pre-political identities do not exist. A comparative look at historical demos-building processes shows that identity formation first and democratisation following has simply never occurred in practice in the simplified way suggested by the defenders of the no demos thesis. To sum up: the no demos thesis is much too simple, because demos-building processes are far more complex and consist of mutual dependencies between institutional components and different aspects of democratic practice. Furthermore, the no demos thesis is circular, because it implies a permanent repetition of negative circumstances that must forever hinder demos-building.

But the discussion that has been briefly sketched underlines some important aspects that characterize the relation between demos formation and democratisation: first, the demos question is crucial for the further democratisation of the EU, since democratisation is not only to be understood as institution-based, but also as the development of democratic practice. Second, both approaches that have been presented hint at four decisive components of a demos: a democratic identity, a European public space, a European civil society and democratic citizenship. They also agree on the fact that at least three of these elements – democratic identity, a European public space and a European civil society – are currently missing or incomplete in the EU.

Yet, the two approaches disagree firstly on the question of whether a European demos can or will develop, because they disagree secondly on the presumed ways and chronological orders in which it could develop. Whereas the no demos thesis claims the normative ideal of demos-building preceding democratisation, which has been discussed and rejected, the more constructivist approach is based on the idea that demos-building and identity formation will go hand in hand with the development of democratic practice. The syllable 'pre' in this respect indicates a decisive normative as well as methodological difference: demos-building is not a precondition for EU democratisation, but an indicator of a sufficiently successful democratisation process.

Following this normative and conceptual perspective, the chances of EU demos formation can be characterized as follows: the EU is not at the beginning of its democratisation, but it is – despite its democratic deficits – the best developed example of a democratically organized transnational political entity. Therefore, the development of an EU demos and its elements is no longer at its strict beginning, either. But the four demos-elements mentioned have not yet reached an equal status quo. Whereas EU citizenship, at least in a legal sense, has been developing decisively over the last 25 years, active citizenship is not developed to a similar extent. The same is true for the development of a European public space and an EU civil society, as well as for the development of a European identity. But democratic identity (as well as a European public space and a European civil society) can (and probably will) further develop through democratic practice and active citizenship at the EU level. It can be assumed that the development of the demos elements of citizenship, identity, public space and civil society will be mutually interdependent. The further discussion will concentrate on the component of self-definition of a demos, democratic identity.

What is European identity?

It is hence no surprise that since the 1990s the question of further EU democratisation has been more and more discussed in relation to the question of the formation of a European identity. But what exactly does European, or EU identity mean from a normative and methodological point of view?

As has been said above, democratic identity means the self-identification of a democratic subject. EU identity, then, is often depicted as a type of “collective identity”. Constructivist research on nationalism of the last decades has shown that this term needs to be further specified and criticised. The results of the research of Benedict Anderson (2006), Ernest Gellner (1983) and Eric Hobsbawm (2008) can be summed up as follows: first, collective identity is not something that is naturally existing or pre-political but is socially constructed. Second, collective identity is not static, but open to change. There are no stable collective identities, only narratives that are historically changing. Third, democracies do not rely on a homogeneous people or nation, but on heterogeneous societies comprising multiple different groups and interests. Fourth, even though they are related to regions or countries, identities are not necessarily linked to fixed geographical areas. Fifth, there are no simple or monolithic identities. Identities, on the contrary, are always complex and they express belongings on all levels of human existence. Sixth, the term collective identity can only be used in the sense that collectively shared memories, values and identifications are always a part of individual identity.

This means that the phenomenon can be more accurately termed a collective pattern of individual identifications than a collective identity in the proper sense. Benedict Anderson famously spoke of “imagined communities” (Anderson 2006). These collective patterns of individual identifications are socially constructed. What is at stake is that the EU population needs to develop a minimum level

of identification with the EU polity and a minimum set of collectively shared values. It also needs a minimum level of civic trust in and support of the EU (the next question is, of course, what “minimum” might mean in this sense).

To sum up: European identity formation is not a precondition for EU democratisation, but democratic identity is what defines a demos, and the existence of a demos is a normative condition for a democratic system that can be termed fully developed. European identity does not have to exist before further EU democratisation can start, but the degree of development of a European identity will be an indicator for the quality of the EU democratisation process. The democratisation process therefore can well go on without yet having a strong European identity—but from a normative point of view, it should get stronger over time.

Empirical findings

The results of empirical studies and discourse analyses on EU identity construction indicate that when not searching for an identity that can be directly compared to national identity, elements of a European identity can already be found. But they appear to be different from national identity. Moreover, the results can be differentiated into two types: there are a) survey findings that tend to regard the micro-level of citizens, their support for and their identification with the EU, as well as their trust in the EU; and b) there are results of discourse analyses rather regarding the macro- and meso-levels of large-scale national discourses and narratives, which tend to analyse the work of political elites.

Regarding the empirical findings on EU citizens, there is good reason to argue that a demos is in development in the EU (see in detail Wiesner 2014, 55–60, 2024, 42–51). Taking the most recent Eurobarometer Survey results, more than two-thirds of EU citizens fully or to a certain degree feel that they are citizens of the EU (74%). This number has been continuously increasing in the last 15 years, coming from a level of 62% in 2010 (Eurobarometer 2024: 28). In all Member States, the majority of respondents say they feel like a citizen of the EU (fully or to a certain extent). There are, however, considerable national variations spanning from 88% of respondents partially or fully identifying as European in Luxembourg, and 86% in both Portugal and Finland to 59% in Bulgaria, 61% in Greece and 65% in Romania, Italy, France, and Czechia (Eurobarometer 2024: 29).

Without claiming that such a feeling of EU citizenship is enough for strong input legitimacy that also justifies redistributive policies, I argue that it perfectly justifies the EU citizens to be the demos electing the European Parliament (EP). But it is also true that, besides this EU-related demos, the EU will depend on the stronger demoi in the member states and their member state-related input legitimacy in the future, which speaks all the more in favour of taking the whole multi-level system into consideration when speaking about democracy in the EU. In sum, we can speak of related demoi: the stronger, older national ones and the newly developing, weaker, EU-related demoi.

While surveys analyse individuals' opinions, the discourse analyses concentrate on EU elites, that is, politicians and leading national media. Empirical results are mostly in accordance with these survey findings (see in detail Wiesner 2014, 60–65, 2024, 42–51). They underline that national and European identities are related in their construction processes. However, there are different national narratives of European identification. These findings fit with survey findings indicating that European identity is part of a multilevel system of identities. Finally, identity construction processes

in the EU are indeed similar to national identity construction. Like national identity, European identity is constructed in discourse and is enforced by institutions and socio-economic structures. In Europe, it has also been important, like in national states, to distinguish an 'Other' (EU politicians thus often distance themselves from the US or Asia), and to refer to positive founding myths.

In sum and for discussion

The answer to the question whether the EU has a social contract depends on the understanding of social contract. If we ask for a legal dimension, there are arguments enough to claim that the Treaties build a constitution. Considering the other two components for a social contract, the bottom-up dimension and the horizontal dimension, they are different in the EU from what they are in nation states, and they seem to be weaker in the EU than in member states. Concretely, the EU has a weakly developed Demos and a weakly developed European Identity (Wiesner 2024). The social and the imaginative component of the social contract in the EU is weaker than the ones in member states.

However, even though the imaginary part [aka national identity] may be better developed in the member states – it is also this imaginary part that causes the current frictions. Playing the devil's advocate we might argue that it might be an advantage for the EU that the narratives are only weakly developed?

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Contribution 5: Normative beliefs about justice and the social contract in Europe

Ruzha Smilova (Centre for Liberal Strategies)

Introduction

Justice principles are key elements of the social contract (SC) in contemporary democratic societies. The traditional SC theories (those of Hobbes, Locke, Rousseau and Kant) had rather limited ambitions. They mostly aimed at guaranteeing security and basic rights, or freedom, and had little concern for social justice (CO3, Mapping the theories of social contract: An overview, Colin-Jaeger, 7). After the Rawlsian moment, which marked the “rebirth of the social contract” (ibid., 8), however, the principles of justice became its central element. John Rawls, for example, uses the SC framework to propose a procedure for selecting principles of justice that are fair and can serve as the foundation to build just society. Following in his footsteps, many theorists worked within this framework to defend a range of principles of justice - as based on mutual advantage, on reciprocity, impartiality, etc.

After briefly elaborating on the link between principles of justice and SC, based on the work of John Rawls, I discuss his dismissal of desert-based accounts of distributive justice. Rawls’ position is striking given the intuitive appeal for the general public of desert as the ground of just distribution and its long-held status as the default positions on matters of distributive justice.

Turning to the normative beliefs of Europeans regarding justice, I analyze recent data (ESS Round 9, 2018, Social Justice panel), which demonstrate the preeminence of beliefs on desert as a ground of just distribution. These data show that the Equity principle (‘A society is fair when hard-working people earn more than others’) enjoys overwhelming support among Europeans - in some European societies of as many as 90% and in no European society it is supported by less than $\frac{2}{3}$ majority. Furthermore, the Equity principle is much better supported than the Equality principle (“A society is fair when income and wealth are equally distributed among all people”), though the Need principle (“A society is fair when those in need are supported irrespective of whether they can give back to society”) also enjoys considerable support. I interpret these results on the normative beliefs (preferences) of Europeans regarding principles of justice in light of the recent debates around meritocracy. I argue that the meritocratic ideal for ordering society is inextricably linked with the Equity principle and that it should be taken seriously despite the mounting - both philosophical and social-psychological - criticisms against it. My contribution also engages with the preeminent recent philosophical critique of meritocracy, advanced by Michael Sandel (2020) and I aim to demonstrate the shortfalls of his proposed solution to the meritocracy problem.

Lastly, I argue that people's beliefs about justice - and their overwhelming normative preference for the Equity principle - should be taken seriously. Such views should not be easily dismissed as just an 'ideological trap' set by neoliberal elites conspiring against the people. Influential accounts of justice - including those developed within the social contract framework - leave little normative space for individual merits or deserts as grounds for justice claims. This insensitivity to desert sets limits to their normative appeal for people holding rather different views on justice. It also limits their explanatory power: when people are frustrated that the social contract is broken - as institutions do not meet their expectations to embody and guarantee justice - they might have very different complaints against the state than the ones a Rawlsian or a Scanlonian theory of justice would predict.

A brief survey of the relevant literature

I will not elaborate on Rawls' general SC argument for his two principles of justice (already covered in section 3 of Colin-Jaeger's mapping of SC theories in the first contribution to this deliverable). Instead, I focus on Rawls' well-known argument in TJ against desert-based principles of justice (Rawls 1971), which had such an impact on political philosophy, that "to date most philosophers regard the quest for a desert-based theory of justice as a fool's errand, on Rawlsian grounds" (Mulligan 2018, 12). The main objection to such principles is that they make economic benefits depend on factors beyond one's control, which are arbitrary from a moral point of view (Rawls 1971, p. 102-104). Rawls' argument has been adopted by political philosophers with widely diverging views on justice. It has become the canonical position. Yet, Rawls' position is puzzling as desert-based views are widely held by the general public and this contradicts his own "commitment to developing a theory of justice that, while not mirroring 'common sense morality' in every detail, nevertheless remains sufficiently close to it that the theory can be seen as a rational reconstruction of what people ordinarily believe about justice." (Miller 2021).

Even though desert-based views about justice remain popular - and the wide acclaim of meritocratic ideals in many western societies well demonstrates this - meritocracy (henceforth M) has been subjected to vehement critiques from diverse corners of the ideological spectrum. Both liberal egalitarians and communitarians have advanced forceful criticisms. There are different claims about the ills M brings. Some claim that the meritocratic dream - the ideal that the talented and the hard working deserve to get ahead - has been betrayed by self-serving 'meritocratic' elites (Lasch 1994). As an ideal of justice M has proven counterproductive as it drives up inequality without also promoting upward social mobility (Mijs 2016, Littler 2017, Markovits 2019). As David Miller acknowledges, "Part of this repugnance is no doubt due to the ideological use of desert to justify gross economic inequalities" (Miller 2021).

Merit is also tyrannical, claims Michael Sandel in the most sophisticated philosophical critique of M to date, as it also arguably destabilizes and ultimately threatens to destroy political communities (Sandel 2020). Following the critical line developed by Sandel, one may maintain that M as an ideal erodes the social contract and undermines the cohesive political communities, on which well-functioning democracies are built.

There are also those who speak in defense of desert-based principles of justice and support M as an ideal for just society. Thomas Mulligan (2018), for example, has taken the position that individual desert should be the basis of justice for contemporary Western societies. He argues that the stand-off in the academic debate over justice between the two main contemporary traditions: egalitarianism and libertarianism, can be overcome by reverting to the age-old idea that “we should give people the things that they deserve” (ibid.)

More recently, a sceptic of desert-based principles such as Thomas Scanlon has refined his position. In “Giving desert its due” he evaluates arguments that desert may play some limited role in distributive justice, noting that “the appeal of desert-based ideas of justice is more piecemeal. It derives from the plausibility of claims that economic distribution should be sensitive to particular forms of merit [effort, valuable contribution, etc.] ... rather than on the general idea that justice depends on desert.” Ultimately, he rejects the view “that desert has a fundamental role in the justification of significant differences in economic benefit” yet admits that desert “may make small monetary prizes appropriate” (Scanlon 2017). For Scanlon, then, the problem with desert is with the enormous distributional inequalities justified in its name, though he admits that distributions may be desert sensitive.

Meritocracy delivering on its promises was behind the unprecedented economic and human development that modernity brought about, argues Adrian Wooldridge (2021). He holds that the promise for upward social mobility unleashed human talent and brought economic and human development. The high legitimacy (boosting upward social mobility), and the unprecedented human development, resulting from the dominance of the meritocratic ideal, arguably contributed to the triumph of liberalism as the victorious ideology.

Justice principles and the Social Contract

Justice principles are key elements of the social contract in contemporary democratic societies. The traditional social contract theories (those of Hobbes, Locke, Rousseau and Kant) had a rather limited scope and primarily aimed “to secure fundamental goods, such as security, property rights, or freedom, but were not concerned with more demanding goods, such as social justice” (see Contribution 1 by Colin-Jaeger). After the Rawlsian moment, which marked the “rebirth of the social contract” (ibid. p.8), however, the principles of justice became its central element. John Rawls, for example, uses the SC framework to propose a procedure for selecting principles of justice that are fair and can serve as the foundation for just society. Following in his footsteps, many more theorists worked within the social contract framework, to defend different principles of justice - as based on reciprocity and mutual advantage (Gauthier, Buchanan), on impartiality (Barry), on reasonableness (Scanlon), etc.

No place for desert?

A striking feature of the contemporary accounts of justice developed from within the SC framework is the absence of a principle that has long been believed to be part of justice claims. This principle in its crudest form holds that one should get what one deserves. In its contemporary form it comes

in the form of a “meritocratic principle”, according to which the talented and the hard working should get ahead in society.

Desert-based principles of justice have been discredited by an argument developed by John Rawls which gained prominence and almost universal endorsement. He famously argued that desert is not a serious contender for a principle of justice for the basic structure of society as it makes economic benefits depend on factors over which people have little control - hence they can neither take credit for them, nor can they be rewarded on this ground. For John Rawls, even a system of fair equality of opportunity that fully compensated for the effects of class and other inherited social differences would not make for a just society. This is because in a completely even, level playing field, the winners would be the most talented. Yet differences of talent and other abilities are as morally arbitrary as are differences of class, or any other undeserved social circumstances. Hence, these differences are a matter of morally arbitrary ‘natural lottery’, which, in the same way as all other circumstances beyond one’s control, should not be allowed to affect just distributions (Rawls 1971, 101-104). After all, “no one deserves his place in the distribution of native endowments” (Ibid., 104).

Rawls’ dismissal of desert-based accounts of distributive justice is striking given the intuitive appeal of desert as the ground for just distribution for the general public and their long-held status as the default positions on matters of distributive justice. “It is interesting to observe how deeply the notion of justice as desert or merit is embedded in human history. It seems a pre-reflective, basic idea of primordial or Ur-justice. One finds it grounded in every known culture and religion” (Pojman 1999: 90, quoted in Mulligan 2023). Today, too, “desert plays a leading role in most people’s idea of distributive justice. When asked how jobs, salaries, prizes and other such benefits should be assigned, they are likely to say that they should be given to those who deserve them, by performing well in the relevant social sphere” (Miller 2021).

Rawls’ position against desert is puzzling. David Miller has argued that Rawls’ criticism of widely held views about justice is in tension with his “commitment to developing a theory of justice that, while not mirroring ‘common sense morality’ in every detail, nevertheless remains sufficiently close to it that the theory can be seen as a rational reconstruction of what people ordinarily believe about justice” (Miller 2021). We can put the same point in Rawls’ own words: (1) in order to be principles of justice and not of something else entirely, these principles should be in “a reflective equilibrium with citizens’ well considered convictions on justice”, and (2) these principles should align with citizens’ views to be able to guide their conduct. This second, normative condition is imposed by the ‘strains of commitment’ test, which excludes as plausible candidates for foundation principles of justice principles that cannot be followed as they are judged by citizens to be too alien to their deeply held convictions.

Some authors argue that desert has resurfaced as distribution-relevant consideration in luck egalitarianism: “many luck egalitarians invoke desert, whether explicitly or implicitly” (Segall 2015: 355, quoted in Brouwer and Mulligan 2019). Yet, as Huub Brouwer and Tim Mulligan demonstrate, luck

egalitarians such as Gerry Cohen, Richard Arneson and Eric Rakowski are rather dismissive towards desert, and at best allow it to play a marginal role in just distributions (Brouwer and Mulligan 2019).

The wide acclaim to which the meritocratic ideal has been held across many western societies for many decades has not spared it criticism from positions covering a wide ideological and methodological spectrum. One would assume that right-libertarians would have sympathy for desert-sensitive distributions, yet they either dismiss any 'patterned' distributions, including desert-based ones (Nozick 1974), or take the free market to produce the only mechanism for allocating goods that is compatible with liberty, yet rightly point out that free markets do not necessarily reward merit (Hayek 1960). While the growing inequality associated with this ideal (as it justifies meritocratically produced inequalities) make egalitarian left liberals its natural critics, the most philosophically elaborate critique came from the prominent "communitarian" opponent of liberalism - Michael Sandel.

Meritocracy - the ideal and its failings

Meritocracy (M) as an ideal for ordering society has contributed to the appeal of liberal democracy (LD). Its promise is that governing elites in LD are recruited entirely based on their own personal merits—talent and effort. The same holds true for everybody else's place in society: no circumstances beyond one's control (accidents of birth, privileged social milieu, loving and caring parents, elite school, etc.) should affect one's chances of career advancement and personal success. Only the best qualified make it to the top positions in society. And they do so solely for their own merits.

Meritocracy promises more than competent bureaucratic rule with egalitarian access. It offers an ideal for ordering society, which defines success and allocates each person's place in society—with all the rewards that follow—according to own personal 'merits'.

Meritocracy has two necessary elements:

1. access to position under fair equality of opportunity (henceforth FEO) and
2. success based solely on personal merit (talent+effort), i.e. merit-based success.

The promise - decisions taken by 'meritocratic' elites will be more competent and would tend to produce better results (than the obvious alternatives - nepotism or lottery). Delivering on its promises - of competent elite rule with egalitarian access and distributing rewards and social status according to personal merit was arguably behind the unprecedented economic and human development that modernity brought about (Wooldridge 2021).

Against this success story, the cascading critiques against M may come as a surprise. Why think that M could be a main cause for the erosion of community and a prime driver for growing populist support, as many have argued? Some find the flaws in the ideal, others - in how it is practiced.

The promises of Meritocracy

The attractiveness of meritocracy is two-fold: moral and pragmatic.

1. At the **moral level** it promises fair, merit-based elite recruitment, and merit-based upward social mobility.

It strikes a difficult balance here: between the democratic egalitarian principle of equal participation (each an equal say in decision-making) and the fact that in representative liberal democracies, elites de facto make decisions. M promises an equal and fair ex-ante chance of making it to the top, opening the door to each to compete on equal terms for position in decision-making elites.

Social mobility promise is also a compromise: between the egalitarian fundament of democratic societies (each, as an equal citizen, has equal worth and should be assigned equal status) and the fact of persistent wealth and status hierarchies in complex contemporary societies. In a democratic society, these hierarchies may stay only on condition that each citizen has a fair chance to climb the ladder.

2. At the pragmatic **level**, meritocracy recognizes that to ensure quality decisions, competence and expertise are needed. Yet these are not equally distributed among citizens. Hence some 'merit-based' selection is pragmatically justified.

M promises here better-results-democracies, without violating the morally attractive egalitarian principle of ex ante equal chance of making it to the top. The social mobility narrative also has a pragmatic rationale, as the competition promises as a side effect to make everyone better off (trickledown effect).

Rule by individual merits, even when leading to power asymmetries, may ultimately work for all. One thus may argue that M is part of the social contract in contemporary liberal democracies, because

1. produces better-results-government, when meritocratic principle of elite recruitment is meticulously applied;
2. doors are kept open for all talents to compete on a level playing field;
3. equal access to quality education to develop one's talents is guaranteed to each, with special measures for children from disadvantaged families and backgrounds.

Fair equality of opportunity (FEoO) - the underlying principle of meritocracy - must be maintained across generations. Given the moral and pragmatic attractiveness of meritocracy, it surprises that increasing number of political philosophers and analysts find various faults not just with how it is practiced, turning M into myth (Hayes 2012; Littler 2017; Markovits 2019), but find it problematic as a morally attractive ideal (Sandel 2020). Some authors blame it for the current crisis of the liberal left (Fraser 2017), and for the crisis of democracy itself (Krastev 2017; Bovens and Wille 2017, Galston 2018, Sandel 2020, Goodhart 2020).

The tensions of Meritocracy With equal citizenship requirement

At the most fundamental level, the problem of M for democracy - and a factor for the erosion of the SC - is the tension between M and the democratic requirement for equal citizenship. This may be overlooked:

When FEoO is realized, citizens *ex ante* have a fair chance of success (ruling elite).

Yet even a “perfect’ M does not guarantee that all citizens unconditionally exercise their rights - by participating in the democratic process and by having influence on its outcomes

‘Merits’ are not equally distributed - conditioning on them the exercise of rights excludes the vast majority of citizens from participation in government. This is the case when decision-making is outsourced to experts. The vaster the areas of meritocratic, expert-based decision-making, the vaster the scope of *de facto* excluding citizens from democratic decision-making.

Yet this problem extends beyond technocratic decision-making by experts, and affects representative political institutions, too. The more elites - including politicians - are selected among the highly educated, the less people with lower levels of education *de facto* exercise their political rights. Participation rates among the less educated in most developed democracies is low and further declining - maybe because the less educated are discouraged by what they perceive to be their low political efficacy. This lends credence to claims that our democracies are turning into “Diploma democracy” (Hakhverdian et al. 2012, Bovens and Wille 2017) where ‘credentialed’ elites - and not all citizens equally - in fact rule.

Thus, even if FEO is guaranteed, M would not meet the strong democratic requirement of equal citizenship. Ultimately, only selecting representatives by lottery (Manin 1997, Van Reybrouck 2016) would guarantee the ‘results-equality’, required by a strong equal citizenship principle. This is a route few would risk taking. Representative democracy with some form of M elite recruitment is here to stay - it seems a reasonable compromise between the strong equal citizenship principle and better-quality government. It works, however, on the condition that FEO is guaranteed to all. Promising equal and fair *ex ante* chance of making it to the top, the M opens the door to each to compete on equal terms for a place among decision-making elites. Yet, at the end of the day, elites rather than all citizens equally decide.

With equal status requirement

M elites not only get the right to decide but are also ***granted higher value and prestige***. Yet part of the SC in democracy is the egalitarian ideal of equal value and respect for each citizen (Dworkin 2002, Christiano 2008). Egalitarianism is plainly incompatible with granting higher moral prestige and attaching greater value to members of M elites. The tension is not resolved by opening the prospect of making it to the top to everyone—by ‘leveling the playing field’ (realizing FEO), ***unless equality of status is maintained***. The democratic requirement of equal status is met only if belonging to the M ruling class *does not* bestow higher moral value and esteem and does not offend the equal concern and respect each member is owed in virtue of simply being a member of the democratic community—irrespective of personal achievements. Trying to factor in individual merits without threatening equality of status is worth exploring if M is to be part of the SC in LD. This is a task I have undertaken in another paper.

The conclusion at this point is that the tension of M with the *equal status requirement* may be the root cause of its potential to erode SC in contemporary democratic societies. SC assumes of equal status of all citizens, who are due equal concern and respect, irrespective of their individual merits.

Meritocracy and the crisis of representation

When ruling elites in a democracy are meritocratically selected—with the promise of improved government performance—a crisis of representation may instead ensue.

It starts with the wedge between “credentialed” elites and some sections of the public, who may feel they have been “treated unjustly, unfairly, or disrespectfully” (Galston 2021). The growth of this wedge is difficult, if not impossible to stop. The ideological triumph of liberalism at the turn of the century made M elites too complacent (Galston 2018, 17), unable or unwilling to address some of the pressing problems of their societies. This drove elites and ordinary citizens further apart. The failures of the elite to address those pressing grievances left many—in the ‘bitter heart-land’ but not only—dissatisfied with liberalism’s performance and resentful towards meritocratic, “no loyalty elites” (Krastev 2017, 90).

Takis Pappas has argued (Pappas 2019) that the best predictor for the rise of populist, illiberal-democratic parties, which deepen democratic erosion when in power, is precisely a crisis of representation. The crucial part of the explanation is the type of ruling elites in M: they tend to be unrepresentative—descriptively but also substantively—of the general population, as their paths rarely cross. Elites become detached from those educationally, geographically, occupationally distant from them. The perceived cultural distance leads to growing discontent with politicians among the less educated (Noordzij et al., 2021). Culturally and geographically distant from those at the bottom, ‘credentialed’ elites are rarely responsive to their grievances and fail to offer solutions to the problems ordinary people face. Substantive representation of underprivileged marginalized groups is negatively affected when these groups are not descriptively represented.

Political theorists and political scientists argue for “politics of presence” (Philips 1995, Williams 1998, Elsässer and Schäfer 2022), yet what people receive instead is “democracy without choices” (Krastev 2002). This adds unaccountability to the other failings of M elites. The solutions they offered have negative repercussions on sectors of the public that are among the most (and multiply) disadvantaged. Worse affected are those with low capacity to exercise political influence—because of low level of education, connectedness and access to resources and greater difficulties in organizing collective action.

Furthermore, meritocratic elites often present painful solutions as inescapable forces of nature—in the form of TINA (‘there is no alternative’) politics (Schmidt-Gleim and Wiesner 2021). The aim is to absolve elites of responsibility, yet the result is eroding trust. Having lost trust in elites, many ‘left behinds’ develop resentment. Coupled with growing feelings of loss of control their resentment grows into anger. Turning resentment into anger is often promoted by ‘political entrepreneurs’: they ‘perform crises’ (Moffitt 2015) and turn the accumulated grievances into anger. The ‘angry politics’ solutions often are worse than the problems that triggered them. They pit parts of society against each other, driving up polarization to a point where the social contract breaks, challenging the survival of the political community.

Let me summarize the factors behind the breakdown of the SC:

- Growing (cultural and other) distance between meritocratic elites and ordinary citizens;
- Accelerated technological development and globalization leave many behind, yet increasingly distant elites fail to notice and address their problems.

- Growing depoliticization and spread of TINA politics further contribute to a sense of frustration and political inefficacy.
- Accelerating consecutive crises (financial, climate, COVID, energy, economic...) pile on each other, producing multiple grievances that demand often mutually incompatible, and hugely unpopular, solutions.
- Political entrepreneurs 'perform crises' (or blow existent crises out of proportion) and promise 'easy' solutions, which deepen polarization.

Meritocracy - a pernicious myth?

Meritocracy contributes to the erosion of SC by often failing to deliver on its attractive promises. It might be a noble, inspiring ideal yet it breeds discontent as it inevitably fails to live up to its exacting demands. M is a myth, which many people believe. Yet, its critics maintain, this myth is pernicious.

The fear that M is just a myth was expressed early-on, maybe as early as the mid-19th century, when meritocracy-based civil service reform was discussed in England. Drawing on qualitative and quantitative data, some authors more recently argued not only that M is a myth (McNamee and Miller 2009; Bloodworth 2016, Littler 2017, Friedman and Laurison 2017) but that it is a pernicious myth. It destroys democracy (Lasch 1994) or at least undermines it (Bowens and Wille 2017).

Among the many shortcomings of M is that it justifies and promotes inequality (Mijs 2016, 2021, Littler 2017, Markovits 2019), destabilizes and ultimately threatens to destroy political communities (Sandel 2020).

It is not always clear where these critics find the main fault to lie - with the normative belief ('it is just to get ahead solely on one's merits'), with perception ('in our society people get ahead solely on their merits'), or with both. The important distinction 'normative belief in M - perception of M' is not made explicit either by Jo Littler (2017) or Daniel Markovits (2019). The simple argument is that belief in M - or 'meritocracy myth' - perpetuates and deepens inequalities, by face lifting existing privilege with the benign-sounding justification that it is M produced (people tolerate larger inequalities when they believe they are M produced). Larger inequalities themselves seem to reinforce M beliefs (Mijs 2021)

What is worse, M creates its own "aristocracy of talent": M elites entrench themselves by blocking access of outsiders to their newly acquired privileges (Markovits 2019). This accounts for slowing down, even reversing the trend of upward social mobility in countries with highest levels of M beliefs (as US).¹ A way to establish whether M is a pernicious-for-democracy myth is to look at social mobility levels. Educational equalization during the 20th century had a positive influence on social mobility (Breen 2010). Regarding the US, social mobility is declining at the national level (Connor and Storper 2020). Indeed, compared to many European countries, the US in 2020 is lagging behind most EU states in social mobility (27th place in the Global Social Mobility Index 2020, developed by the World Economic Forum).

Some countries with high belief (perception) in M indeed score relatively low on social mobility. US citizens have the highest and further growing belief in M (95% believe that "hard work makes

you rich”) and they score relatively low on social mobility (2020 index). Austrians, at the other extreme, have low perceptions of M (below 60%), yet they are in the top 10 of the most socially mobile countries in the world. This suggests that perceptions of M and social mobility are inversely related, which would support the claim that M myth is (at present) counterproductive, maybe even pernicious.

Yet contrary to the observed trend, there are cases where high beliefs in M go together with high upward social mobility - as in Sweden and Norway, which score high both on M beliefs and upward social mobility. The observed discrepancy between M beliefs and social mobility in some countries has puzzled scholars.¹ Perceptions of social mobility, furthermore, influence citizens’ view on redistributive policies: optimists object more strongly to redistribution, while pessimists are positively inclined. Thus, countries with lower perceptions of M and lower perceived social mobility tend to support more redistributive policies - including heavy investment in quality education and accessible healthcare, which in turn contribute to high levels of social mobility.

These observations may justify criticisms of the ‘meritocracy myth’. Perceptions of M seem counter-productive in fostering upward social mobility, which may in fact be better promoted by redistributive policies such as heavy investment in accessible quality education (and redistributive policies are not generally favored by believers in M). Yet because there are cases where the reverse trend is observed, this conclusion has limited scope.

Belief in M is the explanation Jonathan Mijs (2019) gave to the oft noted fact that in countries with high and further growing inequality, people tend to be OK with it, while in much more equal societies, people are more sensitive and protest any increase in inequality.² Newer results (Bartram 2023) demonstrate, however, that there is no correlation between perceptions of M and growth of inequality-at least not in European democracies, which are of interest for us in this report.

Another intriguing observation is that people believing in M often fail to see that inequality is growing.³ High perceptions of M may contribute to SC erosion through citizens seeing in populist

¹ Alesina, Stantcheva and Teso (2018) have shown, for example, that Americans overestimate upward social mobility, while Europeans tend to underestimate it.

² In the “The paradox of inequality” Mijs (2019) he argued that “income inequality and belief in meritocracy go hand in hand”, which explains why people in high inequality societies may be willing to tolerate it.

³ The more distant from each other the rich and the poor become, the more they fail to perceive their inequality (Trump 2017). Providing info about growing inequality is not sufficient to shake their belief in M, which is equally spread among both groups in the US. Perceptions, especially when ideologically buttressed, are resistant to more info (Alesina et al. 2018). Without lived experience with the opposite groups, people just fail to see the growing gap. If they come in contact, both groups are likely to realize the magnitude of the divide, and the poor are more likely to weaken their belief in meritocracy. The growing segregation between rich and poor (most pronounced in the US but also observed elsewhere), even when leading to polarization, may thus

leaders and their “victim rhetoric” a way of “absolving themselves of the burden of responsibility” for failing to make it to the top (Neerdaels 2023).

To conclude. M is an attractive yet demanding ideal. If everyone’s place in society is to be determined solely by her own personal merits, this requires perfect FEO, impossible to fully realize. Does it mean societies should not even strive to approximate the ideal? Anything short of full M is worse than no meritocracy at all, its critics conclude (Mijs 2016). To be tenable, this all-or-nothing position should demonstrate that unless M ideal is fully realized, its application is bringing more harm than benefits. Some have advanced such arguments: M justifies inequality, as demonstrated by societies where people believing in M tolerate much higher levels of inequality (Mijs 2019). However, there are examples of societies (most of them - in Europe), where high belief in M goes hand in hand with increased social mobility, lower levels of inequality and vast support for redistributive policies.

Such cases indicate the limit of the general thesis of M as a ‘pernicious myth’. We should thus be careful not to overstate the dangers of M. The ‘all or nothing’ position often advocated may seem principled yet is hardly tenable. As perfect FEO is unachievable, it denies trying to provide opportunity to the disadvantaged to develop their talents. This is damaging both to individual prospects and is socially wasteful as it blocks Pareto improvements and thereby hinders social development.

Targeting the moral core of meritocracy

The more consequential objections against M target the ideal itself rather than its various applications.

Sandel unfavorably compares inequality in modern meritocratic and in traditional aristocratic regimes and argues that even when inequality in the latter is greater, it is less offensive to those at the bottom (Sandel 2020). The ‘losers’ there may have viewed their place at the bottom as ‘natural’ rather than ‘deserved’. The extra offense of inequality in M comes from the self-celebratory sense of entitlement—from the ‘meritocratic hubris’, as Sandel calls it, of the winners, who believe to be fully deserving of their success. Convinced of their entitlement, they believe they do not owe anything to anyone else and show neither solidarity, nor responsibility towards the ‘losers’. The hubris of the winners goes further, as they put all the blame for their loss on the ‘losers’ themselves: if the losers lost in a fair competition, then their loss must be entirely their own. Both the win and the loss are fully deserved in the ‘meritocratic’ picture. The comparative ‘defense’ of inequality in aristocratic regimes may sound puzzling yet is part of the rhetorical strategy Sandel uses to discredit M not just as a practice, but as an ideal with a flawed moral core.

paradoxically prove to be conducive to preserving the status quo rather than shake it - particularly regarding socio-economic issues and redistribution. Those at the bottom simply do not lose their belief in M. Instead, they become resentful of the smug elites. The resentment by the ‘losers’ is unlikely to fundamentally shake the system, however, unless they drop their belief in M. This stalemate situation can rapidly change, and tensions accelerate with political entrepreneurs seizing the opportunity to politicize the resentment many feel. Populist leaders may start to ‘perform a crisis’ (Moffit 2015), swiftly turning resentments into anger.

Being the dominant ideology of social order, belief in M is widespread among both the winners and the 'losers'. The effects on the latter are devastating: believing they deserve their plight, they lose self-esteem and develop depression - a mechanism, which for Sandel explains the opioid crisis and the growing rate of 'deaths of despair' among uneducated whites (predominantly male) in the US (Case and Deaton 2020), who view themselves as 'status' losers with no one else to blame. The populist backlash is another response: instead of falling into depression, the humiliated 'losers' revolt against the resented M elites.

Objections to the M ideal dig deeper, aiming at its moral core. Few but the most radical critics of M object to one's career prospects being determined by personal merits, rather than by 'blood-line', family connections, money and bribes, etc. This shows that few are ready to fight head-on the 'tyranny of merit'. Michael Sandel takes up precisely this task.

Luck and the impossibility of moral desert. Luck egalitarian presuppositions of Sandel's critique

Michael Sandel identifies as the core of M ideal the moral claim to desert and strikes there. He does not just contest that the place of meritocratic winners is determined by their merits. He targets the further claim that winners are also morally anointed - fully deserving of their success. Meritocracy is a morally flawed ideal, he argues, as it unjustifiably grounds moral desert on personal 'merits'. Repeating Rawls' critique, talents - the genetic lottery - are fully a matter of luck, and no one can take any credit for them. Nor does one deserve the success and the rewards these talents (even if somehow deserved) would earn. Whether they command high market value is also a matter of luck. Personal merit-based success is no less morally arbitrary than any other form of brute luck - being born wealthy, with aristocratic title, etc. The successful **do not deserve** their place even in fully fair meritocracies. Adding insult to injury, the lucky winners believe they deserve their success and develop 'meritocratic hubris'.

Sandel's conclusion for the impossibility of meritocratic moral desert is too quick. It fails to establish there cannot in principle be 'moral desert' for any personal achievement, as it neglects the role personal choice and effort play there.

Aware of this possible line of defense, Sandel tries to deflect it by quoting Rawls on desert: "The assertion that a man deserves the superior character that enables him to make the effort to cultivate his abilities is equally problematic; for his character depends in large part upon fortunate family and social circumstances for which he can claim no credit. The notion of desert seems not to apply to these cases." (Rawls 1971, 104). Thus, concludes Sandel. "even effort cannot save the idea that market rewards should reflect moral desert" (Sandel 2020, chapter 5 "Success Ethics").

Yet, contrary to what both Rawls and Sandel argue, deciding to exert effort is at least partly a matter of personal choice rather than luck. To see why, consider Ronald Dworkin's distinction between brute and option luck (Dworkin 1981/2000). If I choose to exert an effort to develop my innate talents and because of this choice I succeed, my success would be a case of good option luck, for which I am at least partly responsible and can be credited with. Thus, personal success may at least partly be determined by personal effort for which one can be credited. This I take to be the core moral intuition, which drives many (95% of Americans, according to Mijs 2018) to embrace the meritocratic ideal, which promises rewards not just to the talented but to the hard-working. Irrespective of whether one deserves or one's talents, one may deserve to be praised if

one decides to develop - often through hard work - the talents one happens to have. One deserves to be praised even more for putting one's talents in the service of others.

Sandel also does not notice that it cannot be a duty of the talented to develop and use their talents just because they happen to have them. This would amount to the 'slavery of the talented' rightly pointed out by Dworkin (1981/2000) as a serious challenge to the account of egalitarianism that came to be known as luck egalitarianism. On some versions of luck-egalitarianism (GA Cohen's), the slavery of the talented objection is difficult to deflect. As on such accounts society is under an obligation to neutralize the effects of bad brute luck on people's fortunes, this implies that the beneficiaries of good brute luck have an obligation to compensate - by working hard, developing their talents and being productive - the less fortunate. This disregards the separateness of persons and would permit *de facto* enslavement of the talented. It also leads to a paradox. Those who have had (what turned out to be) bad luck of being born with talents, now have an obligation to develop them (even if they do not want to), because society thinks that they have benefitted from good luck for which they should repay the less fortunate. Ultimately, people stop being owners of their talents, stop being self-owning people. They, rather, are treated as repositories and trustees of a communal asset—the talents they happen to have, without those assets truly belonging to them. The only thing that truly belongs to them is the duty to develop whatever assets they happen to be entrusted with by Fortuna.

This view of persons denigrates the talented as mere repositories of socially owned talents which they have a duty to develop and use for the benefit of society. As stressed by Elizabeth Anderson (1999) the luck-egalitarian account of justice denigrates not just the talented. Extending social benefits to the disadvantaged by quoting their lack of talents and their bad brute luck as grounds, is also deeply offensive and disrespectful. It is disrespectful to show how little value society sees in them and their contributions but is also offensive in assuming the disadvantaged envy the more talented—and hence they need to be compensated.

It is a strange choice for Sandel to build his central argument against the moral core of the meritocratic ideal on the luck-egalitarian intuition that the effect of luck on one's chances should be neutralized rather than rewarded. I conclude here that we should resist the luck-egalitarian line Michael Sandel adopts because of its deeply troubling implications, denying the separateness of persons, and denying the talented the right to choose whether to work hard and develop their talents.

In a fair meritocracy one may at least partly deserve one's place in society—if she had worked hard for it. It is true that brute luck will play a role here. One may—because one's bad brute luck, not succeed after all, even after putting in a lot of hard work. Yet, when one's efforts bear fruit, and perhaps contribute to achieving socially valuable goals, it is unfair to deny them reward. This is the simple intuition behind the wide support the Equity principle ('A society is fair when hard-working people earn more than others') enjoys among Europeans (ESS 2018, Social Justice Panel).

Belief in Meritocracy and erosion of social contract in post-communist countries compared to other European countries

'Belief in meritocracy' - normative or descriptive, preference or perception?

A note of caution is due when analyzing 'belief in meritocracy'. Some authors discuss 'belief in meritocracy' without carefully distinguishing the normative understanding of 'belief in M' (normative belief in, or preference for) and the descriptive understanding of 'believe that one lives in M' (perception). In the first, normative belief (preference), people believe that meritocratically produced inequalities are just and would be OK with inequalities to the extent they are meritocratically produced. In the second, descriptive sense of belief (or 'perception') what is evaluated is the extent to which people believe that their society is just in this meritocratic sense.

The two beliefs - preferences and perceptions - can go together, yet by no means always do so. When they are combined - i.e. majorities with strong normative beliefs in M perceive their society as meritocratic, - people are ready to accept the existing inequalities as justified. Conversely, when people hold strong normative M beliefs yet believe that inequalities in their society are not meritocratically produced, they may angrily refuse to accept them. This is what is observed in societies with a widespread strong sense of social injustice. This is the case in some CEE countries in particular. Some authors have not paid attention to the double meaning of 'belief in meritocracy', hence it is sometimes difficult to comparatively interpret their findings.⁴

Hard work (effort and ambition), or talent (ability) as well?

There are also divergent views regarding what is included in merit when beliefs in M are evaluated: only hard work, effort and ambition, or talent and ability as well. The classic definition of Michael Young (1958) included both effort and talent in the formula of merit, yet a more careful analysis of the moral intuitions behind the appeal of the M ideal - that one's success should depend only on factors in one's control rather than circumstances beyond one's control (brute luck) - may yield a different definition. As effort but not talent is within one's control, it seems better to

⁴ For example, Jonathan Mijs (2018) provides an impressive longitudinal measurement of 'belief in meritocracy' in 23 democracies, using data from several rounds of the International Social Survey Program (1980 - 2010). The question in ISSP measures *perceptions* of meritocracy ['who gets ahead in society is decided by hard work'] rather than *normative beliefs (preferences)*. The data set Mijs compiled demonstrates high and growing descriptive belief (perceptions) in M in almost all the countries covered. Using a different set of data - from the European Social Survey (rounds 2008 and 2016, covering 17 countries from Europe), David Bartram (2023) finds that belief in meritocracy is much less prevalent (Figures 4 and 5 in Appendix). Yet the question in ESS measures *normative beliefs* in meritocracy (preferences) rather than *perceptions*. The question respondents answered in these rounds of ESS is: 'large differences in people's incomes are acceptable to properly reward differences in talents and efforts'. Bartram postulates a positive correlation between the answers to two questions - on normative beliefs and perceptions and based on this assumption he criticizes Jonathan Mijs' results, as Mijs finds widespread strong beliefs in meritocracy while Bartram finds 'middling' beliefs among Europeans.

limit merit to the former. There is rather limited research on what people include as merits when they hold beliefs in meritocracy.⁵

To better account for the intuition behind M, with its stress on the moral relevance of desert, and personal responsibility more generally - which itself relies on the crucial distinction between personal choice and luck, some authors recently distinguish between three different widespread conceptions on justice in distribution: *strict egalitarian*, *meritocratic* and *libertarian* (Almas et al. 2022). According to the first no inequality in distribution is ever justified, for the second only inequality stemming from differential effort is justified, and for the third - any inequality, whether due to effort or luck, may be justified, provided the state guarantees basic procedural fairness (i.e. fraud and extortion excluded).

According to the research of Almas et al. (2021) there are widely divergent views on justice in distribution across nations globally, with meritocratic beliefs dominating in some countries (Canada, Australia, Norway, Italy), wide-spread 'libertarian' views in others (vast majorities in India, China, Vietnam...), but also egalitarian ones (in Bangladesh, Tanzania, Philippines, Malawi, and Israel this seems to be the predominant view). Data for countries worldwide demonstrate that in inequality acceptance Merit features high (at 0.7 average) for both OECD and non-OECD countries, while acceptance of inequality due to luck significantly lags behind - in non-OECD countries half of respondents on average would accept inequality with such source, while for OECD the average stands at the much lower 0.35 (ibid.).

Note, however, that in the literature there is no uniform way of operationalizing. Some authors still use the effort+talent formula, while more recently more often the questions on hard work (effort) as determining one's success in life are used.

Belief in meritocracy in CEE: a gap between normative preferences and perceptions?

Normative beliefs in (preferences for) M are strong in Central and Eastern Europe (Han et al. 2012) - even stronger compared to Western Europe. However, a growing gap between normative beliefs and perceptions of M was also noted:

Since people in Eastern European countries do believe that M principles should determine income, it can be concluded that there is a significant (and growing) gap in these countries between what people perceive to be the case and what they hold to be ideal. The decline in the perception in these countries that merit determines income is difficult to reconcile with the increase in the degree of inequality held to be legitimate, as one would not expect people to accept ever greater differences of income if they at the same time become more skeptical about the way these incomes are earned." (ibid., 42).

⁵ Data from Chile (Atria et al, 2021) demonstrate the discrepancy in the views on the matter of members of the middle and lower classes and those of members of the economic elite in that country: while the former include only effort, the latter stress the importance of talent and ability.

The same observation can be replicated with data more than a decade later (the above study covered the 90s and first decade of 2000s). The strong preference for equality among nations in the region is well documented: the state is believed responsible for equalizing incomes through redistribution (for details and discussion, see Eder 2017). Yet the meritocratic preferences are even stronger: data from the new panel of ESS Round 8 2018 on social justice show that 80% of Bulgarians, Croats and Poles, 87% of Slovenes, and 88% of Estonians declare that they find inequalities resulting from hard work justified (data from Adriaans et al 2020). In 2018 large majorities in 5 West Balkan countries (in addition to the EU members Bulgaria, Slovenia and Croatia, Serbs and Montenegrins) hold normative beliefs in meritocracy (2018 ESS data, reported in Stoilova and Haralampiev 2022).

The M ideal has been embraced by most citizens of most European democracies, surveyed by ESS already in 2008 and 2016 (data in Bartram 2023), though support has dropped. The nations with the strongest preference for M in the beginning of the century in Europe were the Belgians, the Germans, the Brits, the Swedes in Western and Northern Europe, and the Czechs, Estonians and Poles in the East. The Hungarians were the clear outlier in this regard, with the majority disapproving of M already in 2008 and further increasing their disapproval in 2016 (theirs is the lowest rate of approval among all Europeans). Slovaks and Hungarians are among the least enthusiastic supporters of the 'equity principle' in the next round of ESS in 2019, when a new module on social justice was introduced, asking respondents about their support for four alternative distributive justice principles - equality, equity, need and privilege. Somewhat surprisingly, the Czechs and the Lithuanians also show less enthusiasm for the equity principle - which legitimizes inequality based on merit - though the rates are still very high: 70% of all Eastern Europeans express support for it. Despite the decline, majorities in most of the countries surveyed still have strong normative beliefs in (preferences for) M.

There are considerable differences among the countries with regard to perceptions of M, however. Jonathan Mijs shows that 95% of Americans believe they live in M, and this high level of descriptive belief is not matched by any other nation studied. Among citizens of other developed democracies, just over 50% of the Dutch and of the French share such perceptions. CEE countries also diverge widely. Though in the case of Poland there is a remarkable upward shift in perceptions of M (according to the ISSP data, compiled by Mijs 2018), with over 85% of Poles in 2010 believing they live in M (starting with very low levels in mid-80ies early 90ies), this is not so for the Hungarians and the Latvians, and also for the Czechs and the Slovaks. Unfortunately, ISSP data are not available for all CEE.

A nationally representative survey for Bulgaria, conducted in 2017 (Trend 2017) helps to fill this gap at least in this case. It demonstrates that just 24% of Bulgarians believe that in their country success is determined by hard work (and 69% believe success depends on 'connections', and 66% do not agree that one becomes rich in a fair way). Compare this to the data from ESS for Bulgaria (quoted in Stoilova and Haralampiev 2022), where over 80% declare to hold normative beliefs (preference) for M. The mismatch is considerable - and goes strongly against the assumption made by Bartram about expected correlation in the answers to the normative and the descriptive question.

This mismatch between normative beliefs in and perceptions of M - where the high normative beliefs are frustrated by the harsh reality of post-communist societies with high levels of corruption and nepotism - is worth exploring further. It goes against the expected positive correlation, which allowed Bartram (2023) to compare the results from ESS (measuring normative beliefs) with

those of ISSP (measuring perceptions). If the same mis-match is confirmed in other cases of CEE democracies which underwent rapid democratic erosion as a result of populist mobilizations, it may be (part of) an explanation for the sources of popular discontent with the system and the high propensity of voters to support newcomers, promising to shake the system.

For Bulgaria this explanation is corroborated by the well-documented high electoral volatility and political instability. Other interesting cases are Hungary and Poland, where the greatest democratic erosion has been documented as a result of Viktor Orbán's and PiS rule, respectively. What strikes in these two cases is how different are the attitudes of Hungarians and Poles towards M. While Poles have the steepest increase in perceptions of M (Mijs 2018) with 85% in 2010 believing they live in meritocracy, Hungarians have shown more ambiguous attitudes, with a dip in the early 90ies (after relatively high levels in mid-80-ies) and reaching in 2010 (the year Viktor Orbán came to power) 70%. Even more striking is the difference in the normative beliefs in M of the Hungarians and the Poles. While Hungarians are the champions of Europe in low and further declining normative beliefs in M (preferring egalitarian to merit-based income distributions) with scores of 1.59 (2008) and 1.42 (2016) on a scale of 1 to 4 (ESS data, Bartram 2023), Poles report above the average for Europeans (2.53 and 2.55 for 2008 and 2016) normative beliefs in meritocracy.

The mismatch between normative belief and perception observed among Bulgarians is not confirmed here - and if there is a mismatch, it goes in the opposite direction: Poles have higher perceptions than normative beliefs, and this is even more pronounced for Hungarians - with majority (70%) in 2010 believing they live in M (society where hard work earns one success), yet much weaker normative preferences for M. The starkly different results for Hungary and Poland regarding belief in M and the similarity of the path towards democratic erosion is an indication of the limits of the explanation explored in this contribution.

Let me finally conclude the discussion in this long section. The moral alarm, that the American dream - the belief in M - not only has been betrayed by self-serving meritocratic elites (Lasch 1994) but has also proven counter-productive as it drives up inequality without also promoting upward social mobility, may be warranted, but only to an extent. It may hold for some societies but is by no means universally valid.

Belief in M also cannot - by itself - explain why some countries go down the road of SC erosion and democratic decline. For some cases - like the US, where overwhelming majorities believe (both normatively and descriptively) in M, this belief may feature as a component of an explanation for democratic erosion (via strong popular support for populist projects). Yet the explanation does not travel well to other cases - most notably Hungary, but also Poland and Bulgaria.

European democracies in general seem to be much less affected by the assumed 'democracy-eroding' and SC undermining effects of 'belief in meritocracy': the latter is weaker in some European societies and does not seem to be correlated with democratic decline there.

Conclusions

In this contribution, I undertook several tasks. After briefly discussing the central role principles of justice play in contemporary social contract theory, I noted a striking insensitivity within this approach to desert-based accounts of justice, which enjoy ubiquitous popularity even today. Looking

at recent data on normative beliefs regarding justice among Europeans (ESS Round 9, 2018, Social Justice panel), we noted that the Equity principle ('A society is fair when hard-working people earn more than others') enjoys overwhelming support among all Europeans - in some European societies enjoying the support of 90% of the citizens and in no European society it is supported by less than $\frac{2}{3}$).

I have interpreted these results in light of recent debates around meritocracy, as the meritocratic ideal for ordering society as inextricably linked with the Equity principle. I have argued that meritocracy as a purported ideal of justice should be taken seriously despite the mounting - both philosophical and social-psychological - criticisms against it. My contribution critically engaged with the most influential recent philosophical critique of meritocracy, advanced by Michael Sandel (2020), demonstrating flaws in his criticism of meritocracy. I also pointed out the shortfalls of his proposed solution to the meritocracy problem. I further argued that people's beliefs about justice - and their overwhelming normative preference for the Equity principle - should be taken seriously rather than easily dismissed as just an 'ideological trap' set by neoliberal elites conspiring against the people.

In the final sections, I have advanced and tried to substantiate the hypothesis that the observed weakness of the social contract in many countries in Europe is due to a mis-match between the normative belief (or preference) for meritocratic society (where the Equity principle is observed to a high degree) and the descriptive perceptions of majorities, who do not seem to believe they actually live in meritocracy. Lastly, I explored the hypothesis that the mismatch between normative preferences and perceptions is particularly pronounced in some CEE countries with low and further declining 'state of democracy' scores. I thus explained the weakness of the social contract in some European societies - with high levels of distrust in political elites, low electoral turnout, low levels of democratic engagement and overall high degree of political instability - with this observed mismatch between normative beliefs and perceptions of social justice.

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Contribution 6: Polarization, Hegemony and the Social Contract

Emilia Palonen (University of Helsinki, emilia.palonen@helsinki.fi) and Szilvia Horváth (University of Helsinki, szilvia.horvath@helsinki.fi).

Introduction

In the subchapters on hegemony theory and polarization, we explore how Ernesto Laclau and Chantal Mouffe's theory of hegemony can serve as a heuristic for understanding social contracts, in complement with the other works presented in this deliverable. Through this lens, we can analyze how social contracts are established, maintained, and contested as hegemonic formations. In contrast to Rawls, hegemony theory posits that a social contract is not a one-time decision. Instead, it emphasizes the active maintenance of and potential to contest such a relationship. It envisions a resilient social contract not as a merely given state but as a continuous process of renegotiation. Through the lens of hegemony and radical democracy, the social contract serves as a metaphor or a heuristic for better understanding prevailing logics in societies and politics.

In the subchapter on Chantal Mouffe, we summarize the key elements of her theory of democratic agonism, focusing on how it can contribute to the interpretation of polarization; how it shapes the understanding of the democratic social contract; and how it can help in explaining non-democratic social contracts. By doing so, we can gain conceptual tools to assess the frontier(s) of democracy, examine challenges to both democracy and the tacit agreement on which societies are grounded, conceptualize how to address illiberal social contracts, and evaluate which conflicts jeopardise or strengthen both the democratic order and the social contract.

Both cases address the challenge of continuous construction of the social contract and the role of adversary disagreement in the polity. The ideas of consensus or one-time agreement would be seen as non-democratic from this perspective that highlights how the social is marked by antagonism that democratic processes turn into agonism. These approaches also question what is the body politic that emerges, and would align with Wendy Brown's (2019; 2005) criticism that in the prevailing neoliberal logic in politics, maximising rationally conceptualised economic gain override the Rousseauian idea of a democracy premised on making citizens more equal. Here the public is reduced to individuals who are controlled rather than holding power. The Laclau-Mouffean collective subject, emerges as premised on antagonism when the polarised logic's negative identification a mutual opposition impedes the sovereignty of the subject. Questions emerge about the relationship between consensus and the social contract.

Hegemony theory and the social contract

Emilia Palonen

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Many contemporary struggles can be conceptualized through the category of the social contract – and in this role hegemony theory will be important. We explore how social contract can be thought of through the lens of the theory of hegemony of Ernesto Laclau and Chantal Mouffe (1985): social contracts are established, retained, and contested as hegemonic formations. It would enable a perspective of a social contract as a heuristic for assessing the processes of imagining collectives as it seemingly provides a glue to society. Regularly it would be civic and ethnic forms of nationalism that would take this role. In this way, it does not assume a foundational basis or an imagined cultural tie, but it envisions a contract that would assume a crafted but consenting relationship between the powerholders and the citizens. In contrast to the Rawlsian decision behind a veil of ignorance, theory of hegemony challenges the idea that this would be a one-off decision but affords attention to the active maintenance and the possibilities of contesting such a relationship. Moreover, the ideas on which the contracts are based are not something to be taken for granted but building a basis of our society in a particular way. A resilient social contract is not merely a given state but is a continuous process of re-negotiation, is incomplete and requires constant evaluation of whether everyone is indeed included and equally so. Alternatively, social contract offers a perspective to see contestation and exclusion or inclusion (see Pateman and Mills, in the first contribution to this deliverable). Through the lens of hegemony and radical democracy, social contract offers a metaphor or a heuristic for better understanding prevailing logics in societies and politics.

Ernesto Laclau and Chantal Mouffe (1985) drew on Gramscian-Althusserian tradition when building a strategy for the new social movements in the *Hegemony and Socialist Strategy: Towards A Radical Democratic Politics*. The concept of hegemony has long roots from the Greek political philosophy to left-wing political thought, where it was importantly theorized by the Italian Marxist Antonio Gramsci (Cospito, 2024). It has been associated with leadership in a wide sense that includes the mechanisms of epistemic production, media, and education institutions. The attention is moved from the focus on who is in power to who controls instruments of power, which Louis Althusser called state apparatuses. In the hands of Laclau and Mouffe, these got even more discursive flair. They observed how certain ideas were dominant and contested in what they called the discursive field where political meanings originate.

Gramsci's thinking has been interpreted as the mere contestation of an existing order to be filled with another type of order. These can take place through the party but also the media or other institutions. Althusser (2008: 39) argued that "ideology has a material existence" and theorized how it exists in practices and apparatuses. These generate consciousness, a subject. Therefore, controlling such apparatuses is of utmost importance. This enables us to see what hegemonic battles take place in politics and societies, where social imaginaries with their orders are tried out and substituted through articulatory practices. Instead of ideology Althusser stressed the ideological. Just as politics and the political (Mouffe 2005), these are distinct concepts: it diverts our attention to the ideological character rather than ideology as some substantive thought system itself.

Gramsci thought of politics as a continuous cycle: there is always space for crisis; it is normal for political parties to dismantle or reproduce themselves and gain or lose members. Gramsci (1996: II, 241) highlights this cycle and the 'normal' process of changing representation with his term 'organic crisis'. As a post-Gramscian theorist, Ernesto Laclau (1990, 1996, 2005) discusses transformation in the discursive field in terms of unity and fragmentation. For him, the results of the process are by no means evident or mere moments in an already determined flow of events. Focusing on the creation and battle between political camps, it is important to conceptualize the emergence and articulation of unity and the fragmentation of it. In this, the notion of hegemony is extremely useful.

Due to the way in which articulation takes place, hegemony is not a static state of affairs but is always in flux with competing attempts to sediment and contest. Rather than one-off replacement of order with another, hegemony is a process: a constant movement through rearticulation, a process that takes place between the extremities of fragmentation and unity. Articulation is necessary because of the inherent distance between the represented and the representative: to make political claims and demands these must be articulated. They must be brought up, rather than merely emerging naturally, which means that things and their representation, the form they take, are distinctive. The process of articulation, therefore, implies changes. The changes are based on the relationality – the way in which diverse things are being related to others combined and distinguished. The articulating a temporal relational unity also implies the creation of a difference or distinction. On the one hand, the distinction between elements in the chain, and then the distinction between what is not articulated, what is the constitutive outside.

Attention to hegemony also enables us to understand that polarisation is not the product of a single political party, but a larger structure of political articulation and identification, which to succeed must be maintained by all the main political parties. It is maintained because political and social groups articulate their identifications through the situation of polarisation, rather than through radically different identifications and new frontiers. This theorising may sound complex, but it is relatively straight-forward. Gramscian thinking is useful to grasp how dynamics and logics could be conceptualised and operationalised in the understanding of this type of analytical heuristics and theorizing of the political.

Polarisation in the Laclaudian-Gramscian perspective

From the Laclaudian perspective which draws equally on Derrida, Lacan and le Bon, political identities in general are constructed through negativity and performed in a rhetorical process. Identity is conditioned by a constitutive lack, subject of lack in Lacan, and constitutive outside, what we are not. Lack drives us to seek to become something more than one is, “us”. The process relies on something is beyond the limit of “us”. Political leaders have a role in ratifying the identity of the self. This alterity in general or, more specifically a ratifying big Other, is part of our identity: our identities are marked by a negativity of what we are not and relationality that confirms our identity. Laclau and Mouffe (1985: 193) write: ‘A hegemonic formation also embraces what opposes it, insofar as the opposing force accepts the system of basic articulations of that formation as something it negates, but the place of negation is defined by the internal parameters of the formation itself.’ It is not yet another entity.

The terms imaginary and myth emerge in Laclau and Mouffe’s work as discursive reference points for several political actors, offering partial fixation and limit of discourses. Laclau (1990) theorized them in *New Reflections on the Revolutions of Our Time*. These not only transform over time and through social change, but they are volatile to political attempts to generate new meanings and contest the status quo – or simply other political beliefs and imaginings. This leads us to also consider polarisation.

Marking and emphasising a specific political frontier is the crux of polarisation. A critique of polarisation, however, does not go against political frontiers. On the contrary, conflict is a vital part of politics, and politics is a vital part of democratic life. As Laclau (1990: 160) has stressed, ‘there is only politics where there are frontiers’. But as Aletta Norval (1997) has also pointed out, there are also limits and not all that is political involves frontiers. Any system needs limits, and crucially political discourses and groups need something which is posited outside the system, not as a mere

limit but as something that is in an antagonistic relation, as an enemy or adversary. Politics is about the making visible the limits of the totality “us”, an imagined community, by turning the limits into frontiers.

Polarisation is a situation in which the signifying frontier is constantly articulated at the same location. The identities are constructed on each side against each other, and any incompatible differences are blocked out. The bipolar system sustains both communities, which articulate their identities through the same frontier. In the construction and maintenance of polarisation, negation is essential. Polarisation is a situation in which self contains and is maintained through a strong internalised otherness.

In my reading, plurality of frontiers is part and parcel of democracy, it enables the negotiations, conflicts of interest and debates that keep politics as an open process, which nevertheless tries to establish positions. The problem of polarisation is that it contains a dominant frontier, while others are being downplayed. This situation is not ideal, as it creates ‘consensual’ camps, a system through which political differences are being downplayed on both sides, and in which ‘politics’ as process of frontier-making is lacking. In short, for a functioning democracy, politics should occur over more than one frontier, and with changing coalitions.

This kind of polarisation is in fact close to affective polarisation (McCoy & Somer, 2019). Yet here we see polarisation as a strategy and hegemony, which goes against the larger framework of affective polarisation studies.

Polarisation solves the initial problem of fragmentation – a lack of unity –, by instituting a frontier which sustains two communities as a bipolar hegemony. Furthermore, polarisation requires constant rearticulation and therefore, constant antagonising around that frontier, since new cleavages or demands would otherwise emerge that would distort the situation of polarisation. Consequently, to maintain polarisation, any new cleavages or demands must be articulated into the existing system.

In this way, polarisation offers a chance for two camps to exist by making sure that the frontier between them establishes a strong imaginary – a system of differences in which all the demands that arise are articulated. This allows them to create their identities without paying too much attention to the contents of their discourses, beyond the emphasis on the frontiers.

As a form of politics, polarisation is similar to consensus in the way it is challenging to a adversarial understanding of democracy: polarisation as bi-polar hegemony triggers two consensuses divided by a frontier (Palonen 2009). Criticism is difficult to voice in each. While the problem of consensus is that political frontiers are being minimised, in polarisation, disagreements are minimised on each of the two sides, and political divisions are all projected onto the frontier of polarisation between the two camps. This is apart from the political frontier between the people who are able to participate in the polity and those who are not. The stress is on minimising since there will always be some confrontation within the consensual unit, but to maintain the situation, internal conflict is kept to a minimum and its role in the political process is downplayed.

Similarly, anything which is not easily accommodated into the system is ignored or its significance diminished. The emergence of new cleavages, which cannot be easily articulated into the existing system, threatens to distort polarisation. This would put in question the identities and logic of the

communities or political forces that are created through the situation of polarisation, since they are reliant on the imagined frontier, and on otherness. The other can rarely be seen except as an adversary – even if the two ‘enemies’ are each other’s perfect partners, in terms of maintaining the polarisation. Since polarisation exists through the rearticulation of any new cleavages or demands into the existing system, it will obviously block any ‘real’ political antagonisms and crucial demands.

The social contract from the hegemony perspective

It is important to consider the social contract through the lens of hegemony. First, we recognise the power relation behind the social contract as a hegemonic formation. This means that our critical observation can be expanded from those as such relevant questions of inclusion or exclusion to a more comprehensive questions related to which are the bases or ideals the social contract is built on. This includes the ideological dimensions of social contracts – meaning the sedimented and depoliticised ideals that once were options for the bases of the social contract.

As Giuseppe Cospito (2024) recently has laid out hegemony is a concept from Greek philosophy that disappeared from political theory for a long while before it was recovered and then rearticulated by Piemonte theorists, including, famously, Antonio Gramsci. Cospito reduces hegemony to a form of leadership, domination and consent. He argues that the social contract is implicitly present in the social contract theory developing into a sovereign two-sided power in a relationship that implies responsibilities from the two sides. Then Cospito discusses the re-emergence of hegemony.

In the neo-Gramscian way the emphasis is on the “leadership” – which is understood as quite a wide concept and refers to the ideological, cultural and identity – domination, and relations of power from the perspective of the proletariat. This emphasises the relationships of economy while at the same time recognising the role of instruments of power like the press and other cultural institutions that maintain or contest hegemony leadership of those in power and those outside of power.

Thinking the social contract from the perspective of hegemony, we can see how the connections between contracting groups are made and what are the injustices that may emerge in an assumed social contract. The basic idea of Laclau and Mouffe: of equivalence between the different groups with their diverse demands contesting the powerholding elites was radical. This temporary and contingent unity could then also emerge in a process of representation as one of the groups or demands would stand for the whole chain of equivalence, by losing its particular content be re-described into an “empty signifier”, unfortunately named as it was in fact overflowing, overburdened through the weight of the whole chain to be represented. This generation of a political subject based on a heterogeneity becomes a key concern for Ernesto Laclau, and this is encapsulated in his seminal work *On Populist Reason* (2005).

The study was also a response to the way in which traditional political science approaches took the social for granted. In the mainstream the social is conceptualised in terms of demography: socio-economic differences and economic interest. The contrast is that there is unevenness of the social. And political actors work on a undecidability. For a democratic understanding of politics there is always an assumption of a void: the perspective drawn from the French political theorist Claude Lefort stresses that the core of democracy an empty space which is always refilled but not with interest but by parties which are able to perform the collective subject (Palonen, 2021). So,

taking a hegemony theoretical perspective on the social contracts, this responds to the way in which the social – or the people or the *demos* are constructed.

Considering the binary of demography vs. democracy the foundational or the post-foundational approach on “the social” in the contract, we can both in the heuristic way contest the way in which the social is build or assumed. However, it also opens up potential for criticism: who or whose demands are part of the chain? What is the Name of the impossible, contingent unity? What is not part of the chain (limits) and what is opposed (frontiers)?

Chantal Mouffe’s theory of agonism in the context of polarization and the democratic social contract

Szilvia Horváth

The following summarizes the key elements of Chantal Mouffe’s theory of democratic agonism (based on these works: Mouffe, 2000; 2005 and summarized here: 2013; 2018), focusing on these questions: how it contributes to the interpretation of polarization; how it shapes the understanding of the democratic social contract; and how this theory may also contribute to the interpretation of non-democratic social contracts?

Mouffe’s starting point is that politics is inherently conflictual, and that conflict is a values-in-itself. She challenges Habermas and the idea that the goal of politics should be to eliminate conflicts and dissolve them in a consensus through negotiation. Her argument is based on two foundations. The first tacit one covers a realist perspective: even if we wish for conflicts to disappear from politics and for all divisive issues to be settled through consensus, in polarized societies (i.e., when conflicts are particularly sharp), what is exactly missing is the very capacity for and inclination toward consensus. More generally, Mouffe argues that conflicts cannot be eliminated from politics, and therefore, our task would be instead to understand politics politically.

However, her decisive argument in favour of conflicts is, ultimately, normative. If conflicts disappear from politics and the frontiers that shape identities become blurred, then for citizens the possibilities for identification vanish. Consequently, so does the capacity for emotional commitment—not only to specific parties but, through democratic parties, to democracy itself.

Mouffe’s normative argument in favour of conflict can be extended to pluralism as a fundamental value of democracy. She argues that the problem with Habermas’ discourse theory of consensus is that consensus—even if achievable—would ultimately eliminate the very foundation upon which it was built, and which also constitutes the core of the liberal politics: pluralism. In Mouffe’s political theory, pluralism plays a decisive role; this “deep pluralism” serves as a background for the theory of agonism (cf. Wenman, 2013).

Mouffe argues that conflicts are necessary not only because they express political identities but also because they constitute them. In her writings from the 2000s, she uses the third way as an example; that is, the dissolution of the traditional left somewhere between left and right, which, in her view, led to the disappearance of clear frontiers of identification for citizens. However, the

human need for such frontiers is constant, and in their absence, parties that could provide them—namely, the far-right—rose to prominence.

In other words, the demand for conflict, differentiation (the drawing of clear political frontiers), and the need to have identity on emotional grounds does not disappear from politics simply because political actors refuse or fail to engage with them; rather, the focus shifts to where the functioning of these political logics are still present. The real problem at the ontic level of politics, however, has been that the emerging frontiers were far more radically and exclusionary drawn than those whose disappearance had initially allowed them to come to the surface and thrive.

At this point, it is worth quoting Mouffe's self-definition: she wants "to think with Schmitt against Schmitt" (Mouffe, 2005: 14). She acknowledges that Schmitt correctly grasped the conflictual nature of modern politics, which made him a key thinker to the political understanding of politics. However, his conclusions oppose any democratic principle, including pluralism and the idea that conflicts should not lead to the establishment of an authoritarian regime. In this sense, Mouffe's self-positioning - thinking with Schmitt against Schmitt - introduces a clear democratic criterion into the theory.

My argument is that understanding politics in a conflictual way only becomes a theory of agonism through the introduction of this democratic criterion. Thus, conflicts that constitute politics are subjected to the democratic criterion, which then can be further specified by attaching various additional conditions.

From Schmitt, we can understand that a certain level of conflictual intensity is necessary for things to become political, while the democratic perspective introduces the idea that such intensities must have an upper limit. What is, then, agonism, the democratic type of conflictuality that is constitutive of politics and plays a key role in maintaining the condition of plurality? At this theoretical juncture, Mouffe seeks to distinguish between adversary and enemy. The answer to this question can function as a democratic criterion.

Mouffe, in an argument not entirely alien to the theory of militant democracy, asserts that the political sphere consists of rivals who regard one another as adversaries but who must also accept the rules of the democratic game. If one treats the Other as an enemy and wages a war against them, they can no longer be part of this democratic sphere and must be placed outside of it. She also notes that in such cases, the antagonistic frontier does not disappear (since it was already present in the hostile stance toward the Other) but is instead relocated - now marking those who themselves employed this hostility against the political Other.

What is the significance of all this for polarization, the democratic social contract, and authoritarian practices?

1. Mouffe actually excludes polarization from the political logic, or more precisely, from politics subjected to the democratic criterion. The distinction between enemy/adversary and her conceptualisation of agonism point to this. Treating the political Other as an enemy – this refers to antagonistic relations - not only marks the frontier of democracy, where it ceases to be democratic, but also signals the breakdown of the social contract on which the given democratic order was founded. The tacit agreements on social foundations are also consensuses about democratic functioning. Thus, when analysing actual social contracts (in

terms of content, fissures, challenges, and resilience), we should also consider whether these foundations are democratic - that is, whether we are dealing with democratic social contracts.

2. From this, it follows that the analysis should address which disagreements are acceptable within the framework of a given social contract. Based on Mouffe's theory, it seems reasonable to use the conceptual differences provided by the adversary/enemy distinction, which, as a schema, can also be applied to assessing antagonistic situations: Which conflicts within a community jeopardise both the democratic order and the social contract, and which ones may actually strengthen them?
3. Although Mouffe does not directly address the political logic characteristic of authoritarian transformations, it is possible to do so, provided that we understand agonism as democratic conflictuality. The question arises whether it is possible to distinguish between democratic and non-democratic solely within the logic of the political. This could highlight the importance of the democratic nature of our social contracts and potentially help formulate how to address conceptually the illiberal social contracts from a solely political angle with the focus on polarization.

Finally, we can be more conscious in analysis regarding when we attribute normative value to consensus. For example, should we do this for political conflicts in general, or should we reserve it for the actual social contract - which could potentially be defined precisely as the "actual consensus" regarding social and political foundations? Furthermore, what does it mean for the survival of a society, its well-integrated character, and society's general well-being if political confrontations, or even polarization, develop precisely over certain elements, or a sequence of elements, of the social contract?

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Contribution 7: Affective Polarization and the Erosion of the Democratic Social Contract

Pinar Uyan Semerci (Istanbul Bilgi Universitesi, pinar.uyan@bilgi.edu.tr).

Introduction

Democratic governance depends on more than formal institutions and procedures; it requires an underlying social contract that fosters mutual trust, solidarity, and respect for shared democratic norms. Classical social contract theorists—Thomas Hobbes, John Locke, and Jean-Jacques Rousseau—offered distinct but complementary visions of this contract. Hobbes emphasized the necessity of centralized authority to prevent societal collapse into a state of nature (Hobbes, 1651/1994). Locke envisioned governance as a cooperative endeavor grounded in mutual consent and aimed at securing natural rights (Locke, 1689/1980). Rousseau argued for the primacy of the general will, in which citizens transcend narrow self-interest to pursue the common good (Rousseau, 1762/2011). Contemporary democratic theory builds upon these foundations, emphasizing the role of trust, solidarity, and shared norms in sustaining legitimacy and cooperation.

The Social Contract and the Foundations of Democratic Legitimacy

The social contract, in its classical formulations, offers a normative basis for legitimate governance. Hobbes viewed the social contract as a mechanism for escaping the chaos of the state of nature by submitting to a sovereign authority capable of maintaining order (Hobbes, 1651/1994). Locke emphasized mutual consent and collective problem-solving as essential to legitimate governance, where individuals enter into political society to secure life, liberty, and property (Locke, 1689/1980). Rousseau advanced the idea of the general will as the basis for legitimate political authority, insisting that citizens must subordinate personal interests to the collective good (Rousseau, 1762/2011). Democratic legitimacy depends on an analogous form of social contract. It requires citizens to accept the legitimacy of political outcomes, even when they lose; to trust institutions that mediate conflict; and to regard political opponents as fellow members of a shared political community. Without this mutual regard and institutional trust, the foundations of democratic cooperation are weakened.

Affective Polarization and the Erosion of Mutual Regard

At the heart of the social contract lies mutual regard—a recognition that citizens, despite ideological differences, are bound by shared norms and values. Democratic stability depends on the ca-

capacity to perceive political rivals as legitimate adversaries rather than existential enemies. Chantal Mouffe describes this as agonistic pluralism: a form of political competition that accepts adversaries as legitimate and democratic conflict as bounded by shared rules (Mouffe, 2000). Affective polarization erodes this foundation. Citizens increasingly perceive their opponents as morally corrupt and threatening, fostering a moralized “us versus them” dynamic (Iyengar et al., 2019). Populist rhetoric amplifies this hostility. Cas Mudde argues that populism constructs society as divided between a morally pure people and a corrupt elite (Mudde, 2004). Jan-Werner Müller extends this argument, contending that populist leaders deny the legitimacy of pluralistic opposition by claiming exclusive moral representation of “the people” (Müller, 2016). As mutual regard deteriorates, the possibility of productive dialogue and compromise diminishes. The democratic social contract, premised on civil solidarity and mutual respect, begins to unravel.

Institutional Distrust and the Decline of Democratic Legitimacy

Affective polarization not only undermines interpersonal trust but also corrodes trust in democratic institutions. Courts, electoral commissions, legislatures, and the media are increasingly perceived as partisan actors rather than neutral arbiters (Druckman et al., 2020). Partisan groups distrust institutions associated with their opponents, leading to the delegitimation of democratic authority. This erosion of institutional trust recalls Hobbes’ warning: absent confidence in sovereign authority, society risks descending into conflict and disorder (Hobbes, 1651/1994). In polarized democracies, institutional legitimacy becomes contingent on partisan affiliation, rendering political outcomes vulnerable to rejection by losing groups. As trust in institutions declines, the capacity of democracies to manage conflict through peaceful and lawful means is severely compromised.

Zero-Sum Politics and Democratic Dysfunction

Affective polarization fosters zero-sum thinking, where political competition is viewed as a struggle for survival rather than a contest between legitimate alternatives (Abramowitz & Webster, 2016). Rousseau’s concept of the general will, in which citizens transcend self-interest to pursue the common good, is subverted by partisan dynamics that equate compromise with betrayal. Political competition becomes a winner-takes-all battle, eroding the norms of cooperation and negotiation. Populist leaders exploit these divisions, framing political conflict in stark moral terms. As McCoy et al. (2018) argue, polarization becomes entwined with underlying social cleavages—ethnicity, religion, class—further entrenching divisions. Ní Threasaigh and Boler (2021) show how digital platforms amplify these dynamics through melodramatic storytelling that reinforces polarized identities. In such an environment, the possibility of building shared understanding or pursuing collective interests is greatly diminished.

Obstacles to Collective Problem-Solving

Effective democratic governance depends on the capacity for collective problem-solving. Whether addressing climate change, public health crises, or economic inequality, democracies require cooperation across partisan lines. Affective polarization makes such cooperation increasingly difficult. Partisan hostility leads to the refusal to work with opponents, even when collaboration would yield mutual benefit (Broockman et al., 2023). Locke’s vision of the social contract as a framework for collective governance is compromised when citizens prioritize partisan identity

over shared interests (Locke, 1689/1980). When opposing groups are delegitimized and compromise is stigmatized, the ability of democratic institutions to generate effective policy solutions is severely weakened.

Conclusion

Affective polarization presents a fundamental challenge to the democratic social contract. By corroding mutual regard, diminishing institutional trust, fostering zero-sum politics, and normalizing undemocratic practices, it threatens the stability and legitimacy of democratic governance. Without a renewed commitment to civil solidarity, agonistic pluralism, and institutional integrity, democracies risk succumbing to antagonistic conflict and democratic erosion. Rebuilding the foundations of the democratic social contract requires confronting polarization and restoring the norms and institutions essential for democratic life.

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Contribution 8: Towards a Resilient Social Contract: Stability, Inclusiveness, Continuity and Democracy in the Social Contract

Nathanaël Colin-Jaeger (American University of Paris, ncolinjaeger@aup.edu).

Introduction

The previous contributions highlight important contributions to social contract theories. Social contract theories refer to a normative framework answering the question of political rules' justification. However, in a more practical sense, *social contracts also refer to existing social arrangements and underlying agreements*. This second sense was, most notably, used by Charles Mills and Carol Pateman, who criticized the mystification operated by the first understanding of social contract theories to justify a *status quo*. Naturally, both theories may interact, as what should be done can be impacted by what is and constrained by feasibility. Conversely, the support for what may can be affected by the normative legitimacy of institutions. Therefore, contestation can be explained by the illegitimacy of current practices. As a general recapitulation, one can refer to the following Table 1.

	Normative social contract	Descriptive social contract
Purpose	Justifying social rules and obligations.	Explain how society functions and what the agreed-upon fundamental rules are.
Thinkers	From Hobbes to more contemporary theories.	Mills, Pateman, and more generally, political scientists, and anthropologists.
Key focus	What should be?	How societies function.
Possible Applications	What theory of justice should be implemented?	How much is an existing social contract supported?

Table 1. Normative and Descriptive Social Contracts.

As such, one important aspect of the CO3 project is to study how these two aspects can interact fruitfully. Developing a theory featuring at the same time a democratic aspect, inclusiveness to new concerns, and continuity as a capacity of renegotiation entails empirical sensitivity, i.e., being sensitive to existing social contracts and contestations to modify the rules of the game. Yet, there are many ways to connect the normative and the descriptive and to work towards a model displaying a commitment to democratic governance, inclusiveness, and continuity. This contribution aims to

clarify the different problems faced by this approach and offers a first roadmap regarding how to answer them.

In this contribution, I unpack the conceptual problems facing a theory displaying inclusivity, continuity, and democratic features, especially for the stability of social contracts throughout time. The contribution presents two challenges: (a) the challenge of internal consistency, which consists of making coherent the set of dimensions displayed in the project – inclusiveness, continuity, and democratic participation; (b) the challenge of stability, since a continuous social contract theory based on the recognition of a diversity of interests may not be stable. I argue that an understanding of stability as resilience helps mitigate this issue.

Relevant literature

This contribution builds on the other contributions of this deliverable. Additionally, it refers to the literature on resilience. Resilience is a fuzzy concept, originally introduced in management (Coutu, 2002) and has become a buzzword in recent decades. As such, it is often mixed with other concepts, such as robustness, stability, sustainability, or even antifragility. Anderson (2015), Walker (2020) and Canizeras et al. (2021) offer valuable clarification of the concept. Following Walker (2020), we can therefore define resilience as follows:

Resilience is in fact the ability to adapt and change, to reorganize, while coping with disturbance. It is all about changing in order not to be changed. A resilient system responds to a disturbance by changing the relative amounts of its different parts and how they interact, thereby changing the way it functions.

Resilience supposes change while conserving an identity at the level of the system. Let me exemplify what resilience is with an example from an ecological system, i.e., a forest. A forest, let us call it the Evergreen Forest, is a resilient ecosystem that has adapted to periodic wildfires, climate shifts, and human interaction over centuries. Its resilience comes from its response diversity, with a mix of tree species—such as pines and oaks—each with different tolerances to drought, pests, and fire. Regular exposure to disturbances, including controlled burns, prevents catastrophic wildfires and maintains ecosystem balance. The forest's modular connectivity, with its patchwork of old-growth trees, young saplings, and open meadows, helps limit the spread of disease and pests. It also has a quick response to shocks, as decomposers recycle nutrients from fallen trees, and deep-rooted plants access water during droughts. When necessary, the ecosystem demonstrates an ability to transform, shifting toward more drought-tolerant species to adapt to climate change. Its resilience is further supported by cross-scale management, where local communities, conservationists, and policymakers work together to sustain biodiversity and regulate resource use. Instead of attempting to control every variable, the forest is guided, not steered, allowing natural processes to shape its future while mitigating extreme threats.

As the Evergreen Forest, political systems can be resilient if they display similar features, such as response diversity, exposure to disturbance, modular connectivity, ability to transform, and cross-scale management. Colin-Jaeger (2024) has recently applied these concepts to federal structures. An important aspect of the CO3 project will be to develop the resiliency aspect of a European Social Contract to show how it can help to make its features consistent.

The Challenges for a Continuous, Democratic, and Inclusive Social Contract.

The leading challenge is to develop a social contract theory that retains its normative features, i.e., justifying a set of overarching social and political rules, while being continuous and democratic. This poses a conundrum: *how can a theory be at the same time open to change and renegotiation and yet determinate?*

Two problems are worth noticing: (i) the problem of internal consistency: Are the different features of the CO3 theory consistent with one another? (ii) the problem of stability: Do the different features of the CO3 theory produce a stable social contract? The following section explores these two problems.

First, the different dimensions of the project ought to be clarified: inclusivity, democracy, and continuity are broad terms. Inclusivity, in particular, needs to be refined. In political and ethical theory, it refers to the systematic expansion of participation in decision-making processes to previously excluded individuals, groups, or entities. It is both a descriptive and normative concept, capturing historical trends of inclusion and serving as a criterion for evaluating the legitimacy of political institutions. Inclusivity has traditionally been linked to democratic theory, where it is associated with principles of justice, equal representation, and recognition (Young, 2000). However, in global governance and environmental ethics, inclusivity raises challenges about the scope of the political community and the moral basis for extending participation beyond traditional state structures. Two key principles shape contemporary debates on inclusivity:

1. The *all-subjected principle* asserts that anyone subjected to a governance structure should have a voice in its decisions (Abizadeh, 2008). This principle is particularly relevant for migration policies and global justice debates, as it challenges the exclusion of non-citizens from political participation.
2. The *all-affected interests principle*, on the other hand, argues that political inclusion should extend to all individuals whose interests are significantly shaped by a given policy (Goodin, 2007). This principle has been central to discussions on transnational democracy and climate governance, where decisions made in one jurisdiction have far-reaching global effects.

The challenge for contemporary political theory is to refine these principles to account for non-traditional subjects of political inclusion, such as future generations, or non-human entities (e.g., nature). Scholars such as Graham-Smith (2003) have argued for a "deliberative ecological democracy," where non-human nature is represented through institutional mechanisms that allow for its interests to be politically articulated. These developments suggest that inclusivity is not simply a matter of adding more voices to existing frameworks but of fundamentally restructuring political representation to address global and intergenerational justice. Yet, how inclusive should a framework be? Inclusivity can indeed be tense with other features of the theory, especially the democratic component. Typically, including too much runs the risk of going against democratic decision-making procedures while including too little may run the risk of not taking into consideration valuable complaints about social order.

Likewise, democracy is a broad term: phenomena such as voting, political competition, political contestation (in the form of demonstration, associative lobbying, referenda), and public deliberation

are all democratic activities. All these phenomena are variously responsive to diverse interests. It is well-established, for instance, that majority voting in democracies can produce a tyranny of the majority and exclude minority interests. As a result, the feeling of being poorly represented fuels disaffection with democracy in Europe (Colin-Jaeger and Reed, 2025). Given the scope of the CO3 project and the focus on continuity, combined with the growing dissatisfaction with representative institutions witnessed throughout Europe, democracy should be understood as open to internal contestation for the institutions to be more responsive to diverse interests. As announced in D3.1, part of the consortium work will consist of exploring the potentialities of deliberative experiments in rejuvenating democratic institutions. Recently, Dryzek and Niemeyer (2019) argued in favor of citizens' deliberations in mini-publics and conventions as a fruitful way to engage with new challenges such as Climate Change – *contra* the view that such important challenges require a return to authoritarianism. Democracy aligns positively with inclusiveness when it encourages the expression of minority views and non-represented interests with specific institutions.

Finally, the continuous aspect requires that existing social contracts are open to renegotiation based on the recognition of overlooked interests and new challenges. At least two distinct mechanisms can be at play:

1. *Recognition of injustices.* Some views may have been excluded from the social agreement, which is what was developed by Pateman (1988) and Mills (1997). Contestation – the most famous example being the Civil Rights Movement in the United States – and a struggle for recognition can put these interests at the forefront and change the status quo. Existing and more or less stable institutions can therefore be unequal and unjust because the apparent universality and abstraction of rights and laws implicitly favor one group over another. As a matter of fact, and as is developed in D2.2, most social contracts in history have been built on the (implicit or explicit) exclusion of some interests. Recognizing injustices leads to substantial modification of the rules of the game. Most notably, it may call for the institutionalization of new rights but could also justify compensation and reparations for past injustices.
2. *New challenges.* New challenges may question existing social agreement, even though these are not characterized by injustices generating contestation and struggles for recognition. Climate Change, for instance, calls for integrating new concerns in social agreement, such as a concern for future generations, or ecosystems. The call for an eco-social contract, presented in another contribution in this deliverable, illustrates this tendency. Likewise, important events, such as geopolitical tensions (as illustrated contemporarily with the tensions between the EU and Russia, or even with the United States) can question existing arrangements and require structural changes.

Continuity is correlated with democratic participation and inclusiveness – as argued in another contribution of this deliverable “Taking the Mapping Seriously”. However, the connection with the different concepts should be developed. Indeed, renegotiation may reflect different bargaining powers. O’Connor (2024) demonstrated how bargaining could reflect inequalities in power within a society, at the expense of minority groups. More generally, the theories of Buchanan (1975) and Gauthier (1986) exemplify how bargaining theories reflect unequal starting situations. One important aspect of the CO3 project is to show how a democratic and inclusive process should cope with internal struggles for recognition and new challenges, without falling back on authoritarian manners to conduct change and new forms of discrimination.

Inclusivity, democratic participation, and continuity seem correlated, but work is still needed to show exactly how to connect these concepts into a coherent theory. Significant lessons can be learned from the theoretical work presented in this deliverable and the more empirical work conducted in Work Package 3 and 4, to bridge the gap between the normative and the descriptive understanding of social contracts. However, another important problem is the one of stability.

Second, even if the different features of the CO3 project are consistent, they may not generate a stable social contract. To start with, it should be noted that there is no natural alignment between the descriptive understanding (“What is the social contract of this country?”) and the normative understanding of social contract theories (“What is the condition for legitimate social institutions?”). The fact that these two domains are analytically distinct implies that an existing social contract may be unfair and yet stable. Conversely, a normatively appealing social contract might be unstable. Hobbes (1651) viewed political stability as a normatively appealing feature, and ensured, in his theory, that political legitimacy was never shared. Locke (1688), in another fashion, thought that an unjust and illegitimate ruling would spur contests and resistance, such that it could not be maintained in the long run. For many reasons, Hobbes’ answer is no longer appealing – especially when it does not guarantee any democratic rights for contestation – while Locke’s hope is unrealistic. Many countries’ social contracts might be stable without meeting any substantial criterion of legitimacy – they may disregard minorities’ interests, have a caste system, and have flawed principles. Conversely, some social contracts may be legitimate normatively and unstable empirically, for instance when they are being challenged by misinformation and foreign intrusion in the public sphere. Rawls (1993) faces explicitly this issue of stability and develops a theory of public reasons to ensure that every individual within a well-ordered society (i.e., a society based on the principle of justice) would have reasons to support the public ruling. However, Rawls’ answer to the problem of stability depends on fundamental presuppositions, such as reasonableness, which assumes away part of the deep diversity regarding political concepts (Gaus, 2022). Hence, it is essential to develop a theory that is more sensitive to empirical diversity and disagreements within societies to reach stability.

Developing such a theory faces an important difficulty, the so-called diversity paradox:

Diversity Paradox: the more inclusive regarding diverse perspectives, the less likely to reach an agreement, hence the less likely the stability of the social contract (Moehler, 2024).

Inclusivity leads to the recognition of diversity and the recognition of diversity within the democratic decision-making procedure, but then it impairs the possibility of having agreed-upon renegotiation of social agreement. This paradox is the reason why social contract theories usually make heavy use of counterfactual hypothetic agreements normalizing individuals’ interests and preferences. Impartiality and consensus – leading to social stability – seem to *require* the restriction of diversity.

Towards an Impossibility Square: Trade-offs and Leading Problems.

Taking the two issues of the previous section seriously, the difficulty lies in reconciling four different aspects of social contract theories, which are not usually associated. We obtain the following “impossibility square”, Graph. 1.

The impossibility should not be overstated, but more broadly be considered as clarifying a set of difficulties that should be faced by the CO3 theory. The section below proposes to understand stability as resilience to circumvent the alleged impossibility.

Graph. 1: Impossibility Square for a Continuous, Inclusive, Democratic and Stable Social Contract.

Different trade-offs are presented in this Graph, and are well depicted by the following trade-offs, featuring mostly a tension between continuity and stability:

1. **More Inclusivity & Democratization → Less Stability:** As more voices and interests are incorporated, decision-making becomes more complex, as stated by the Diversity Paradox.
2. **More Stability & Continuity → Less Democratization:** Highly stable and continuous systems may resist democratic reforms to preserve the status quo. Changes may be conducted by an enlightened elite or an authoritarian government facing new challenges.
3. **More Democratization & Stability → Less Continuity:** Frequent shifts in governance due to democratic processes can disrupt long-term stability and policy continuity.
4. **More Continuity & Inclusivity → Less Stability:** While long-standing inclusive policies promote representation, they may create tensions that threaten overall stability, as a capacity to maintain a social order generating sustained agreement.
5. **More Democratization & Continuity → Less Inclusivity:** Long-lasting democratic structures may entrench majority rule, sidelining minority voices over time.

The most important issues arise with a strict conception of stability defined as a substantial agreement on a set of principles everyone agrees with. Stability, therefore, entails a *static agreement* with the rules of the existing social contract. This requisite of social contract theories is often coined

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as reflecting the fact that a social contract should consist of an equilibrium. Shaefer (2023), indeed, points out that most contemporary theories of the social contract – most notably influenced by Rawls (1971) – think of social contract as equilibrium, because they assume that a well-ordered society is self-sustaining and generates its own support over time. Social contract theories would seek to attain a “fix point”. However, this is not realistic for Shaefer, who contends that we should understand stability not as an equilibrium, but as a capacity to maintain desirable properties despite constant change.

A theory valuing inclusiveness, democratization, and continuity ought to adopt a *dynamic understanding of stability*.

Stability as Resilience: Solving the Impossibility Square?

A resilience-based approach to the social contract provides a sophisticated response to Schaefer’s critique of equilibrium-oriented social contract theories and our Impossibility Square. In this section, I show how understanding stability as resilience helps alleviate the different difficulties encountered by the project, implying to development of an empirically informed approach to studying social contract theories. In what follows, I focus on the general features of resilience which help develop the project. Five features are important to emphasize:

1. *Robustness Over Equilibrium*. The primary distinction between equilibrium-based and resilience-based approaches is the emphasis on robustness rather than sameness. Traditional social contract frameworks assume that institutions, once optimally designed, will perpetuate themselves without significant modification. However, a resilience-based approach acknowledges that the social contract must be continuously recalibrated to remain responsive to shifting conditions and internal contestations. Core principles such as fairness, inclusiveness, and democratic participation must be upheld, yet their practical implementation must remain flexible and adaptive. This approach aligns with insights from ecological resilience theory, which prioritizes long-term adaptability over rigid institutional preservation (Walker, 2020).
2. *Adaptive Institutions*. In a resilient social contract, institutions must be structurally flexible to respond effectively to emerging challenges without descending into disorder. Political and legal systems should enable incremental, iterative reform, allowing for policy adjustments that account for evolving circumstances rather than presuming the permanence of a particular institutional arrangement. Resilience is thus distinct from mere institutional durability; rather than preserving an existing order at all costs, it seeks to guide institutional change in ways that maintain core normative commitments. This can be done, for instance, by using deliberative experiments to modify significant parts of the existing social contract, as a way to channel diverse insights and produce inclusive policies (Dryzek and Niemeyer, 2019). This necessitates governance structures that are open to contestation and continuous revision, ensuring justice remains responsive to societal evolution.
3. *Pluralism*. A crucial aspect of resilient systems is that they are fueled by diversity. Much like in ecological systems, where biodiversity enhances an ecosystem’s ability to withstand shocks, institutional pluralism fosters resilience by enabling governance systems to absorb and adapt to disruptions. However, such a framework remains to be developed for social contract theories, since a pluralistic framework ought to be legitimized on some alternative basis.

4. *Feedback loops and learning mechanisms.* A resilient social contract should integrate continuous feedback mechanisms to assess their effectiveness and make necessary adjustments. Democracy in its many forms and mechanisms (elections, public deliberation, association, contestations) allows for such feedback mechanisms to operate. Developing and building efficient feedback mechanisms is crucial for the system as a whole to learn from contestations and challenges.
5. *Disequilibrium.* A resilience-based approach embraces disequilibrium as an intrinsic aspect of societal progress. Rigid adherence to rules can suppress legitimate contestation and emergent concerns. In contrast, resilience-oriented justice systems recognize that uncertainty and disruption can serve as catalysts for transformation. The proper issue is then to allow transformation without leading to systemic collapse.

These core features offer a starting point for a resilient social contract theory. It needs to be refined empirically – with case studies from EU countries –, and conceptually – since these features are general and leave open many possibilities to be developed further.

However, applying these broad principles, we can already suggest some general learning. For instance, rather than striving for universal consensus on a single conception of justice, resilient societies recognize that pluralism necessitates provisional, adaptive solutions capable of evolving in response to contested norms and emerging values. This suggests that a social contract should above all focus on the condition for various concepts of politics to co-exist, rather than focus on one specific conception. The set of feasible options ought not be chosen abstractly, when applied to particular objects such as the EU, but fueled by the history and specificities of the countries. As Habermas (1987) put it, modernity, defined by the ideals of reason, democracy and human emancipation, is still very much an “unfinished project”, which can be developed based on existing institutions, practices, and ideals. For instance, political systems could integrate deliberative democratic mechanisms—such as citizens' assemblies, participatory budgeting, and deliberative mini-publics—to ensure that evolving justice principles remain grounded in collective decision-making rather than imposed by entrenched elites.

Conclusion

This contribution explored the theoretical and practical challenges of constructing a social contract that is at once democratic, inclusive, continuous, and stable. It has emphasized the need to bridge the gap between normative and descriptive approaches to social contract theory, recognizing that theoretical justifications for political rules must be informed by real-world social arrangements and contestations. A key challenge identified is achieving internal consistency—ensuring that inclusivity, democracy, and continuity can coexist without undermining each other—and maintaining stability, as a continuously evolving social contract may struggle to sustain broad social support over time.

The analysis put forward one central problem, which is illustrated with the Impossibility Square, characterized by a multiplicity of trade-offs across the four dimensions endorsed by the CO3 project. Most notably, the tension between a continuous aspect, feeding in the representation of diverse interests in a democratic process, and the stability of a social contract, is pervasive.

To address these challenges, this contribution proposes to understand stability as resilience rather than equilibrium. Unlike equilibrium-based theories, resilience emphasizes adaptability, robustness, and institutional flexibility, allowing political systems to absorb shocks while maintaining their core values. Resilient social contracts must incorporate feedback loops, pluralism, and mechanisms for incremental reform to remain responsive to changing societal conditions. This perspective aligns with insights from ecological resilience theory, suggesting that political systems should be designed to guide transformation rather than resist it.

However, significant theoretical and empirical work remains to be done. It is crucial, in particular, to develop the connection between this conceptual framework and empirical works conducted in case studies in European countries.

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